

CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

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D10.1 Validation of the CRISTAL project using the Validation Framework

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable
transport infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/ Term	Description
AE	Acoustic Emission (for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates)
AES	Acoustic Emission System (for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates)
AIPo	Agenzia Interregionale per il Fiume Po (Italian infrastructure operator for the Po river)
AIS	Automatic Identification System
BMC	Business Model Canvas
BN	Bayesian Network (a probabilistic graphical model)
BOOSTLOG	Project Name (a project referenced in Task 10.5)
CPTs	Conditional Probability Tables
DAG	Directed Acyclic Graph (the graphical structure of a Bayesian Network)
DM	Data Management
DT	Digital Twin
EPCIS	Electronic Product Code Information Services (a global GS1 standard)
EuRIS	European River Information System
FBG	Fibre Bragg Grating
FOS	Fibre Optic Sensor system (for riverbed monitoring)
GSM	Global System for Mobile communications
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPR	Ground Penetrating Radar
IV	Infrastrutture Venete (Italian infrastructure waterways operator in the Veneto region)
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
IWW	Inland Waterway
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
LoRa	A physical proprietary radio communication technique (from "long range")
LSP	Logistics Service Provider
LTE	Long-Term Evolution (a standard for high-speed wireless communication)
Micro-SHM	A proprietary standalone acoustic emission (AE) system
ML	Machine Learning

MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (a lightweight, publish-subscribe messaging protocol)
NPV	Net Present Value
PLB	Pencil Lead Brake
R&I	Research and Investment
RIS	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (in wireless communications)
RIS	River Information Systems
ROI	Return On Investment
SB	Smart Buoy
SCBA	Social Cost-Benefit Analysis
SCMS	Synchro-modal Corridor Management System
SI	Sustainability Index
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar (for IWW assets' structures)
TEU	Twenty-foot Equivalent Unit (a cargo unit)
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VNF	Voies Navigables de France (the infrastructure operator for the French pilot)
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1 Introduction

The CRISTAL project developed and tested within its three pilots a significant number of innovative solutions aimed to contribute towards increasing the performance and attractiveness of inland waterway transport (IWT) in Europe. These include:

- Sensor-based technologies:
 - Acoustic Emission (AE) system for health monitoring of lock gates;
 - Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) system for inspecting the assets' structures;
 - Intelligent Smart Buoy (SB) system for monitoring key parameters that affect the navigability;
 - Fibre Optic Sensor (FOS) system for riverbed monitoring.
- Digital systems/platforms:
 - Synchro-modal Corridor Management System;
 - Digital Twin.
- Innovative Business and Governance Models.

In addition to the above, each pilot has tested a series of state-of-the-art commercially available technologies and technical solutions (pilot specific “own initiatives”) to determine their feasibility for novel applications in the IWT sector selected according to the specific situation of the referenced inland waterway.

All these innovations and new applications have been tested in three pilots deployed in three countries: Italy, France and Poland. The pilots delivered complex sets of results comprising data collected on site, observations, different digital files, expert opinions (as responses to questionnaires and/or surveys), etc.

CRISTAL outcomes have had to be further analysed and evaluated for validating the project's innovative solutions and applications tested in the pilots. Therefore, Work Package 10 (WP10 Validation) was specifically dedicated to this scope, and this deliverable report presents its overall findings. Due to the significant diversity of project results, a complex and comprehensive **validation framework** was developed throughout WP10, which comprises different methodologies and approaches employed by WP10 tasks for addressing four core validation aspects:

1. **Technology Evaluation:** Determining if/how technologies meet performance criteria and determine readiness levels.
2. **Business Models Viability:** Assessing the ability of models (defined via Business Model Canvases, BMCs) to sustainably identify, deliver, and capture value.
3. **Operational Performance:** Defining a common operational framework of KPIs to assess deployment quality and identify barriers.
4. **Sustainability Impact:** Assessing performance with respect to economic, environmental, and social pillars of sustainability.

The evaluation of the CRISTAL innovative solutions for their full or partial validation was the crucial final activity in the project, therefore, deliverable D10.1, which reports the overall outcomes of WP10 that was dedicated to this scope, is a complex document that addresses multiple aspects and facets, from technical ones to business, operations and sustainability. Based on all of these, the General Framework for Validation was confirmed, and it is recommended as a blueprint that may enable future IWW innovation projects to systematically structure their evaluation and

validation process, ensuring they align technical capability with commercial viability, social acceptance, and EU policy goals.

1.2 Mapping CRISTAL outputs

Table 1 provides an overview of the alignment of the document to the formal deliverable and corresponding tasks' descriptions included in the Grant Agreement (GA) along with the relevant justifications regarding how the WP10 objectives have been achieved.

Table 1: Alignment of D10.1 contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & tasks descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D10.1 Validation of the CRISTAL project using the Validation Framework	Report on the CRISTAL project using the Validation Framework in order to provide resilience validation and technology evaluated against WP3 developed crisis event scenarios.	Section 2 Overall Approach Section 3 Technical Assessment and Validation of CRISTAL Technologies Section 6 Sustainability Validation Section 7 General Framework for Validation of Inland Waterway Interventions	D10.1 presents in detail the evaluation of technical solutions; these were considered in the overall approach (§2), assessed technically (§3), and then sustainability and resilience aspects were addressed (§6). Both of these key aspects have been eventually integrated in the general framework for validation (§7).
	Confirm business models developed in WPs 6-9 and pilot performance versus KPIs and sustainability impact.	Section 4 Validation of the Business Models Section 5 Evaluation of Pilot Operational Performance Section 6 Sustainability Validation	Business models initially developed in WP4 have been reviewed and confirmed with respect to pilots' outcomes and living labs results (§4). The operational performance of CRISTAL innovative solutions was evaluated considering the actual pilots' results vs KPIs initially defined in WP1 (§5), and then sustainability impact was addressed (§6). These specific assessments have been also integrated in the general framework for validation (§7).
TASKS			
Task 10.1 Technology	Determining the level of technology	Section 3 Technical Assessment and	Sensor-based technologies that have been developed within the

validation for application to Digital Twins and Pilot Cases	<p>transfer and performance criteria for the proposed application. Validation against the performance requirements. The validation will assess the technologies developed, proposed and confirmed in WP2</p>	Validation of CRISTAL Technologies	<p>project were evaluated, including their interaction with the digital ones, especially with the DT. Technical requirements and KPIs have been initially defined, to allow for the design of meaningful and realistic test plans for each technology (Annex 1). The extent to which each technology meets the requirements and KPIs was determined and conclusions and recommendations have been drawn.</p>
Task 10.2 Business Model Validation	<p>This Task will validate the business models, as defined in WPs 6 thru' 9, to be deployed in the pilot cases. The business models will be validated regarding their ability to sustainably identify value, deliver value and capture reward....</p>	Section 4 Validation of the Business Models	<p>The validation of business models has been carried out for the key innovations, i.e., the sensor-based systems and digital solutions. The validation process was structured around the BMC methodology, the primary validation mechanisms were a series of stakeholder-centric Living Lab workshops supplemented by Social Cost-Benefit Analysis. The validation of BMCs confirmed the core value propositions related to improving infrastructure maintenance and navigational safety for all technologies.</p>
Task 10.3 Pilot Operational Performance versus KPIs	<p>This task will define a common operational framework of KPIs to assess the pilots using the most appropriate common KPIs defined in WPs 1, 3, 6-9. We will assess deployment level achieved and performance versus the framework in order to ensure the quality of the pilot operation and outcomes in the</p>	Section 5 Evaluation of Pilot Operational Performance	<p>This assessment focused on gaining specific insights into operational experiences, measuring performance in practice, quantifying efficiency improvements, and predicting the broader adoption potential of the CRISTAL technologies. The validation methodology employed a standardised questionnaire and semi-structured interviews with infrastructure operators, to gather empirical support for shifts in operational procedures and strategic decision-making by integrating Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) from previous work packages.</p>

	scope of the project...		
Task 10.4 Sustainability Validation	The task will focus on the assessment of the sustainability performance of the tested Pilot Cases by comparing pre- and post pilot operation data in terms of the three sustainability pillars, economic, environmental and social. To perform this task, a Sustainability Validation tool will be developed...	Section 6 Sustainability Validation	A coherent, uncertainty-aware validation of CRISTAL's sustainability performance across the pilot sites was carried out. A Sustainability Validation Tool based on an elicitation-driven Bayesian Network (BN) was developed and used for this scope. Processed results show a predominance of favourable outcomes re. key aspects such as Operational Efficiency, Modal Shift Rate, Infrastructure Resilience, CO2 Reduction and Energy Consumption.
Task 10.5 General Framework for Validation of IWW Interventions	This task will take the insights and approaches developed in 10.1 to 10.4, develop a common approach beyond the CRISTAL pilots and innovations, in order to deliver a general framework as the basis of future IWW research and innovation, which will be provided as a methodology...	Section 7 General Framework for Validation of Inland Waterway Interventions	The formalised General Framework for Validation integrates the requirements for systematic assessment across technical, operational, commercial, and sustainability domains. Its core components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rigorous technical evaluation. • Use of the Living Lab (LL) methodology. • Iterative Business Model Canvas (BMC) refinement. • A standardised framework of operational KPIs coupled with the definition of clear baseline scenarios. • Application of the Bayesian Network (BN) methodology to integrate diverse data sources and expert judgment.

1.3 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The document D10.1, titled "Validation of the CRISTAL project using the Validation Framework," is structured around the five principal tasks of Work Package 10 (WP10). Following this initial Section 1 (the Executive Summary), the document details in Section 2 Overall Approach on Evaluation and Validation the objectives of validation, the targets of validation, and the specific activities that have been considered, in line with the WP10 specific tasks.

The core structure comprises five major sections (§3 to §7), each corresponding to a Work Package 10 task (Task 10.1 through Task 10.5). Each individual task chapter generally contains some similar subheadings, such as “Context”, “Methodology”, “Findings” and “Conclusions”, comprising specific content for each task and section. Also, each section includes specific headings that have been associated to particular work carried out in the specific tasks.

Section 3 Technical Assessment and Validation of CRISTAL Technologies presents the outcomes of Task 10.1, with a clear focus on the rigorous technical evaluation of the technologies for their full or partial validation, which is a key pre-requisite for further implementation and market uptake.

Section 4 Validation of the Business Models reports the work undertaken within Task 10.2 for the validation of business models of the key innovations developed within the CRISTAL project, and its results. The validation process was structured around the Business Model Canvas (BMC), a methodology used to test the viability of how each innovation could create, deliver, and capture value.

Section 5 Evaluation of Pilot Operational Performance presents the work conducted under Task 10.3, which was dedicated to the operational validation of technologies implemented within the CRISTAL project. This assessment focused on gaining specific insights into operational experiences, measuring performance in practice, quantifying efficiency improvements, and predicting the broader adoption potential of the CRISTAL technologies.

Section 6 Sustainability Validation reports the outcomes of Task 10.4, which produced a coherent, uncertainty-aware validation of CRISTAL’s sustainability performance across the Italy, France and Poland pilot sites. To translate heterogeneous evidence into a single decision-ready quantity, a Sustainability Validation Tool was developed, based on an elicitation-driven Bayesian Network (BN).

Section 7 General Framework for Validation of Inland Waterway Interventions presents the outcomes of Task 10.5, which synthesised the validation methods and findings from Tasks 10.1 through 10.4 into a formalised General Framework for Validation of IWW Interventions.

This document provides a blueprint for advancing future IWW research and innovation beyond the CRISTAL project. The framework integrates the requirements for systematic assessment across technical, operational, commercial, and impact domains.

In addition to the core part of the document (§1 to §7), seven annexes have been included at the end to provide further relevant details pertaining to WP10 tasks and subsequent sections of this report, as well as clear evidence of work carried out and how the different specific methodologies have been applied.

2. Overall Approach on Evaluation and Validation

2.1 Objective of Validation

The objective of Work Package 10 (WP10) was to provide a generic Validation Framework for the CRISTAL project. This objective encompassed five main tasks (Task 10.1 through 10.5), each having a specific purpose:

1. **Technology Evaluation:** Task 10.1 focused on technology validation and aimed to evaluate CRISTAL technologies against crisis event scenarios and cascading effects of climate change to ensure the resilience of critical infrastructures. This task was meant to provide resilience validation and technology evaluation. It specifically covered the validation of innovative core technologies, i.e., the Acoustic Emission System (AE), Fibre Optic Sensor System for Riverbed Monitoring (FOS), Smart Buoys (SB), and the Digital Twins (DTs).
2. **Business Models Confirmation:** Task 10.2 was explicitly purposed to confirm the business models developed in earlier work packages (WPs 6 through 9) by assessing their capacity to sustainably "identify value, deliver value, and capture reward". This task involved applying the Business Model Canvas methodology and conducting quantitative stakeholder polling to move from perceived value to realised value.
3. **Pilot Performance Assessment:** Task 10.3 aimed to measure the pilot performance against Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). This required defining a common operational framework of KPIs to assess the quality and outcomes of the pilot operations, while identifying potential barriers and coping strategies.
4. **Sustainability Impact Assessment:** Task 10.4 focused on assessing the sustainability performance of the tested pilot cases by comparing pre- and post-operation data across economic, environmental, and social pillars. This task included developing a sustainability validation tool that integrated outputs from all other WP10 tasks to provide an accurate estimation of CRISTAL's overall sustainability.
5. **Framework Generalisation:** Task 10.5 intended to generalise the insights and approaches developed in Tasks 10.1 through 10.4. The purpose was to deliver a general framework, presented as a methodology, guidebook, and accompanying spreadsheets, that would serve as a basis for future Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) research and innovation beyond the CRISTAL pilots and innovations.

2.2 Targets of Validation

The CRISTAL project defined thirteen initial Key Results (KRs) across four objective areas, formulated to meet the primary strategic goals: increasing the Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) modal share by a minimum of 20%, improving reliability by 80%, and assuring 50% IWT capacity even during extreme weather events.

Objective Area 1: Development of pathway towards 20% market share increase and 80% reliability

- **Key Result 1 (KR 1):** The project stipulated roadmaps for necessary developments and administrative and regulatory frameworks, which included developing business and governance models aimed at achieving the targeted 20% market share growth. This activity

involved identifying information, infrastructure needs, data exchange, and operational management requirements.

- **Key Result 2 (KR 2):** CRISTAL aimed to implement a synchro/multi-modal corridor management system designed for use by all involved actors, including public authorities, logistics/mobility operators, and passengers. The system intended to ensure on-time shipments (and continuity of passenger transport) via IWT in a minimum of 80% of calamity situations.
- **Key Result 3 (KR 3):** The objective involved the successful establishment of governance, business models, finance structures, technological developments, and organisational models intended to ensure sustainable improvements for implementing the Good Navigation Status.

Objective Area 2: Use of state-of-the-art technologies to increase operability and resilience, assuring 50% capacity during extreme weather situations

- **Key Result 4 (KR 4):** The project mandated the development of a real-time monitoring system focused on water levels, hydrological conditions, and infrastructure maintenance, including a River Information Services (RIS)-Layer. Infrastructure managers planned to use the collected data in conjunction with their Decision Support System (DSS) RIS-Layer to determine the level of water under keel, supporting X2V (infrastructure to vehicle) functionality.
- **Key Result 5 (KR 5):** The plan included developing and piloting a digital twin that incorporated real-time data and weather data. This system intended to provide infrastructure early warning and maintenance capabilities, supplying derived Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to judge capacity during normal and extreme weather events and to support corridor management.
- **Key Result 6 (KR 6):** CRISTAL intended to create platforms for stakeholders with the purpose of sharing insights gained and integrating these stakeholders into the project.

Objective Area 3: Implementation of technologies and strategy in the pilot regions for Europe-wide roll-out

- **Key Result 7 (KR 7):** The consortium targeted the completed application, testing, and validation of real-time measurement tools for actual water levels and IWT infrastructure maintenance and resilience. This focused on using novel subsurface inspection data to plan predictive maintenance and improve resilience within the three pilot regions.
- **Key Result 8 (KR 8):** The project sought the completed implementation, testing, and validation of the corridor management system, governance, and technology innovations across the three pilot areas.
- **Key Result 9 (KR 9):** CRISTAL planned for the completed implementation, testing, and validation of the digital twins specific to the three pilot regions: Poland, Italy, and France.

Objective Area 4: Exploitation on local as well as European level and beyond

- **Key Result 10 (KR 10):** The project intended to deliver a roadmap for IWT improvement focused on realising European Commission (EC) flagship developments, such as the EC IWT

Transaction Plan 2021-2027 and the EC Digital Inland Waterway Area (DINA)¹, at a strategic (European) level.

- **Key Result 11 (KR 11):** The plan required a roadmap for individual pilot regions intended to realise flagship developments at the pilot level.
- **Key Result 12 (KR 12):** CRISTAL set out a roadmap for individual stakeholders, such as engineers, assets managers, and logistics professionals, intended to realise flagship developments at the organisational level.
- **Key Result 13 (KR 13):** The project sought a roadmap for the financial sector intended to realise flagship developments, specifically aligned with the EC Taxonomy, incorporating the results of the "Maritime taxonomy".

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The initial Key Results (KRs) defined for the CRISTAL project transformed into Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) through a structured process across several work packages and tasks, culminating in performance assessment and validation.

The overarching goal of defining KPIs was to measure the success of CRISTAL's interventions against its high-level strategic objectives: increasing IWT modal share by a minimum of 20%, improving reliability by 80%, and assuring 50% capacity during extreme weather events.

KR-to-KPI Conversion Process, Tasks, and Deliverables:

1. KPI Definition and Selection (Task 1.2 reported in Deliverable D1.3):

- Work regarding KPIs started in Deliverable D1.1 and continued in Task 1.2. The core effort involved business process mapping and defining the main business processes within the three pilots, focusing on increasing the utilisation of inland navigation infrastructure.
- The KPI formulation process applied the concept of **leading and lagging KPIs**. Lagging (top-down) KPIs measured the results achieved by project completion, while Leading (bottom-up) KPIs supported research and development activities in the pilot sites.
- The outcome of Task 1.2 was a defined list of KPIs (such as Efficiency, Environmental, and Social indicators) from which the pilot site owners could choose the most suitable ones, allowing for the addition of individual KPIs based on regional circumstances.
- This initial set of KPIs, which included the transformation of KRs into measurable metrics, was selected specifically to be used to validate the performance and results of the pilots within **Task 10.3**. The overall KPI system included indicators related to the project's specific objectives and needs.
- Deliverable D1.3 reported the efforts undertaken in Task 1.2 regarding the KPI definition, summarising the input from pilots and other research projects that formed the basis for selecting suitable indicators for the three pilot sites and their associated Living Labs.

2. Framework Alignment and Technology-Specific KPIs (Reported in Deliverable D6.1 and D10.1 Annexes):

- Work Package 6 (WP6) coordinated the definition of the baseline and test plan, which involved meticulously detailing the assessment framework.
- Deliverable D6.1 presented the initial KPIs selected for measuring the effectiveness and success of the testing phase for each pilot. This chapter laid the foundation for an informed evaluation of the pilot's impact.

¹ Proposal COM/2024/33 for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Directive 2005/44/EC on harmonised river information services (RIS) on inland waterways in the Community.
<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52024PC0033>

- The Digital Twin (DT) Key Results, which included providing early warnings and maintenance systems to judge capacity (KR 5), translated into KPI analysis points such as judging **capacity during both normal and extreme weather events**. DTs provided data to judge capacity during both normal and extreme weather events and to support corridor management.
 - The technology KRs (e.g., KR 4: Real-time monitoring system of water levels) were converted into Functional and Non-Functional Requirements, and associated KPIs were defined within **Task 10.1**. For example, the Acoustic Emission System (AE) had functional requirements (e.g., detecting acoustic emissions related to structural anomalies) linked to measurable indicators and acceptance criteria derived from KPIs. Key parameters monitored for the Smart Buoys included depth accuracy, velocity accuracy, and temperature accuracy, and these served as KPI definitions to assess functional requirements.
- 3. Business Model and SCMS Integration (Task 4.3 and Task 10.2):**
- The Key Results related to the Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS) (KR 2) and DT (KR 5) became metrics within the preliminary **Social Cost-Benefit Analysis (SCBA)** framework developed in **Task 4.3**, as reported in Deliverable D4.3. The SCMS was designed to monitor and record operational choices for evaluation and KPI calculation.
 - The quantification method for the potential benefits and costs of CRISTAL solutions focused on the SCMS, integrating the costs and benefits of the upstream technologies (like FOS, AES, and Smart Buoys) and DTs. The SCBA calculated benefits based on factors like **reduction in waiting time** and **improvement of reliability** and capacity, which were benefits inherent in the original KRs.
 - Task 10.2, Business Model Validation, aimed to test the hypotheses embedded in the Business Model Canvases (BMCs). This task used the operational performance measured against KPIs from Task 10.3 to validate the *Value Propositions* and *Cost Structure* elements of the BMCs.
- 4. Final Operational Assessment (Task 10.3 and Final Deliverables):**
- Task 10.3 defined a common operational framework of KPIs to assess the pilots, ensuring the quality of the pilot operation and outcomes. It was in this task that the chosen KPIs (as elaborated in WP1, 3, 6-9) were used to measure pilot performance.
 - The results of this assessment were reported in deliverables associated with the pilots (such as D7.2, D8.2, and D9.2) and subsequently summarised within WP10 deliverables. For instance, Deliverable D7.2 contained a chapter focusing on the impact of the solutions adopted with respect to the objectives of the CRISTAL project, detailing the Italian pilot KPIs. Similarly, Deliverable D8.2 presented the impact assessment of the French pilot solutions and the KPIs achieved by these technologies. The Polish pilots explicitly assessed each voyage using the KPI framework.

KPIs were essential metrics used to measure deployment and performance. The initial KPI list was presented to the pilots to choose the most suitable ones, with the opportunity to add individual KPIs. As the project proceeded the KPIs expanded and also were used in certain pilots, work packages, tasks and deliverables. This is detailed further in Annex 7. Evolution of KPIs in the CRISTAL Project.

3. Technical Assessment and Validation of CRISTAL Technologies

3.1 Context

Work carried out in previous work packages of the CRISTAL project (WP2 and WP5) focused on developing sensor-based technologies for different applications in IWW environment, which would contribute towards achieving the high-level objectives of the project and the associated KPIs.

These technologies have been further deployed and tested in the project River Pilots (WP7, WP8 and WP9). In addition to the sensor-based technologies developed within the project, the pilots also considered, tested and assessed other technologies, including the digital ones developed within the project (the Digital Twin, DT, and the Synchro-modal Corridor Management System, SCMS), as well as pilots' "own initiatives", i.e., technologies that were of interest to stakeholders involved in the pilots (e.g., CEDRE system, French Buoys, cold ironing, smart bulletin, etc.).

The scope of Task 10.1 was to evaluate and validate the sensor-based technologies that have been developed within the project, including aspects concerning their interaction with the digital ones, especially with the DT.

3.2 CRISTAL Technologies to be Assessed and Validated

The sensor-based technologies developed in the CRISTAL projects are summarised further. The development of these technologies has been reported in detail in deliverable reports D2.1 (CRISTAL, 2022), D2.2 (CRISTAL, 2024) and D2.3 (CRISTAL, 2025a) of the CRISTAL project.

Acoustic Emission System for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates (AE)

The Acoustic Emission (AE) system developed by partner CERTH detects transient elastic waves generated by phenomena such as micro-cracking, frictional activity, and other structural responses, which may indicate existence or development of defects within lock gates. AE provides early-warning indicators and localisation of active damage sources, enabling condition-based maintenance and reduction of unplanned outages. The system consists of wideband piezoelectric AE sensors, low-noise preamplifiers, a multi-channel acquisition unit with precise time synchronisation, and a signal-processing pipeline for hit detection, feature extraction (e.g., amplitude, energy, RA value, i.e., the weighted sound reduction index for pink noise, average frequency), event clustering/localisation, and severity classification. Thereby, the output data usable by CRISTAL's Data Management (DM) and Digital Twin (DT) include event counts and rates, energy and frequency-based descriptors, source location estimates, and health indicators that can be supplied to and consumed by the DT/SCMS, or potentially links to other external interested stakeholder. The system uses developed proprietary libraries, which enable to detect the build-up of gate's microcracks in the vicinity of the sensors coming from possible metallic plastic deformations and, thereby, to provide an early warning of large failures caused by this buildup, and general out of the normal events like gate's pistons' failure, objects bouncing against the gates, precipitations at the bottom of the water lock trench obscuring the normal gate operation etc. The deviation from a normal operating space is an indication/prediction of upcoming gate failures. AE sensors are mounted on the gate and near the parts of the gate that are of interest to inspect, as shown in Figure 1. The AE sensors can be observed on the top of the gate, below the red magnetic holders.

Figure 1: AE sensors mounted on a lock gate

Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)

The radar-based non-destructive subsurface inspection system (SIR) was developed by partners EUMO and UNEW. It was designed for examination and inspection of inland waterways infrastructure assets, in particular to examine the subsurface condition of key structural assets, e.g., the sheer vertical concrete walls integral to lock infrastructure.

The use of this advanced technology to assess the integrity of the inspected assets and provide information on their condition would enable preventive and/or predictive maintenance. Therefore, the goal of using SIR technology is that, by enabling improved maintenance practices, to efficiently contribute toward improving the reliability and resilience of assets. The technology's description will be more detailed in D8.3.

The developed SIR system combines a bespoke physical hardware platform, comprising state-of-the-art radar technology integrated with a dedicated motorised positioning frame, and a software-driven data analytics workflow, responsible for converting raw radar measurement data into more intuitive 3D spatial profiles of subsurface Features of Interest (Fols), with a primary focus on the detection and characterisation of voids. The platform is operated by the crane and positioned over the lock wall (Figure 2a). A quadrant scanning begins with the radar antenna positioned at the upper-left corner of the frame, marked by the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) antenna (Figure 2b, yellow arrows showing the scanning sequences). Data collection is semi-automated. The operator initiates a scan by manually triggering Prism2 via keystroke, which starts data recording. After completing the quadrant scanning, the rig is re-positioned by the crane to another quadrant on the wall (Figure 2c).

Currently, visual inspections of lock chambers are carried out within scheduled maintenance activities, which can detect just a limited number of potential issues, and mostly surface ones. The SIR system uses state-of-the-art radar techniques designed for in-depth scanning (Ground Penetrating Radar, GPR), which is typically used for earthworks, masonry and concrete structure inspection, to detect, localise and profile features (i.e., structural anomalies) concealed within such subsurface media. Returned data can be analysed to determine both quantitative (e.g., depth, footprint, etc.) and qualitative (e.g., shape, complexity, composition, etc.) feature properties.

Figure 2: Data collection with SIR technology - procedure for lock walls

The SIR system was designed to allow semi-automated subsurface inspection of vertical and sloping walls or structures (such as lock walls and dams), as opposed to conventional GPR, which is manually operated and most frequently applied to horizontal surfaces (i.e., the ground).

Smart Buoys (SB)

The Smart Buoy (SB) system was developed by partner L-PIT. It is an integrated environmental monitoring and navigation support platform designed for inland waterways, which combines floating sensor nodes, bridge-mounted devices, vessel transponders, and a central server application into a unified architecture for real-time data collection, transmission, and analysis.

The SB system consists of **two functional sub-systems**:

1. Buoy-based sensing and communication – Each buoy is equipped with sensors that measure water depth, current velocity, temperature, tilt, and atmospheric conditions. It also receives data on bridge clearance via wireless links and detects vessel traffic through an Automatic Identification System (AIS) receiver. A sealed electronics insert houses the power supply, processing unit, and communication modules, ensuring durability in harsh river environments. Data is logged locally and transmitted in real time via Global System for Mobile Communications (GSM)/ LTE (Long-Term Evolution standard for high-speed wireless communication networks).

2. Backend infrastructure – A central server application ingests buoy data over the MQTT protocol (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport lightweight messaging protocol), processes it, and distributes it to external applications such as digital twin and smart canal management systems.

Figure 3: SB System structure and data flow

The SB prototype adapts standard 700 mm navigation buoys with modular electronics, including an STM32-based carrier board, Controller Area Network (CAN) interfaces, GNSS, and an LTE IoT module for remote data transmission.

Bridge-mounted devices use radar sensors to measure vertical clearance and broadcast it via AIS AtoN, while vessel transponders (e.g., NOMAD2 Class B) supply identity and position data to nearby buoys. Additional deck buoys support AIS testing.

All buoy data is sent over MQTT, with configuration files defining measurement cycles and communication parameters. Server-side software parses telemetry and events, distributing them to navigation authorities, research systems, and Electronic Product Code Information Services (EPCIS)-compliant long-term data platforms.

The SB system enhances safety and situational awareness in waterways by:

- Providing real-time hydrological and environmental data.
- Broadcasting bridge clearance information for vessel passage safety.
- Detecting and tracking vessel traffic.
- Supporting integration with external systems for predictive analysis, fleet management, and environmental monitoring.

Through modular design, robust communication, and energy-optimised operation, the SB system demonstrates a scalable and cost-effective approach to modernising the monitoring of inland waterway infrastructure.

Fibre Optic Sensor System for Riverbed Monitoring (FOS)

The FOS consists of a system equipped with Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors (small sensors

embedded in an optical fibre); FBG technology is highly mature and widely employed across diverse industrial sectors for critical applications. In the CRISTAL project, FBG technology was used to develop a submerged weighing platform. The advantage is that it uses a completely passive optical operating principle, eliminating the need for electrical power at the measurement point. In the CRISTAL project, the weighing platform features a straightforward mechanical design based on the bending plate principle, which reduces maintenance requirements. The weighing platform is intended to indirectly estimate the height of the sediments heap through the direct measurement of its weight.

Figure 4 illustrates the operating principle of the FOS. The top drawing shows a cross-section of the river and its riverbed, with an array of weighing pads (the red segments) installed slightly beneath the surface. These pads are connected in series by a fibre optic cable (dark-green line), which transmits signals from the FBG sensors embedded in the pads. The enlarged inset schematically depicts the force (weight) exerted by the sediments heap on a pad. The middle drawing represents the pad in its 'reference condition', i.e., with no load applied. For clarity, the plate is shown unburied, with its upper surface aligned with the riverbed; however, any load present in the installation setup can still be considered part of the reference condition. The bottom drawing illustrates the loaded condition, where the plate is activated (bent) under the weight of deposited sediments. The force acting on the pad is generated by the sediments' weight resting directly on the plate (with negligible non-vertical forces due to the muddy nature of the heap), thereby enabling the indirect estimation of the sediments heap height through the direct measurement of its weight.

Figure 4: Operating principle of FOS

Figure 5 shows the weighing plate prototype equipped with fibre optic sensor that was produced for laboratory testing. The concept drawing on the left shows the bending plate designed as the cover of a massive monolithic box; a gasket ensures a waterproof enclosure, while the fibre optic cable penetrates the structure and terminates in a breakout box. The fibres (not shown in the drawing) extend from the box and are routed to position the FBG sensors in the desired locations. The picture in the centre shows the weighing plate with the cover open, and the close-up view on the right shows the FBG sensors installed on the exposed surface of the bending plate.

Figure 5: FOS prototype produced for preliminary laboratory testing

3.3 Methodology for Technical Assessment and Validation

3.3.1 Approach and Method for the Evaluation and Validation of Technologies in the Overall Project's Context

An essential prerequisite for successfully evaluating and validating the technologies at technology readiness levels (TRL) expected at the end of the project is the quality and relevance of data and other information gathered within the pilot activities. Therefore, appropriate tests should be planned and carried out for each technology described in §3.2 and deployed on the pilot sites. The deployment of technologies, as well as the testing activities for collecting data necessary for their evaluation, are complex activities that require significant resources, therefore, in practice, they cannot be repeated during the project lifetime.

In order to ensure successful collection of data and information that would be used for evaluation and validation purposes, Task 10.1 considered an initial preparatory Phase 1 focused on establishing the technical requirements for the technologies and planning tests to generate the necessary data to evaluate the technologies. Following Phase One of Task 10.1, the tests were implemented in the pilots, and the results analysed by the Work Packages responsible for the pilots. Subsequently to this, Phase Two of Task 10.1 evaluated the technical implementation and performance of the technologies to establish the extent to which the technologies could be validated. A summary of this process is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Positioning of Task 10.1 activities within the project

Furthermore, the overall structure of Task 10.1, along with interactions with the other WPs with activities associated with Task 10.1, is shown in the diagram in Figure 7. The first step in the methodology for Phase One of T10.1 was to establish the technical requirements, and Key

Performance Indicators (KPIs) associated with those requirements, separately for each technology. These technical requirements were based on the intended scope of the intended function of the technology, how they would interact with and operate within the pilots, and considered the overall higher level requirements and KPIs for the project. Two main categories of technical requirements and KPIs were established for each technology - the first was the Functional Requirements and KPIs, and the second one comprised Non-Functional Requirements, which consist of a group of sub-categories, i.e., Operational, RAMS, Security, and Compatibility Requirements and KPIs.

Figure 7: Structure of Task 10.1 and interactions with the relevant WPs

The **Functional Requirements** are the core functions the technology must perform in order to fulfil the intended role and provide a solution to the technical problem it is intended to solve, the associated KPIs are generally the parameters and thresholds for the parameters used to evaluate how well the technology performs one or more of those functions. Generally, the functional requirements are specific to the intended role of the technology and therefore distinct between technologies.

The groups of sub-categorise of requirements that make up the **Non-Functional Requirements**, might have elements in common, or equivalent requirements between the different technologies, although the specifics of the requirements might be different, these are:

- **Operational Requirements** - Specify the characteristics the technology must have in order to be able to be operated in the intended environment, includes characteristics such as the operating environment the technology must tolerate, how it is to be deployed, transportability, and power requirements.
- **Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS) Requirements** - Specify the characteristics the technology must have in relation to it being in a state which enables it to perform the intended functions when needed, and be maintained in such a condition, in addition to doing so without causing harm to people, the environment, or other assets.
- **Security Requirements** - Specify the characteristics the technology must have on order to prevent unauthorised, or undetected, interference with the operation of the technology, or the data generated and communicated across the interfaces with the technology.
- **Compatibility Requirements** - Specify characteristics the technology must have on order

to interface with the pilot environment and systems, and other systems.

The KPIs for the Non-Functional requirements are similar in concept to those for the Functional Requirements, in that they are the indicators that are used to assess if the technology satisfies the requirements, however in the case of the Non-Functional requirements the character of these indicators is more likely to be simple criteria to be checked that the technology conforms with. Establishing the requirements and KPIs was led by the technology developers for each technology, in consultation with the operators of the pilot sites where the technology was to be tested. The requirements and KPIs are primarily focused on the testing, operation and evaluation of the prototype technologies in the pilots within the project, rather than the commercial full-scale deployment of the technologies.

Once the requirements and KPIs were established, the second step in the methodology for Phase One of T10.1 was to design a test programme for each technology to ensure that the testing of the technology generated the data required to assess the technology against the KPIs, and, therefore, determine the extent to which the technologies could be validated. This included defining the parameters that would need to be monitored and recorded during the testing, and, where necessary, developing specific test scenarios to ensure that the required conditions occurred during the tests to generate data on how the technology responded in those conditions. Individual scenarios might generate data relevant to the assessment of the technology against more than one KPI.

In the next phase, the technologies were tested in the pilots, according to the testing plans designed in Phase One of T10.1. An assessment of conditions and prerequisites in the pilots for implementing the testing of technologies, and of potential impacts of pilots on IWW environment was carried out, and the outcomes are reported in deliverable report D6.2 (CRISTAL, 2025b).

Following on from the implementation of technologies testing in the pilots, the second Phase of T10.1 was aimed to assessing the data from the tests and evaluating the functional and non-functional performance and characteristics of the technologies against the technical requirements and KPIs. This assessment considered both quantitative criteria and a more qualitative approach according to the intended scope of the technologies, and how well they fulfilled that role overall. In addition to comparing the outcomes against the requirements and KPIs, the suitability of the requirements and KPIs was also reviewed with respect to the practical experience in the pilots, and, where it became apparent that the requirements and KPIs could benefit from revision, this was noted.

3.3.2 Evaluation and Validation Planning for Acoustic Emission System for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates (AE)

According to the methodology described in the previous sub-section, the AE validation plan comprised the following steps: (i) consolidation of functional and non-functional requirements with KPIs; (ii) execution of the testing plan across pilots; (iii) analysis of results against acceptance criteria; and (iv) conclusions and recommendations.

A coherent set of functional and non-functional requirements was defined which maps each requirement to measurable indicators and verification activities. The functional specification comprises 6 requirements, with KPIs explicitly assigned to three of them. Representative functional items include:

- AE-FR-01: The system shall detect acoustic emissions related to structural anomalies;
- AE-FR-02: The system shall localise the source of emissions on the gate surface;

- AE-FR-03: The system shall log and timestamp acoustic events for post-analysis.

The non-functional specifications contain 19 requirements, of which 6 carry quantitative KPI targets. Examples of non-functional aspects addressed are:

- AE-NFR-OP-01: The system shall be portable and easily installable and dismantlable;
- AE-NFR-OP-02: The AE system ought to be flexible enough to accommodate various use cases linked to various types of lock gates;
- AE-NFR-OP-03: Minimum disruption to operation of the lock.

The complete list of functional and non-functional requirements for AE technology is provided in the spreadsheet of AE requirements, shown in the table “Technical Requirements for AE” in Annex 1.1 Technical Requirements and Testing Plan for AE. Some of these requirements have been identified and added during the onsite AE measurements and due to interaction with lock’s personnel, which are the potential end-users of this technology. Considering the defined requirements a series of relevant tests have been designed for collecting data that are necessary for assessing if and how the technology meets the main requirements.

The testing plan includes 25 assessments and measurements, and the execution is delivered through a test sequence covering them. Each test has a defined objective, inputs and preconditions, the measurement procedure, the data to be collected, and the acceptance criteria derived from the associated KPIs. Test descriptions and results are recorded in the table “Testing plan for AE” in Annex 1.1 and summarised in Section 3.4. Operational parameter notes accompanying the plan specify practical ranges and observations used during execution. The plan, therefore, enables traceable validation from requirement to test case and from measurement to decision, ensuring that AE performance and robustness are demonstrated on the pilots, thereby demonstrating that the results of this technology are directly consumable by the Digital Twin and rest of CRISTAL’s functionality.

The detailed lists of tests, including their descriptions, KPIs the tests were relevant to, and other details is provided in the same Annex 1.1.

3.3.3 Evaluation and Validation Planning for Acoustic Emission System for Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)

A set of 6 functional requirements and 21 non-functional requirements for SIR system have been defined, and the complete list is provided in Annex 1.2 Technical Requirements and Testing Plan for SIR. These requirements have been discussed with partner VNF, from the perspective of both organiser and coordinator of French Pilot (WP8) and potential end-user of such technology.

Considering the defined requirements a series of relevant tests have been designed for collecting data that are necessary for assessing if and how the technology meets the main requirements.

The testing plan was designed with respect to the deployment of the SIR system in the French River Pilot (WP8) on a lock and carry out a subsurface inspection of the lock walls and the surrounding area. Considering the overall scope, the detailed test plan was developed to test the system in operation and capture scan results on-site, to further develop and test the post scan processing of the scan results to generate useful visualisations for the assessment of subsurface condition of the lock, and to assess these results against the Functional and Non-Functional KPIs. In general, these tests were designed to assess the capabilities of the SIR system in terms of the accuracy, precision and resolution of the results, assess the operational reality of deploying the system in an operational environment in terms of practicality, and compatibility. The detailed lists of tests, including their descriptions, KPIs the tests were relevant to, etc. is provided in the same

Annex 1.2.

Another relevant preparatory activity was to assess the conditions and facilities on the testing site before deploying the SIR technology and performing the planned tests. Partner VNF identified an appropriate lock on the waterway that had specific needs for investigation of its structure in order to determine the potential damages. Therefore, a wide gauge lock on the River Seine was selected for the testing of SIR system as its engineering structure is heavily weakened by water infiltrations that need to be localised in order to be repaired. Considering the requirements for deployment and operational use of SIR system, some specific facilities and equipment has had to be made available at the pilot test site, including a crane or similar lifting system, power supply, a suitable environment for the assembly and commissioning of the technology prior to the testing campaign, an appropriate area for operating the SIR technology, etc. Further details on the preparatory activities concerning the testing site, to ensure that the tests could be performed in safe conditions and without undesirable impacts, are presented in deliverable D6.2 of the CRISTAL project (2025 b).

3.3.4 Evaluation and Validation Planning for Smart Buoys (SB)

Functional and non-functional requirements for SB technology have been defined and the complete list is provided in Annex 1.3 Technical Requirements and Testing Plan for SB. These requirements have been discussed with partner UniGda and with IWW infrastructure manager Wody Polskie, from the perspective of environmental and legal requirements and limitations.

Considering the defined requirements, a series of relevant tests have been designed for collecting data that are necessary for assessing if and how the technology meets the main requirements. These include a combination of laboratory calibration, pre-deployment of functional tests and full-scale field.

The detailed lists of tests, including their descriptions, KPIs the tests were relevant to, etc. is provided in the same Annex 1.3.

3.3.5 Evaluation and Validation Planning for Fibre Optic Sensor System for Riverbed Monitoring (FOS)

Functional and non-functional requirements for FOS technology have been defined and the complete list is provided in Annex 1.4. Since the FOS was tested just in simulated environment, just the essential ones have been discussed with AIPo, covering partially the overall requirements for a commercial application. The FOS has been tested in a simulated environment, set up in an experimental hall in the ENEA Frascati Research Centre, according to commitments in GA.

Considering the defined requirements a series of relevant tests have been designed for collecting data that are necessary for assessing if and how the technology meets the main requirements.

The detailed lists of tests, including their descriptions, KPIs the tests were relevant to, etc. is provided in the same Annex 1.4 Technical Requirements and Testing Plan for FOS.

The plan for testing the FOS application involved several steps. The principle was to associate a weight measurement with the quantity that will then provide a height for the sediment column. The design and testing of a test scale equipped with FBG sensors arranged to distribute the measurement points across multiple locations, has been implemented, considering different pressures of sediments at different positions along the scale surface. A series of dry runs, consisting of loading and unloading weights, calibrate the system. Subsequently, a new waterproof scale, the “scale prototype”, was constructed and subjected to new tests, including

underwater. The weights for underwater tests were made by simulating a real column of sand and sediments, simulating the actual accumulation of sediment in a river. All details concerning the FOS testing in laboratory are presented in detail in deliverables D2.2 and D2.3.

3.4 Summary and evaluation of test results

3.4.1 Acoustic Emission System for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates (AE)

AE testing activities have been performed on the Italian lock sites Conca Di Baricetta and Isola Serafini, as well as on the French lock Lyon Couzon. More specifically, in June 2023 CERTH visited firstly the Italian lock Conca Di Baricetta and secondly the Isola Serafini. Also in June 2023, CERTH visited the French lock at Lyon Couzon. Lastly in July 2025 an extensive testing was carried out on the Italian lock Conca Di Baricetta.

The full summary of results for the Acoustic Emission (AE) system testing is based on the execution of the test sequence defined in the table “Testing plan for AE” (Annex 1.1). The campaign was carried out after ordering the equipment and the completion of ancillary activities, and adhered to the procedures and measurands specified in the testing plan, with each step conducted under the stated preconditions, the agreed measurement setup, and the corresponding acceptance criteria derived from the AE KPIs. A few relevant tests are presented further.

In the activity labelled AE-OS-01, measurements were carried out by using artificial failures through Pencil Lead Brake (PLB) first in the laboratory, and secondly at the lock gate site, following the procedure described in table “Testing plan for AE” (Annex 1.1), to measure the sensitivity of the AE, specifically the ability to detect signals > 20 db. Easy pattern recognition of the acoustic emission from the PLB using hit number peaks was verified, which is a first level of detecting microcrack simulated event from the background noise. The acceptance criteria defined in the testing plan were satisfied and the test passed.

In the activity labelled AE-OS-02, CERTH’s team installed the micro-SHM in various points on the gate to test the ability of the logging software (AEwin) to connect at the same time in many micro-SHM loggers, following the procedure described in the table “Testing plan for AE” (Annex 1.1). This was done by deploying multiple AE loggers at the same time and checking the ability of the system to parse such recordings in parallel. This also included validating on-site the ability of the AE logger to connect remotely through Wi-Fi to a laptop running the logging software to carry out recording from multiple AE loggers at the same time, as well as measuring the Wi-Fi distance connectivity. The acceptance criteria defined in the testing plan were satisfied and the test passed.

In the activity labelled AE-OS-03, which involves detecting metal microcracks build-up before major metal crack failures, and furthermore, detecting upcoming out of the normal operation failures. Laboratory and onsite sensitivity measurements with various AE sources, from simulated microcrack to friction produced AEs and impact hammer experimentation with various impact loads and utilising ultrasonic high frequency sources. In all cases the ability to capture the AE emission producing a large set of onsite sources of out of the normal gate states was verified. The acceptance criteria defined in the testing plan were satisfied and the test passed.

Under the same testing activity (AE-OS-3), micro-SHM have been deployed onto actual lock gates in various water locks in Italy and French, where they recorded and retrieved, through the developed AE library, the normal operating space of the gates numerous times under various conditions. Various techniques simulating indications of microcrack development, like ultrasonic pulse sources (one of the key ingredients during the creation of microcracks is the release of

ultrasonic AE) and PLB, have been applied in the vicinity of the sensors. The operation and sensitivity of the model for detecting microcracks was verified, using the PLB procedure that can accurately mimic the elastic waves produced inside the material produced by microcracks. These simulated signals were produced and recorded on lock site and later used in producing testing, training and validation sets for the microcrack model, passing with high accuracy above 95%. The acceptance criteria defined in the testing plan were satisfied and the test passed. In the corresponding activity regarding the second model measuring deviation from normal operational parameters was tested. The procedure used involved checking the sensitivity of the algorithm in measuring the deviation from the normal gate's operating space using various out of the normal sources of acoustic waves, like from impact from a hammer with various tips, rubber, steel, aluminium, plastic has, and also using ultrasonic sensor producing in 40khz, 60khz, 80khz in pulse or sinusoidal or double exponential wave form, all with various small to medium amplitude/strength. The acceptance criteria defined in the testing plan were satisfied and the test passed.

In the activity labelled AE-OS-04, the team installed the AE logger and the sensors in real lock site under 60 minutes, following the procedure described as installation time < 60 minutes. The acceptance criteria defined in the testing plan were satisfied and the test passed.

In the activity labelled AE-OS-06, AE recording operation was carried out onsite testing at locks while various ships and boats were able to pass without interfering to AE system operation, showing that there was minimal disruption to overall lock gates operation. The acceptance criteria defined in the testing plan were satisfied and the test passed.

In the activity labelled AE-OS-08, CERTH's team carried out in their lab and also during the last visit to VNF lock at Lyon testing of remote connectivity to the data management using a 4G bridge (smartphone turned into 4G bridge) to connect and send data to the data management located in Greece at CERTH's lab. The data produced was transmitted to the data management. The acceptance criteria defined in the testing plan were satisfied and the test passed.

In the activity labelled AE-OS-11, the auto sensor test (AST) feature of micro-SHM was verified. The AST capability enables the AE system to control an integral pulser in the AST-equipped preamplifiers, allowing any AE channel to pulse the sensor while the receiving electronics remain active. This allows the sensor to act both as a pulser and receiver, enabling to detect if the sensors have good sound conductivity with the inspected area: utilising this feature periodically, the operator is sure of sensors' good acoustic conductance. The acceptance criteria defined in the testing plan were satisfied and the test passed.

The whole set of tests and the testing sequence and results are presented in detail in Annex 1.1.

3.4.2 Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)

The SIR system was tested in real environment, on a wide gauge lock on the River Seine, in France. The SIR system was deployed on two further narrow-gauge locks latter in the project, but the outcomes were not considered for this assessment, only for generating further visualisations (D8.3). The testing campaign on the wide gauge lock was carried out in December 2024, according to the following testing programme for data collection:

- On the 1st of December, the SIR modular platform was assembled close the lock to be scanned, and commissioning tests of the assembled equipment carried out (without scanning a structure).
- On the 2nd to 4th of December, the SIR modular platform was placed alongside the vertical

lock chamber wall at five separate locations of the northern wall of the lock, towards the Western end by a crane, and scans of those locations carried out.

- On the 5th of December, the radar antenna was dismantled from the positioning frame and installed in a manual pushcart for the scanning of the horizontal area of ground Northwest of the lock.

The overall testing campaign is presented in detail in deliverable D8.2 (CRISTAL, 2025d). During the data collection tests, scanning data for five Quadrants, and Areas of the ground totalling approximately 150m², was successfully recorded and stored for off-site postprocessing and analysis. This demonstrated that the data capture process was working, however confirmation that useful data was collected required the data to be processed. Furthermore, extensive manual notes were taken recording the operation of the SIR modular platform and the events that occurred during the on-site testing. Following the on-site testing the data was processed to generate the visualisations of the subsurface conditions from the scans, and the results have been reported in deliverable D8.3 (CRISTAL, 2025e).

In the evaluation of the outcomes of testing of the SIR system, two factors have been considered and compared, i.e.:

1. The target level of technology compliance with the defined requirements and KPIs that could be theoretically achievable after assessing the test results, based on the designed testing plan.
2. The actual level of technology compliance with the requirements and KPIs, as it was achieved through the assessment of outcomes of tests carried out within the pilot.

It should be noted that the envisaged level was subject to various uncertainties and restrictions, therefore, it was not expected that all requirements would be assessed as being fully satisfied during the testing. Furthermore, due to the actual conditions for deploying the technologies within the pilot, some tests had to be limited compared to the initial planning, which also impacted the assessment done.

Table 1 summarises the levels of compliance for both cases described above, for the different types of requirements, which allows to compare the number of requirements targeted for different levels of compliance against the number of requirements that actually achieved those levels of compliance.

Table 1: Level of compliance of SIR system with requirements and KPIs (target level vs achieved one).

Level of compliance with requirements		Number of requirements				
		Overall	Functional	Non-functional		
				Operational	RAMS	Compatibility
Target level for technology validation (theoretically possible)	Fully	10	1	5	0	4
	Partially	17	6	5	5	1
	None	1	0	1	0	0
Level achieved through testing in pilot	Fully	5	0	1	0	4
	Partially	18	7	5	5	1
	None	5	0	5	0	0

Of the 28 requirements identified and/or defined, 10 of which could be fully assessed and 17 partially, the outcome was that 5 of the requirements were assessed as being fully satisfied, and 18 partially satisfied. This means that of the 27 requirements that could be at least partially assessed, 23 of those were at least partially satisfied. The rest were either not satisfied, or

insufficient data was collected during the tests to assess with confidence if the SIR system satisfied those requirements.

The general outcome of the evaluation of the outcomes of testing the SIR system and assessing the outcomes against the KPIs (see requirements and test tables in Annex 1.2 for details) is that the KPIs were mostly met, which was assessed as being fully compliant for 5 requirements and partially for 18.

- In terms of the functional requirements, the SIR system was able to capture data that was processed to produce output in which features of interest were detected with the required resolution and apparent accuracy to be considered useful and meaningful for interpretation as to the subsurface condition of the structure. The outputs are discussed in detail in D8.2 and D8.3.
- In terms of operational requirements, the SIR system was able to be deployed to an IWW structure, i.e., the walls of a lock chamber and surrounding area, be operated in the prevailing conditions, and capture data.

The main reasons why the requirements were only partially evaluated and validated are:

- The absence of reliable ground-truth data on the subsurface structure under inspection, i.e., there was no independent details of the subsurface structure or the condition of that structure to compare the outputs of the SIR system against within the scope of the project activities and fully evaluate the accuracy of the outputs. Although laboratory testing provided suitable evidence of visualisation accuracy for the purposes of this work, further refinement efforts would benefit from comparative studies on structures where accurate reference data are available, such as detailed technical drawings, CAD models from construction, and/or information from invasive inspections (e.g., borescope surveys, which, although they might occur during inspections or corrective actions, there were no available records and did not take place within the project period).
- The rate at which the structure could be scanned using the rig for scanning the vertical lock walls was lower than necessary to make it practical to scan the whole of large structures with large areas (up to hundreds of m²). However, the mechanical positioning of the antenna could be significantly increased without losing scanning resolution (the rate of antenna advancement was such that an excess of data was captured, and only ¼ of the measurements captured was used for generating the outputs). Also, a significant number of measurements had to be restarted or repeated due to errors in the operation of the radar software, which slowed down the scanning process; resolving these issues and achieving the full automation of the scanning process, along with speeding up the movement of the antenna, could significantly increase the scanning rate by a factor of four or more. Furthermore, specific locations were selected for the Quadrants to be scanned, which were not adjacent to each other, requiring the crane and equipment to be moved each time; this greatly increased the time between the scanning of quadrants compared to scanning of adjacent quadrants in turn and only moving the crane after a cluster of quadrants within its reach had been scanned.
- The classification of the features detected by the SIR system according to the predicted type of material that they consisted of was not achieved, as the lack of independent classification of materials for comparison, and limited number of scans to gather data was not sufficient for the development and calibration of this state-of-the-art capability for a ground penetrating radar system in this application.

- It was outside of the scope of the tests of the prototype SIR system in the project to be able to provide sufficient data for assessing if the system met all of the requirements. For example, it was not possible to fully test the requirement SIR-NFR-RAMS-03 (that “The Mean time between failure (MTBF) of the inspection system should be as low as possible, and consistent with enabling scanning of infrastructure within the access period”). This is because, although some data on the reliability and failure rates of the SIR system could be collected during the tests, the period of deployment for the testing of the experimental equipment was too short to collect enough data to be statistically significant to fully assess if the requirement had been met. Additionally, assessment of the reliability of the prototype SIR system can only be partially assessed based on the limited time it was deployed. Therefore, while these requirements are still relevant to the assessment of the SIR system and the tests results indicative of the performance of the SIR system, there is an upper limit on the level of performance the SIR system could achieve with respect to some requirements based on the outcomes of the tests.

Considering the outcomes of the development of the SIR system and using them as a datapoint for the potential capabilities of the technology, the KPIs, targets and priorities for the SIR system could be revisited. In the development of the current prototype, priority was given to the achievement of the goals related to the resolution of the scan output. If in hindsight end-users might consider greater scanning speed and depth as higher priorities, and an increase in the minimum size of features the system can reliably detect and resolve acceptable, then the system could be revised accordingly (such as using lower frequency radar antenna, wider spaced scan transects, and higher antenna movements speeds).

The analysis of the results indicates that the SIR system and the outputs it produced could, generally, be considered as being demonstrated to be fit-for-purpose in the context of a prototype proof of concept in an operational environment. The SIR system was largely functional and produced useful outputs; however, it would benefit from further refinement in order to fully meet all requirements, and further testing to verify the outputs of the system. Also, the requirements could benefit from being reconsidered in terms of the priorities and what is likely to be technically feasible.

3.4.3 Smart Buoys (SB)

The validation and testing plan combined laboratory calibration, pre-deployment of functional tests and full-scale field trials in the following sequence of activities:

1. **Laboratory & Dock Tests (M1–M2)** – Sensor calibration (pressure, GNSS, LiDAR), power-budget verification, penetration testing of communication links.
2. **Controlled Waterbody Trials (M3)** – Two-week operation in a port basin to benchmark accuracy against certified gauges and to test stability of communication modules (LTE, LoRa, AIS).
3. **Full-Scale River Trials (M4–M9)** – Deployment of buoys on key navigable sections of the Odra and Lower Vistula, covering a range of natural flow and traffic conditions. *KPIs collected:* availability, latency, energy autonomy, mechanical integrity and hydrological accuracy when coupled with the Digital Twin.
4. **Integrated System Validation (M9–M12)** – End-to-end assessment of the data pipeline to RIS⁺⁺ and Digital Twin, including synchro-modal voyage-planning.

Data acquisition was aligned with the testing plan and included hydrological measurements

(water level, bathymetry, vertical clearance), positional and motion data from GNSS, operational system metrics (uptime, latency, battery status, mechanical integrity), vessel traffic information via AIS, and server-side integration data such as MQTT delivery, RIS⁺⁺ ingestion and EPCIS event generation. These datasets formed the basis for KPI evaluation and end-to-end pipeline verification.

Evidence gathered within Autumn 2024 and Spring 2025 campaigns (Chapter 6 in deliverable D9.2, CRISTAL 2025 c) demonstrated the feasibility of this plan; all units maintained > 99 % uptime and supplied accurate bathymetry that may support dynamic draught management during four full-scale IWT tests.

Risk assessment confirms that no additional permanent infrastructure is required beyond standard navigation safety measures and temporary service boats.

Most functional and non-functional requirements defined for the Smart Buoy system were exercised during the pilot. These included hydrological accuracy, system availability, communication robustness (LTE, AIS, LoRa), energy autonomy and the full integration chain with RIS⁺⁺, the Digital Twin and EPCIS-compliant services. Representative requirements, such as water-level accuracy (SB-FR-01), high availability (SB-NFR-OP-02), AIS reception (SB-FR-03) and end-to-end interoperability (SB-NFR-OP-09), were successfully demonstrated.

Key KPIs—including availability, communication stability, hydrological measurement performance and data-pipeline reliability—were fully validated across all major campaigns. Some KPIs were only partially validated, notably LoRa long-range performance and mechanical resilience under winter conditions. Other KPIs related to barge-coupled trials and high-density AIS loads could not be evaluated due to external environmental limitations rather than system shortcomings.

The requirements and KPIs proved generally appropriate for assessing system maturity. Minor refinements are recommended, such as defining KPIs for winter-resilience and high-traffic AIS performance, and clarifying expectations for fallback communication modes in low-coverage environments.

The combined evidence from WP9 confirms that the Smart Buoy system meets all essential functional and operational requirements and achieves the majority of KPIs defined for the pilot. End-to-end integration with RIS⁺⁺, the Digital Twin and EPCIS workflows was consistently demonstrated. Based on validated performance under full-scale river conditions, the technology is assessed at TRL 7–8, indicating readiness for large-scale deployment within European inland waterway corridors.

3.4.4 Fibre Optic Sensor System for Riverbed Monitoring (FOS)

The prototype scale test was carried out in a laboratory environment, as testing in real environment was out-of-the-scope of the project, due to high costs associated to the complex civil engineering works required for even a temporary experimental installation of the prototype scale. Nonetheless, the results of the tests done in the laboratory allowed for the validation of the proposed concept for monitoring waterways' depth variation.

The FOS testing in laboratory conditions is described in detail in deliverables D2.2 and D2.3, including the setup and deployment of the technology, and the testing methodology. The site for testing the scale prototype of the FOS was set up in the Giasone experimental hall at the ENEA Frascati Research Centre, a general-purpose facility equipped with a pool for floating and underwater experimental activities and devices development. Tests were performed using the

prototype scale, whose geometry and mechanical structure enable reliable scaling of the obtained results.

The concept design of the FOS system was implemented into the prototype shown in Figure 5. After the scale prototype was fully assembled, it was first tested in a **dry setup** with discrete known loads. The scale prototype was further tested with additional loading tests using continuously varying loads. Finally, tests were done with construction boxes gradually filled with sand. Following on from the tests in dry environment, the setup was adapted for tests in **submerged set up**, in a pool filled with water.

Two main features of the setup result, the expected scenarios, and conditions of waterways have not been adequately simulated in laboratory: i) the absence of running water and ii) the low water level. Although the adopted setup does not simulate a running-water scenario, it can be assumed as adequate for the testing within the scope of the project. Flows of water infiltrating the sediment of the riverbed would not effectively alter the loading on the scale, but in the case of an alteration of the build-up itself, with a consequent increase or decrease of the height and weight of the column based on the scale. The build-ups of sediment of interest within the scope of the project, although with a large variability in their minute composition, are permeable but the water flows do not pass through them directly, having a mostly imbibition-like condition. Although the test is conducted with a low water level, with the simulated build-up not submerged and dry, no relevance to the results can be assumed. The condition only affects the density of the simulated build-up, and thus the weight-to-height calibration that should be worked out.

The setup with a pile of solid loads based on the bending plate is assumed to be significantly representative of the expected operating condition, which is an underwater hill-like heap of sand and stone debris. Construction boxes with the base slightly larger than the active area of the bending plate were used. The scale was buried under a thick layer of sand, levelled on top, so that the weight of the pile of loads was uniformly distributed on the active area of the bending plate. The muddy character of the build-up expected in the intended application results in a mostly viscofluid-like loading condition, so that the weight of the columns overlaying the bending plate acts vertically and is uniformly distributed on the bending plate itself. That condition could not be assumed only in the case of a mostly hardened build-up, or in the case of a build-up with a prevalent content of medium/large stones. In such cases, non-vertical forces and reactions act within the projected columns, with consequent unpredictable unloading of the bending plate. Such cases, which are unusual in waterways to be monitored continuously and in real-time for water depth variations, could be effectively detected by the proposed system. The viscofluid-like loading condition is detected thanks to the centre-symmetric pattern of the sensors instrumenting the bending plate. The viscofluid-like loading condition results in a symmetric signal distribution among the sensors. That allows for real-time validation of the correct working conditions in the intended real application.

The performed test allowed to verify the operational measurement range of the prototype scale and its resolution. The scale prototype for laboratory tests was designed based on expected real loading conditions at the Po River pilot site. The bending plate and structure were sized to detect height variations under 50 cm and measure sediment build-up up to over 5 m. Dimensioning considered the density of typical local sediment/debris, and tests used material with matching granulometry. The granulometry analyses that have been provided showed that most samples consisted of sands (4.76–0.075 mm), with over 99% medium sand (≈ 0.425 mm) in the river's middle section (surveys S51 and S56). This data guided the choice of <2 mm sand for FOS lab tests. Debris granulometry is not critical for FOS: it measures the height of the deposited column, using density—an installation-specific parameter—as a reference.

The scale was tested by incrementally adding 0.5 m of material using construction boxes filled with sand. Calibration was performed for this specific, non-submerged setup. The directly measured $\Delta\lambda$ as strain of the FOS sensors, has a range from 0 to 0.1. Once the scale has been fitted and calibrated to verify its consistency and linearity, the data is compared to provide a true measurement. As mentioned previously, taking into account the average density of the sediments in the water, a resolution of +/- 30 cm is achieved in the sediment height range from 0 to 5 m.

The working principle of the proposed system is assumed not to be affected by its installation in running or still waters. Flows of water infiltrating the build-up would not effectively alter its loading on the scale, except in the case of actually modifying the height of the column of the build-up itself projected on the scale. The build-ups of interest for the project are mostly muddy and permeable, and do not allow the water to flow freely inside them. That condition shall also be assumed for build-ups with a relevant content of stone debris and rock fragments. In the absence of a variable flow of water inside it, which would produce varying inner hydrostatic forces, the build-up loading on the scale shall not be influenced by the regime of the water flow. What running water could effectively influence is the installation groundwork of the scale, which could be moved/tilted and thus alter the functionality of the installed scale.

The working principle of the proposed system is also assumed not to be affected by its testing in low water, the upper part of the simulated build-up not submerged. That condition only affects the overall density of the simulated build-up, which would be lower if completely submerged, and thus only affects the weight-to-height calibration.

The adopted setup provided reliable results, although it does not adequately simulate the expected scenarios due to the following main reasons: i) the absence of running water; ii) the low water level, which makes the simulated build-up not completely submerged; iii) modelling the sediment build-up by a narrow pile of loads on the scale.

Further information on the measurements carried out in the laboratory and their validation was published in the paper “Fiber optic river navigability monitoring system” (Vicca, D., et al., 2025)

3.5 Conclusions

In this subsection, conclusions are drawn about the extent to which each of the four sensor technologies developed within the CRISTAL project were validated with respect to the requirements and KPIs determined for each of the technologies. Consideration is also given to any limitations of the testing and assessment process, based on the fact that the deployment and testing of the technologies within the project were of limited scope compared to full operational trials. Further consideration is also given to the overall status of the technologies with respect to the potential future commercialisation and operational use, as well as identifying the extent of any further development, refinements and assessments that might be required.

Acoustic Emission System for Health Monitoring of Lock Gates (AE)

AE was deployed on 3 locks in less than 60 minutes in each case, demonstrating the adaptability of the technology to different lock gates and general ease of deployment. Furthermore, the traffic was able to continue using the locks during the deployment and testing of the technology, which showed that it had a minimal impact on traffic. Tests using Pencil Lead Break and hammer impacts to simulate microcracks and other anomalies, respectively, showed that the AE technology can be expected to detect acoustic emissions in lock gates related to real microcracks and other events associated with failures or circumstances outside of normal operational conditions. Furthermore, the outcome of the tests was consistent with other applications of

acoustic emission. In addition to this the AE technology fully satisfied the majority of the functional and operational requirements set for it showing that the technological approach is valid for the aims of the project, and that the tested prototype is largely suitable for operational use with perhaps just some final product development and approval work necessary for the prototype technology to enter full scale trials stage and be implemented and adopted.

Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)

For the purposes of assessing the SIR system, it was deployed to scan the walls and surrounding area of one wide-gauge lock, as this deployment utilised the full range of system capabilities. Processing of scan results showed that it generated data that could be processed and further interpreted to provide useful information about the condition of the lock structure and surroundings. This proved that the system was generally functional, and the majority of the requirements were at least partially satisfied. However, lack of independent verification of the condition of the lock through invasive inspection or repair work (which was outside the scope of the project) meant that it was only possible to partially assess the accuracy of the SIR system outputs. For the information generated by the SIR system to be fully relied on, for informing the maintenance decision making process, the accuracy and limitations of the information generated would need to be fully verified. Also, although it was possible to carry out the scans and interrupt the scanning process to allow traffic to continue through the locks, assessment of the tests against the operational requirements indicated that further development of the mechanical and operational process of carrying out the scans could be necessary, to make the SIR system fully suitable for regular operational use, particularly with regard to reducing the time taken for the scanning process. It might also be worthwhile reconsideration of some operational KPIs based on experience as well as the scope of the use of the system in terms of whole structure scans or targeted scans, although this scope could be variable according to the requirements of individual end users.

Smart Buoys (SB)

Tests related to most functional and non-functional requirements defined for the Smart Buoy system were carried out during the pilot, successfully demonstrating the system. The outcomes of these tests showed that the system fully met all essential functional and operational requirements KPIs, although some KPIs were only partially met, and it was not possible to evaluate the system against some KPIs due to limitations in the scope of the testing, such as equipping barges in river service with corresponding equipment, related to barge-coupled trials and high-density AIS loads could not be evaluated due to external environmental limitations rather than shortcoming of the system. Therefore, the SB system is considered to be largely functional, only requiring some refinements towards full scale trials and a commercial product, and, possibly, a reconsideration of some KPIs based on testing experience.

Fibre Optic Sensor System for Riverbed Monitoring (FOS)

Prototype scale tested in laboratory in both dry and submerged conditions with a variety of loads verified the ability of the FOS to weigh the load from the mass above it in conditions simulating installation on a riverbed, and it was possible to calibrate the scale to provide a measurement of the height of material above it. The laboratory tests showed that the FOS satisfied the key functional requirements, and that it was not possible to fully assess the FOS with respect to other functional requirements, or most of the operational requirements in laboratory conditions. Further testing in river conditions would be necessary to calibrate the scale and evaluate the

accuracy and reliability of the measurements with real river sediments, as well as confirm the underlying assumptions and suitability of the FOS to be relied on in regular operational use.

Summary

All the major functionalities of all of the technologies were at least partially validated and generally mostly validated, showing that all of the technologies have the potential to contribute to the high-level project objectives. The outcomes for AE and SB technologies demonstrated in the pilots show that they are close to potential future full scale trials, commercialisation, and operational use, with only some minor further development, refinements and assessments required. The outcomes for the SIR technology showed that the technology is functional as far as can be assessed in the scope of the project, considering the lack of an alternative subsurface condition assessment method to fully verify the information generated by the SIR system. Also, that the SIR system prototype could benefit from refinements to the mechanical design to improve the operation of the system, particularly the scanning speed. The outcomes for the FOS showed that the prototype scale was capable of weighing the load from the mass above it in conditions simulating installation on a riverbed, and it was possible to calibrate the scale to provide a measurement of the height of material above it. However, further testing might be needed to verify the underlying assumptions and functional operation in river conditions, as well as assessing the operational characteristics.

4. Validation of the Business Models

This chapter is intended to present both the initial Business Model Canvas (BMC) and their validated or updated versions, highlighting key changes in value propositions, customer segments, or revenue models based on the evidence gathered. The outcome was a set of validated, optimised, and more robust business models ready for wider dissemination and potential exploitation.

4.1 Context

The validation of business models was a crucial step within the CRISTAL project, defined under Work Package 10 (WP10), specifically in Task 10.2. The objective was to validate the business models that had been developed for the project's various innovations to ensure they could sustainably identify value, deliver value, and capture reward. This validation was not a mere theoretical exercise but involved active engagement with the entire stakeholder ecosystem, including ALICE members, to gather practical views on the proposed models and address potential challenges. The goal was to produce validated and optimised business models, enriched with real-world cost and revenue factors, and to analyse their transferability and scalability.

The business models in CRISTAL were developed using the **Business Model Canvas (BMC)**, a strategic template comprising nine building blocks: Customer Segments, Value Propositions, Channels, Customer Relationships, Revenue Streams, Key Resources, Key Activities, Key Partners, and Cost Structure. This framework was used to describe the rationale of how an organisation created, delivered, and captured value. The BMC provides a visual chart that assists firms in aligning their activities by illustrating potential trade-offs. The process in CRISTAL involved a series of interactive, co-creation workshops where technology developers, potential end-users, and governance partners populated the canvases for each innovation.

In the context of CRISTAL, these business models covered a range of core innovations, from physical sensor technologies developed in WP2 to integrated digital platforms like the Digital Twins (DTs) from WP5 and the Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS) from WP3. An initial challenge identified during the BMC development phase was the difficulty in quantifying costs and revenues, along with a blurring of customer segments. Therefore, this chapter assessed how the pilot projects and the Living Labs helped to clarify these ambiguities and test the initial assumptions. The validation process raised a series of open questions for the BMCs, and the ability of the technical and pilot work packages to answer these questions formed the core of this evaluation in WP10.

This validation work builds directly on the formative business models and **Social Cost-Benefit Analysis (SCBA)** frameworks reported in Deliverable D4.3. It serves as a critical bridge between the Design phase of the business models (Phase 3) and their Implementation and Management (Phases 4 and 5), which were tested in the pilots (WP7-9) and further refined through Living Lab activities reported in D4.4. These were calibrated with the final report of WP4, D4.5, and the operational assessments from the pilots D7.2, D8.2 and D9.2. The findings from this chapter will directly inform the final evaluation of the project and contribute to a general framework for the validation of future inland waterway transport (IWT) interventions.

More details and further materials pertinent to this chapter are stored in Annex 2. BMC SCMS Validation Surveys.

4.2 Technologies and Technical Innovations to be Validated

The core technique under validation in Task 10.2 was the **Business Model Canvas (BMC) methodology itself**, as it was applied to the CRISTAL innovations. This involved assessing the viability of the business models developed for each core technology and system within the project. The validation focused on several key innovations, each with a distinct BMC that was co-created and refined during dedicated workshops.

Physical Sensor Technologies and Sub-systems (WP2)

- **Acoustic Emission System (AES):** Developed by CERTH, this system used piezoelectric sensors to detect high-frequency stress waves generated by material deformation or microcracks in metallic structures, such as lock gates. The technology aimed to provide early warnings of potential failures, enabling predictive maintenance and reducing unexpected downtime. The business model was validated in both the French and Italian pilots on lock gates at Couzon (France) and Conca Di Baricetta and isola Serafini (Italy), respectively. It targeted infrastructure managers and waterway authorities as key customers, offering enhanced reliability and safety. The system demonstrated excellent capability in distinguishing between normal operations and simulated failures, validating its potential for real-world application.
- **Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR):** This technology, developed by UNEW and EUMO, used Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) for the non-invasive inspection of infrastructure assets like lock walls and dams. The primary goal was to detect subsurface anomalies such as cracks, voids, or corrosion, thereby enabling a shift from corrective to preventive and predictive maintenance. The business model was framed as a service offering accurate and reliable detection of defects, with direct customers being infrastructure managers and maintenance entities. The value proposition included increased asset lifetime, lower costs, and enhanced safety. The BMC highlighted that the service could reduce the need for more costly invasive methods like core sampling. The system was designed to be modular and semi-automated, capable of generating 3D subsurface imagery.
- **Smart Buoys (SB):** Developed by Ł-PIT for the Polish pilot, these buoys were equipped with sensors to measure parameters like water level, current speed, temperature, and bridge clearance. They were designed to provide real-time environmental data to improve navigational safety and efficiency on free-flowing rivers like the Vistula. The business model offered this data as a service, targeting infrastructure managers, shipowners, and software companies. The value proposition included replacing manual measurements, thereby saving time and resources, and providing new data types like vessel counts and bridge clearance measurements, which were not previously available.
- **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS):** Developed by ENEA, this technology used Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors to monitor sand dune formation in critical sections of free-flowing waterways like the Po River. Unlike traditional daily bathymetric surveys, FOS offered continuous, real-time monitoring with low environmental impact. The technology, which achieved TRL 4-5, aimed to provide Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) on navigability directly to infrastructure managers via smart dashboards. The business model centred on providing this data as a service, with a value proposition focused on more efficient dredging planning and increased safety. The technical setup involved chaining together weighing pads housing the fibre optics, made from durable materials for submarine applications. However, a significant bottleneck identified was the high installation cost, estimated at €250,000 for a prototype, therefore, the validation was limited to laboratory testing, in accordance with the GA.

Digital Systems (WP3 & WP5)

- **Digital Twins (DTs):** Developed by Fraunhofer, the DTs were virtual representations of physical assets (like locks or river segments) that aggregated data from various sensors (FOS, AES, SIR, SB). The DTs used this data to provide forecasts, alerts, and visualisations to support decision-making for both transport operators and infrastructure managers. For example, the DT-Water Level used historical data and machine learning to forecast navigability, while the DT-Locks analysed AE and SIR data to provide maintenance recommendations. The use cases were tested across all three pilots. The business model recognised that DTs would likely be exploited through integration into larger systems like the SCMS rather than as standalone commercial products, with a focus on making the software open-source. The technical architecture was designed to be modular and scalable, using open-source components and state-of-the-art technologies (Java, Python, Angular, Docker) to ensure maintainability and future expansion.
- **Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS):** The SCMS, developed by CERTH, was an online platform designed to function as a single point of information for all stakeholders. It consolidated data from the DTs, CRISTAL sensors-based systems and external sources (like EuRIS) to provide early warnings, identify the impact of disruptions, and suggest synchro-modal re-routing options involving road and rail. The system's value proposition was to enhance the reliability and resilience of inland waterway transport by providing forecasted alerts and visibility of alternative transport modes, representing an added value over existing RIS platforms. The primary customers were identified as freight transport planners, logistics service providers (LSPs), and transport operators. The business model explored revenue streams such as subscription fees for the service, with a preliminary SCBA showing potential net benefits depending on transport volumes and baseline reliability.

4.3 Methodology for Business Models' Validation

The validation methodology for Task 10.2 followed a structured, multi-faceted approach, integrating qualitative feedback from stakeholders with quantitative analysis where possible. This process was designed to test the hypotheses embedded in the Business Model Canvases developed in earlier work packages (WP4). The methodology aimed to move the business models from a state of *perceived value* (speculative) to *realised value* (empirical and observable).

1. **Application of the Business Model Canvas (BMC):** The foundational methodology was the BMC itself, used not just for design but as an analytical tool for validation. Each of the nine blocks of the developed BMCs served as a hypothesis to be tested. For example, questions such as "Are infrastructure managers the correct primary customer segment for FOS?" or "Is a subscription fee a viable revenue stream for the SCMS?" were addressed. The workshops for each technology served as the first step in this process, bringing together technology developers and potential users to co-create the initial canvases.
2. **Stakeholder Engagement via Living Labs (LLs):** The primary validation mechanism was the stakeholder workshop conducted within the Living Lab framework. As described in D4.4, each pilot country established a Living Lab to engage with relevant stakeholders, including end-users (transport operators), key partners (infrastructure managers), and regulators. This qualitative approach was crucial for validating the *perceived value* of the innovations and testing the assumptions within the BMCs against real-world operational and commercial realities.
 - a. In the **French pilot**, the LLs were integrated into VNF's existing institutional meetings, such as the National Users Committee. During these sessions, the BMs for SCMS, CEDRE, DT, AE, and SIR were discussed with freight operators, engineers, and maintenance staff. This

- allowed for direct feedback on value propositions and the identification of adoption barriers, such as data confidentiality concerns and the need for expert interpretation of SIR data.
- The **Italian pilot** used a series of dedicated LL workshops to validate the BMs for SCMS, AE, FOS, and the Smart Bulletin. This process led to the co-creation of the "Manifesto for the Sustainable Development of the Padano-Veneto IWW," which endorsed the value of the technologies and identified necessary governance-level actions. The SCMS BMC was explicitly validated through a survey during these sessions, confirming stakeholder interest in a single point of information.
 - In the **Polish pilot**, the LL engaged a wide range of stakeholders, including logistics operators, port authorities, and government representatives, to discuss the outcomes of pilot voyages and the technologies used, particularly the Smart Buoys. The BMC for the SCMS was presented and evaluated, confirming stakeholder interest while also underscoring the severe constraints imposed by inadequate infrastructure and hydrological variability.
 - Stakeholder engagement varied in depth and reach, depending on pilot maturity and institutional integration.

Figure 8: Stakeholders Engagement Intensity by Category and pilot, Source Deliverable D4.4, CRISTAL project

- Quantitative Stakeholder Polling:** To supplement the qualitative LL feedback, structured polls were conducted with stakeholders during the French, Italian, and Polish workshops. These polls used rating scales (1-5) and multiple-choice questions to quantify perceptions of the SCMS business model. Key metrics assessed included the appeal of the value proposition, the completeness of the BMC's demand, supply, and finance blocks, and the perceived impact on resilience and traffic growth. This quantitative data provided a more objective measure of stakeholder buy-in and highlighted specific areas of the business model requiring further development.
- Social Cost-Benefit Analysis (SCBA) Framework:** To quantify the benefits and costs of the integrated innovations, a preliminary SCBA was developed for the SCMS, which aggregated the value generated by the upstream technologies. This SCBA model calculated the Net Present Value (NPV) based on benefits such as reduced waiting times, improved reliability, and modal shift, against the costs of development and operation. The initial analysis

showed that the SCMS could demonstrate net benefits of €135,225 over 20 years, but this outcome was highly sensitive to transport volumes and the baseline reliability of the waterway. This validation task aimed to revisit and refine this SCBA with empirical data from the pilots.

5. **Key Performance Indicator (KPI) Analysis:** The operational performance of the pilots was measured against a common framework of KPIs, as detailed in Task 10.3. For example, the four pilot voyages conducted in Poland provided empirical evidence on operational efficiency, cost savings, and emissions reductions. The net logistics cost savings of 11–18% achieved in these pilots provided concrete validation for the value proposition of enhancing efficiency. Similarly, the Italian pilot's Smart Bulletin was estimated to increase the number of navigable days by 4.2% (from 240 to 250 annually), directly validating its value proposition for dredging operations. This quantitative data was used to validate the *Value Propositions* and *Cost Structure* elements of the BMCs.
6. **Cross-Case Analysis:** The methodology involved comparing and contrasting the validation findings from the three distinct pilot environments (France, Italy, and Poland). This helped to distinguish between generic, transferable elements of the business models and those that required specific local adaptations. For example, the strong push for governance reform in the Italian LL highlighted that a business model's success could be tied to the institutional context, a finding with potential transferability. Conversely, the severe infrastructure and hydrological limitations in the Polish pilot demonstrated that even a technically sound business model for Smart Buoys could face significant barriers to creating value if the fundamental conditions for navigation are not met.
7. **Iterative Refinement:** The validation was an iterative process, not a one-off assessment. Feedback from the LLs, polls, and pilot data were used to refine the initial BMCs developed in D4.3.

4.4 Findings and Discussion

The application of the validation methodology yielded a range of findings that confirmed, challenged, and refined the initial business models for the CRISTAL innovations. The feedback gathered from Living Labs, quantitative polls, pilot operations, and KPI analysis provided a reality check on the assumptions embedded within the nine blocks of each Business Model Canvas.

Findings for Physical Sensor Technologies

- **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS):** The value proposition of providing continuous, real-time data on sand dune formation for optimising dredging was strongly validated by stakeholders in the Italian Living Lab, who saw it as a way to improve reliability and reduce costs. However, the business model hit a critical roadblock in the **Cost Structure** and **Key Resources** blocks. The estimated prototype and installation cost of €250,000 strongly precluded a real-world pilot. This finding validates the *bottleneck* identified in the initial BMC and suggests that the business model is not currently viable without significant external funding or a drastic reduction in production costs. The **Customer Segment** of infrastructure managers (e.g., AIPO) was confirmed as correct, but their willingness to pay remains untested.
- **Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR):** The value proposition of non-invasive inspection to inform predictive and preventative maintenance was validated by VNF engineers and maintenance staff in the French Living Labs. Stakeholders appreciated the potential to reduce the need for more expensive, invasive inspections and to improve maintenance planning. However, a key finding was the need for a crucial **Key Partner**: experts in data interpretation.

The raw data from SIR is complex and requires geotechnical or soil structure expertise to translate it into actionable insights, a factor not fully emphasised in the initial BMC. This refined the **Value Proposition** to be not just data, but interpreted, decision-ready information. The **Customer Segment** of infrastructure managers was confirmed, but the feedback indicated a service-based revenue model would be preferred over purchasing the equipment outright.

- **Acoustic Emission System (AES):** The technical viability of the value proposition—detecting microcracks for predictive maintenance—was strongly confirmed by tests in both the French and Italian pilots, which demonstrated a high degree of accuracy in distinguishing normal operations from simulated failures. VNF engineers saw clear benefits, particularly for remote monitoring of infrastructure. The **Customer Segment** of infrastructure managers was validated. However, the Living Labs revealed practical implementation challenges related to **Key Activities**, such as the need for standardised sensor placement, better Wi-Fi connectivity for real-time data transfer, and the establishment of clear intervention thresholds based on historical data. The business model, therefore, requires a stronger emphasis on long-term data collection and calibration to be fully effective.
- **Smart Buoys (SB):** The Polish Living Lab validated the core value proposition: providing real-time data on water levels and bridge clearance to improve navigational safety on free-flowing rivers. Stakeholders, including infrastructure managers and software companies, confirmed their interest in this data as a service. The pilot voyages demonstrated the technology's effectiveness in providing new, valuable data streams like vessel counting and replacing manual measurements. However, the validation process also highlighted a critical dependency: the business model's success is entirely contingent on the fundamental navigability of the waterway. During the 2024 drought, the Vistula became unnavigable for extended periods, rendering the buoy data operationally irrelevant. This finding suggests a major risk factor for the business model that must be addressed in the **Key Partners** and **Risk Management** aspects.

Findings for Digital Integration Systems

- **Digital Twins (DTs):** The validation confirmed the DTs' role as a crucial data aggregator and analysis tool, providing value to both infrastructure managers (predictive maintenance) and transport operators (navigability forecasts). The modular, open-source architecture was identified as a key strength, enhancing its adaptability and long-term viability. A significant finding from the BMC workshops and LLs was that the DTs are unlikely to have a standalone commercial business model. Instead, their value is realised when integrated into larger systems like the SCMS or an infrastructure manager's internal platforms. This refines the **Channels** and **Revenue Streams** blocks, suggesting that revenue would be indirect, derived from licensing algorithms or integration services rather than direct user subscriptions. Stakeholder feedback also stressed the need for long-term historical data to make the predictive features truly reliable, a current limitation.
- **Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS):** The value proposition of a single point of information for actual and forecasted disruptions was strongly validated across all three Living Labs. The quantitative polling reinforced this, with the SCMS offer receiving appeal scores of **3.5/5** in France, **4.2/5** in Italy, and a polarised response in Poland (38% rated it highly, while 24% rated it poorly). The alert system was particularly valued. The BMC identified a wide range of customers, from LSPs and freight planners to transport operators, and this was confirmed during engagement sessions. However, the validation process revealed areas for refinement. French and Italian stakeholders noted that the BMC for the SCMS lacked detail on financial aspects; the finance block was rated poorly in both polls (**1.8/5 in France, 2.2/5 in**

Italy) with specific feedback calling for "proper numbers" and clearer quantification of costs and revenues. In contrast, Polish stakeholders rated the financial elements more positively (42.9% gave it a 4/5 score), though some requested more information on investment costs and potential subsidies.

A key finding that challenged the initial BMC was stakeholder scepticism regarding the real-time synchro-modal re-routing feature, especially involving rail, due to the rail sector's lack of operational flexibility. This suggests that the **Value Proposition** around dynamic multimodal rerouting is more aspirational than practical.

The revenue model based on a subscription fee was seen as plausible, but pricing would need to be carefully structured. Despite these challenges, stakeholders were optimistic about the system's potential, predicting it could attract a **+5-10% traffic growth** in France, a **+10-30% growth** in Italy, and an average of **+9.5%** in Poland.

SCMS Business Model Validation: Comparison of Poll Results

Table 2 provides a side-by-side view of stakeholder perceptions across the three pilot countries, focusing on the appeal of the SCMS, the assessment of its financial business case, and the anticipated impact on inland waterway traffic.

Table 2: CRISTAL SCMS BMC Comparison of Poll Results

Metric	France	Italy	Poland
Appeal of the SCMS Offer *(Rating: 1=Not appealing to 5=Very appealing) *	Score: 3.5 / 5	Score: 4.2 / 5	**Polarised Result:** • 38% rated it 4 or 5. • 24% rated it 1.
Assessment of Finance Block *(Rating: 1=Not at all well captured to 5=Comprehensively captured)*	Score: 1.8 / 5	Score: 2.2 / 5	**More Positive:** • 71.4% rated it 4 or 5.
Predicted IWT Traffic Growth *(If SCMS were fully implemented)*	+5% to +10%	**+10% to +30% (45% of respondents predicted +30%)	Average: +9.5%

4.5 Conclusions

This chapter undertook the validation of business models for the key innovations developed within the CRISTAL project. The validation process was structured around the Business Model Canvas (BMC), a methodology used to test the viability of how each innovation could create, deliver, and capture value. The primary validation mechanisms were a series of stakeholder-centric Living Lab workshops conducted across the three pilot sites in France, Italy, and Poland, supplemented by quantitative polls, operational data from pilot deployments, and a preliminary Social Cost-Benefit Analysis (SCBA).

The validation of the **sensor technologies (FOS, SIR, AES, Smart Buoys)** confirmed their core value propositions related to improving infrastructure maintenance and navigational safety. For **FOS**, the concept of real-time monitoring of riverbed sediment buildup was highly valued, but the business model was found to be commercially unviable due to prohibitive installation costs. The **SIR** model was validated as a valuable service for non-invasive inspection, with the crucial

refinement that its value lies in providing interpreted, expert analysis, not just raw data. The **AES** model proved technically robust, with its value in predictive maintenance being clearly recognised, though its full potential depends on long-term data calibration. The **Smart Buoys** model was validated for its data-as-a-service offering, but its viability was shown to be critically dependent on the fundamental navigability of the waterway, a significant external risk.

For the **digital platforms (Digital Twins and SCMS)**, the validation process provided critical insights into their market positioning and revenue logic. The **Digital Twins** were validated not as standalone commercial products but as essential enablers, with their value being realised through integration into larger systems. Their open-source, modular architecture was confirmed as a key strength for future adoption. The **SCMS** was strongly validated for its role as a centralised information hub for disruptions, with its alert system being particularly prized by stakeholders, as confirmed by high appeal scores in stakeholder polls (4.2/5 in Italy). The preliminary SCBA suggested financial viability is possible but highly dependent on market conditions like traffic volume. A key refinement to its business model was the recognition that the proposed dynamic synchro-modal re-routing functionality is more of a long-term vision. Furthermore, quantitative polling in France and Italy highlighted a major weakness in the financial aspects of the BMC, with stakeholders requesting more concrete cost and revenue figures.

Overall, the validation process successfully moved the business models from the *design* phase towards *implementation*. It highlighted a clear distinction between technical feasibility and commercial viability. While all innovations demonstrated technical potential, their business models require further refinement to address identified challenges. Key recurring themes included the necessity of strong partnerships, the difficulty of quantifying revenue streams without extensive pilot data, and the critical influence of external factors such as institutional governance and infrastructure quality. The validated and refined BMCs presented in this chapter now provide a more realistic and robust foundation for the final evaluation in WP10 and for future exploitation activities.

4.5.1 Validation

The validation exercise detailed in this chapter provided a comprehensive assessment of the business models associated with the CRISTAL project's innovations. By systematically testing the assumptions within each Business Model Canvas through Living Labs, quantitative polls, and pilot data, we have arrived at a more nuanced and realistic understanding of their potential for sustainable value creation.

The business models for the physical sensor technologies (**FOS, SIR, AE, and SB**) were validated as having strong, clearly defined value propositions for their primary customer segment: infrastructure managers. The need for better data to support predictive maintenance and enhance navigational safety is undeniable. However, the validation process also exposed critical barriers. The FOS model is, at present, not commercially viable due to high upfront costs, demonstrating a clear gap between technical potential and economic feasibility. The SIR and AES models were validated as viable services, but with the crucial caveat that they require a service layer of expert data interpretation to deliver true value, shifting the model from a product to a knowledge-based service. The Smart Buoys model was validated in principle, but its success was found to be fundamentally tethered to external conditions—namely, the physical navigability of the river—making it a high-risk proposition in volatile hydrological environments.

The business models for the digital platforms (**Digital Twins and SCMS**) underwent significant refinement. The initial hypothesis of a standalone, revenue-generating Digital Twin was

invalidated; instead, its value was confirmed as an integrated component within a larger ecosystem, likely monetised through licensing or integration services rather than direct user fees. This is a critical strategic clarification for its future exploitation. The SCMS business model was broadly validated, particularly its function as a central alert and information system. Stakeholders confirmed their willingness to pay for reliable, consolidated information that reduces operational uncertainty, giving the offer high appeal ratings in polls. However, the more ambitious value proposition of real-time synchro-modal re-routing was found to be premature. The model's dependency on the flexibility of external partners means this feature remains a future goal rather than a current, bankable asset. The SCBA results reinforce this by showing that profitability is highly conditional on traffic volumes and baseline network performance, underscoring the need for careful market-specific deployment strategies.

In conclusion, the validation process has confirmed that while the CRISTAL innovations offer significant value, their corresponding business models are not simple "plug-and-play" solutions. They are deeply embedded in a complex ecosystem of infrastructure, governance, and multi-modal operational realities. The refined business models are now more robust, with clearer customer segments, more realistic value propositions, and a better understanding of key partners and activities. This provides a solid, evidence-based foundation for the next stages of exploitation and implementation.

4.5.2 Reflections on Research

The research undertaken in Task 10.2 offers several important reflections on the process of validating business models for technological innovations within a complex, multi-stakeholder environment like inland waterway transport.

Firstly, the use of the **Business Model Canvas as a dynamic validation tool**, rather than a static design template, proved highly effective. It provided a common language and a structured framework that facilitated productive discussions among diverse participants, from highly technical engineers to commercially focused logistics operators. The visual nature of the canvas helped to quickly identify gaps and misalignments in the initial models, particularly the frequent absence of concrete cost and revenue estimations, a finding strongly reinforced by the low scores given to the finance block in French and Italian stakeholder polls.

Secondly, the **Living Lab methodology was indispensable** for grounding the business models in reality. The direct engagement with end-users and key stakeholders in each pilot country was crucial for moving from "perceived value" to a more empirically supported understanding of "realised value". This process revealed critical nuances that would have been missed in a purely theoretical exercise. For instance, the French LL highlighted the cultural and practical barriers to data sharing among competitors. The Italian LL demonstrated that technology adoption is deeply intertwined with governance reform, making the "Manifesto" a necessary precursor to a successful business model. The Polish LL starkly illustrated that no business model can succeed if the underlying physical infrastructure is not fit for purpose.

Thirdly, the integration of **quantitative polling** provided a valuable layer of validation. While qualitative discussions in LLs are rich with context, polls offered a structured way to measure consensus and pinpoint specific weaknesses. The consistent feedback across the French and Italian polls regarding the underdeveloped financial components of the SCMS BMC provided a clear, data-driven directive for future refinement. Conversely, the more positive assessment from Polish stakeholders on the financial elements, despite requests for more detail, suggests contextual differences in stakeholder expectations or perceived value. This mixed-methods

approach—combining qualitative depth with quantitative focus—should be considered a best practice.

Finally, the process revealed the **symbiotic but sometimes conflicting relationship between different innovations**. While the sensor technologies are designed to feed data to the Digital Twins and SCMS, their individual business models can exist independently. However, the business models for the DTs and SCMS are almost entirely dependent on the availability and quality of data from these upstream sources and external partners. This interconnectedness means that a failure in one part of the ecosystem can undermine the value proposition of another, making a holistic, ecosystem-level approach to business model validation essential.

4.5.3 Transferability to Future Research

The findings and methodological insights from this business model validation exercise offer significant transferable value for future research and innovation projects, particularly within the transport and logistics sectors.

First, the **mixed-methods validation framework** combining the Business Model Canvas, Living Labs, quantitative polling, and SCBA provides a robust and replicable template for validating innovations in other contexts. Future research projects could adopt this integrated approach to ensure that technological development is consistently aligned with market needs and commercial viability. The process of moving from co-created initial canvases (as in D4.3) to stakeholder-validated canvases (this chapter) can serve as a best-practice model. This is particularly relevant for projects funded under frameworks like Horizon Europe, which increasingly demand clear pathways to market exploitation.

Second, the validation of business models for **data-driven platforms like the Digital Twins and SCMS** yields transferable lessons. The conclusion that DTs are more likely to be exploited as integrated features rather than standalone products is a critical insight for the broader "digital twin" research community. It suggests that future research should focus not only on the technical architecture of DTs but also on their integration strategies and the business logic of the platforms they enhance. Similarly, the findings on the SCMS highlight the challenges of creating business models for synchro-modal platforms that rely on the cooperation of traditionally siloed transport sectors. Future research could explore governance models and incentive structures needed to overcome these barriers, making the "synchro-modal promise" a commercial reality.

Third, the research highlights the critical importance of **context-specific validation**. The stark differences in findings between the French, Italian, and Polish pilots demonstrate that a "one-size-fits-all" business model for IWT innovation is unlikely to succeed. Future research should explicitly incorporate cross-case analysis to distinguish between universally applicable principles and locally contingent factors. This is vital for developing scalable solutions that can still be adapted to diverse regulatory, infrastructural, and market environments. The lesson that organisational alignment and governance reform can be prerequisites for successful technology adoption, as seen in Italy, is a key transferable insight for projects in regions with fragmented institutional landscapes.

Finally, this work sets the stage for future research on the **long-term evolution and management of these business models** (Phase 5 of the design process). The current validation provides a baseline against which future performance can be measured. Longitudinal studies could track how these business models adapt as the technologies mature, as market conditions change, and as stakeholder relationships evolve. Future research could also focus on developing more sophisticated quantitative models for forecasting revenue and assessing ROI, using the rich

datasets that will be generated as these CRISTAL innovations are more widely deployed. This would help address the difficulty in early-stage quantification identified in this study and provide more concrete tools for investors and policymakers.

5. Evaluation of Pilot Operational Performance

5.1 Context

Task 10.3 was defined within the CRISTAL project specifically to conduct the operational validation of the implemented technologies. This validation exercise was critical for translating the theoretical potential of the innovations into tangible, measurable real-world outcomes. The comprehensive assessment focused on four core perspectives:

1. Gaining specific Operational Experiences;
2. Evaluating Performance in Practice;
3. Quantifying measurable Efficiency Improvements; and
4. Predicting the Broader Adoption Potential of the CRISTAL technologies.

The scope of validation encompassed four core technologies, consistently evaluated in conjunction with their associated Digital Twin (DT) solutions, where relevant. These technologies were segmented into two primary application categories:

1. **Maintenance Planning and Infrastructure Condition Assessment:** Technologies assisting infrastructure operators in assessing asset conditions for improved maintenance scheduling. This category includes technologies for structural health monitoring (Acoustic Emission, AE) systems and structural health inspection (Subsurface Inspection Radar, SIR).
2. **Enhanced Information Provision to Users:** Technologies enabling operators to supply enriched data to infrastructure users. This category primarily includes Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS) and Smart Buoys (SB).

These technologies were deployed and tested across the three primary pilot locations:

- French Pilot (VNF): Tested Acoustic Emission and Subsurface Inspection Radar.
- Italian Pilot (AIPO, IV): Tested Acoustic Emission, alongside navigation enhancement achieved through the pilot “own initiative”, i.e., the Smart Navigation Bulletin, which utilised machine learning (ML) algorithms integrated via the Digital Twin. (Note: FOS testing was limited to the laboratory due to technical challenges, but its potential informed the enhanced navigation forecasting).
- Polish Pilot (Ł-PIT, UniGDA): Tested the newly developed Smart Buoys.

A summary of which technologies were deployed in each of the River Pilots is given in Table 3. More details and further materials pertinent to this chapter are stored in Annex 3. CRISTAL Task 10.3 Questionnaire (for operational validation).

5.2 Technologies and Technical Innovations to be Validated

Task 10.3 aimed to support the operational validation of the technologies developed and implemented in the CRISTAL project pilots. The assessment focused on the following perspectives:

- **Operational Experiences:** What specific insights were gained during the operation of the technologies implemented in the pilot?
- **Performance in Practice:** How effectively did these technologies perform in real-world operations?
- **Efficiency Improvements:** What measurable efficiency gains were observed and can be assessed for the future?

- Broader Adoption Potential: What predictions can be made regarding the potential for wider adoption of the CRISTAL technologies?

The term “technologies” refers to the four technologies introduced in the CRISTAL project, consistently evaluated in conjunction with their associated Digital Twin solutions as a technological application, where relevant. Two of these technologies - Acoustic Emission and Subsurface Inspection Radar - assist infrastructure operators in assessing infrastructure conditions for improved maintenance planning. The other two - Fibre Optic Sensors and Smart Buoys - enable operators to provide enhanced information to infrastructure users.

Table 3: Technologies in CRISTAL pilot applications

French pilot - VNF	Italian pilot - AIPO, IV	Polish pilot - L-PIT, UniGDA
1. Acoustic emission 2. Subsurface Inspection Radar	1. (Fibre optic sensors) – Navigation bulletin ² 2. Acoustic emission	1. Smart buoys

5.3 Methodology for Operational Validation

Using a standardised questionnaire, semi-structured interviews were performed with infrastructure operators whose systems were used as testbeds for the technologies (see Annex 3). All relevant key performance indicators (KPIs) from previous WPs have been integrated into this questionnaire, which attempts to provide empirical support for the observed and anticipated shifts in operational procedures and strategic decision-making brought about by these technological advancements. The questionnaire is divided into two main sections: external aspects, which deal with effects on traffic dynamics and infrastructure users, and internal aspects, which deal with infrastructure management procedures.

Internally, the emphasis consists of:

- Infrastructure Status, assessing capacity changes pre- and post-technology implementation, operational disruptions, and real-time monitoring capabilities.
- Data Management for infrastructure maintenance, evaluating enhancements in data quality, availability, and processing speed.
- Technology Adoption, covering the number of technologies installed, satisfaction with their rollout, and anticipated return on investment, and
- Regulatory Compliance, tracking adherence to regulations and environmental standards

Externally, the questionnaire examines:

- External Impacts and Traffic Volumes, analysing the effects of increased traffic or extended usage, despite extreme weather events.
- Navigation Efficiency, assessing potential improvements in inland waterway (IWW) performance. and
- Intermodal Integration, exploring how the technology might boost IWW’s share in freight and passenger transport.

² The Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS) are currently limited to laboratory testing but show potential for improving navigation forecasting. In the Italian pilot, enhanced navigation forecasting was achieved through the integration of machine learning algorithms through the Digital Twin. The evaluation encompasses experiences of the operator with the Smart Navigation Bulletin and the incorporation of Digital Twin technology.

The partners in charge of Task 10.3 recognise the ambitious and thorough scope of the questionnaire. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are challenging for infrastructure operators to measure, and predictions about the future effects of fully deployed CRISTAL technologies are tentative and could be possibly inaccurate. This is because the trials were limited or even isolated, short-term tests that took place over days or weeks, it was especially challenging to estimate, even roughly, the majority of external KPIs. It is currently not possible to extrapolate long-term effects across the whole network of an operator or the larger European waterway system.

However, by integrating quantitative information with practitioner-provided qualitative insights, the questionnaire aims to offer a fair framework for evaluating the effects of the technologies. Every interview was done in a workshop setting or through bilateral discussions.

5.4 Findings

Findings are reported by pilot where the technology was implemented to a level to have an effect on operational performance.

Technologies tested in the French IWW network

Technologies tested by VNF in the French IWW network include the Acoustic Emission system and the Subsurface Inspection Radar.

Acoustic emission (AE) system

The test was carried out on the IWW segment Saone River, at one Lock (Lyon Couzon lock), on 13.05.24

Section 1: Infrastructure Status

IWW Capacity: The operator claims that the operation of these specific lock gates has little bearing on the inland waterway system's operational capacity. In particular, the waterway's throughput capacity is not directly constrained by the lock gate that was tested in this assessment. This suggests that the lock gate, as it stands, facilitates the unhindered passage of ships without adding to traffic jams or delays.

Type of Disruptions: The test was performed on a newly renovated lock gate that had received extensive maintenance before the assessment. Consequently, no previous operational failures or disturbances were noted at this particular gate. This condition gave a trustworthy starting point for assessing the gate's resilience and functionality by enabling a controlled evaluation of its performance under typical operating conditions.

Real-time Monitoring: No detailed information was available regarding the status of real-time infrastructure and water level monitoring, the average unplanned downtime of locks or river/canal segments, or the expected lifespan of infrastructure components before and after the introduction of CRISTAL technologies. The pilot's single-instance nature limits the ability to draw conclusions about these key performance indicators (KPIs). Additionally, the variability in damage profiles across different assets (e.g., locks, canal segments) complicates the extrapolation of findings from the lock to other infrastructure components.

Impact on Predictability of Maintenance Scheduling: The waterway network's current maintenance scheduling strategy mainly depends on reactive monitoring for anomalies like structural deterioration or mechanical failures. Although this approach is good at spotting problems right away, it lacks proactive ways to foresee maintenance requirements. In order to solve this, remote lock operation is being explored as a possible improvement to increase operational effectiveness and decrease downtime. Furthermore, acoustic emission (AE)

technology adoption is being investigated as a potential early irregularity detection tool. By detecting possible problems before they become serious disruptions, AE systems can record high-frequency stress waves produced by material deformation or microcracks, allowing predictive maintenance. By incorporating these technologies, maintenance schedules could become more accurate and predictable, reducing the likelihood of unexpected outages.

Data for other critical KPIs, including Real-Time Infrastructure Monitoring, Water Level Monitoring, Unplanned Downtime of Locks/Segments, Infrastructure Lifespan, and Impact on Overall Maintenance Costs, could not be provided at this stage. In order to support evidence-based decision-making in infrastructure management, improved data collection and analysis systems are required, as the lack of this data reveals a gap in current monitoring capabilities.

Section 2: Data Management for Infrastructure Maintenance

The accuracy and completeness of data related to infrastructure maintenance are being improved. It is expected that improved data quality will offer a more trustworthy basis for evaluating the state of vital assets, like lock gates, and for maximising maintenance plans. The evaluation was unable to determine the associated expenses, or the processing time needed to put these improvements into practice, though. Assessing the resources needed for data management improvements and assessing their cost-effectiveness in relation to long-term infrastructure maintenance requires further studies.

Section 3: Technology Adoption

Number of Specific Technological Objects Installed: 1

Satisfaction with technology usage was rated highly, though costs remain uncertain and require further investigation. Overall, the approach is regarded as to be very promising.

There is currently little clarity between the anticipated return on investment for the adopted technology. Comprehensive data on capital expenditures (CAPEX), such as the price of purchasing and setting up the technology, and operational expenditures (OPEX), such as maintenance and operating costs, must be gathered to properly calculate ROI.

Section 4: Regulatory Compliance

There are currently no regulatory standards or compliance frameworks that have to be followed in order to use the technologies tested in this evaluation. Since no further approvals or certifications are required at this time, the absence of regulatory restrictions makes it easier for these technologies to be adopted. To guarantee continued compliance as standards change, it is advised to continuously monitor regulatory developments, especially in light of new technologies for waterway infrastructure.

Section 6³: External Impacts and Traffic Volumes

Since the operator does not routinely record extreme weather events, data on the frequency of these events impacting the waterway infrastructure could not be provided. The lack of a widely accepted definition of "extreme weather events" for transport infrastructure in the European Union is apparent in this data collection gap. The absence of a standardised definition makes it more difficult to evaluate how weather affects waterway operations, even though different EU bodies and agencies have created working definitions for particular uses. It would be easier to assess the effects of extreme weather events on operational continuity and infrastructure resilience if a clear framework for identifying and documenting them had been established.

³ Section 5 in the questionnaire is about the internal KPIs of only the Italian pilot, that is why it is not mentioned in the French and Polish analysis.

Section 7: Traffic Observations Before and After CRISTAL Impact:

The reliability of lock gate operations is anticipated to be improved by the deployment of the tested technology, referred to as the "CRISTAL Impact." Because more consistent and predictable operations may draw more vessel traffic, improved reliability is likely to lead to higher traffic volumes. However, because there is currently no baseline data and the technology deployment is still in its early stages, it is impossible to quantify this impact.

Section 8: Navigation Efficiency and Intermodal Integration:

There was not enough evidence to assess how the tested technology affected intermodal integration or navigation efficiency. One of the most important metrics for evaluating the effectiveness of waterway infrastructure is navigation efficiency, which considers variables like transit times and lock operation speeds. In the same way, intermodal integration is crucial to the optimisation of the larger transportation system. The scarcity of evidence in these areas emphasises the necessity of thorough performance metrics for fully understanding how the technology affects waterway operations.

Conclusion

The technology has the potential to increase asset management efficiency, according to VNF respondents, and the acoustic emission, in particular seems ideal for the company's plans to switch to remote control of its infrastructure assets. The acoustic emissions (AE) system established for the CRISTAL project is a long-standing method for inland waterway infrastructure predictive maintenance. Early detection of microcracks reduces unscheduled interventions, increases asset life, and improves reliability. Scalability across structures, low-disruption sensor deployment, and early warnings are important features. VNF could benefit from data-driven insights to support maintenance planning and supplement visual inspections if it were integrated into biannual inspections. Standardising sensor placement, establishing intervention thresholds, and enhancing real-time communication—for example, through Wi-Fi extenders—are needed to achieve full adoption.

Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR)

The evaluation is based on the deployment of the SIR system in the pilot on a wide gauge lock on the river Seine, which is not named here for confidentiality reasons. The technology was deployed on two further narrow-gauge locks later in the project, but this was not included in this assessment.

Section 1: Infrastructure Status

Capacity: The inspection of the concrete walls of the lock, as part of the pilot implementation of CRISTAL technologies, does not directly influence the lock's operational capacity. Consequently, no specific data on the segment's capacity, measured in vessels per day, could be provided for the periods before and after the technology's deployment. This lack of impact on capacity suggests that the inspection process, which involves non-invasive diagnostic techniques, does not disrupt normal lock operations or restrict vessel throughput. Rather than the inspection process interrupting vessel movement through the lock, the inspection can be interrupted to permit passage of vessels. However, the absence of quantitative data limits the ability to assess whether the technology indirectly enhances capacity by improving the lock's operational reliability.

The potential benefits of the CRISTAL technologies in mitigating disruptions has been estimated with respect to the scenario of the scenario in a recent period. In the considered period, there were thirty-two interventions to maintain the waterway in, or restore it to, a navigable state occurred. Only five of them halted navigation on this infrastructure (the other infrastructure

remained functional, allowing this Seine segment to stay open for navigation). Of the 32 interventions, only nine were corrective (addressing incidents requiring repairs). The remainder were preventive (two mandated by law, 21 for technical reasons). The most frequent interventions (six in total) involved electrical signage for navigators, with no impact on navigation. The most problematic issues were logjams (also known as woody debris blockages), which occurred three times last year and caused navigation restrictions, and electrical dysfunctions, which also occurred three times and halted navigation. Considering this scenario and disruptions described above, it was challenging to evaluate the baseline performance of the lock or the potential benefits of the CRISTAL technologies in mitigating disruptions.

Real-time Monitoring: No detailed information was available regarding the status of real-time infrastructure and water level monitoring, the average unplanned downtime of locks or river/canal segments, or the expected lifespan of infrastructure components before and after the introduction of CRISTAL technologies. The pilot's single-instance nature limits the ability to draw conclusions about these key performance indicators (KPIs). Additionally, the variability in damage profiles across different assets (e.g., locks, canal segments) complicates the extrapolation of findings from the lock to other infrastructure components.

Predictability of Maintenance Scheduling: The use of Subsurface Inspection Radar is expected to enhance the predictability of maintenance scheduling by providing deeper insights into the condition of the lock's concrete walls. By employing advanced diagnostic tools—potentially including non-destructive testing methods the technology enables a more precise understanding of structural integrity. This improved visibility supports proactive asset management, allowing VNF to schedule maintenance activities based on actual asset conditions rather than reactive or calendar-based approaches. Such advancements could reduce unplanned downtime and optimise resource allocation, although quantitative evidence of these benefits was not available from the pilot. However, it is uncertain whether the maximum depth for an accurate and reliable scanning could be over 1-1.5 meter normal to the surface scanned. Currently, SIR can detect variations in ground composition, but the specific materials of the detected features of interest cannot be determined with high accuracy due to limitations of the technology. In this context, the technology must be paired with invasive methods, such as core sampling. SIR can assist in selecting optimal locations for core sampling. However, as SIR is highly effective at locating metals, it is valuable for specific asset detection.

Overall Maintenance Costs: The impact of inspections with the SIR system on overall maintenance costs could not be evaluated due to the lack of cost-related data over longer period of times. Without information on the costs of implementing the technology, conducting inspections, or performing subsequent maintenance activities, it is not possible to assess whether the technology offers cost savings compared to more traditional methods. For now, it could just decrease the number of core samplings. A detailed cost-benefit analysis, incorporating both capital expenditures (e.g., equipment and installation costs) and operational expenditures (e.g., labour and maintenance costs), is necessary to determine the financial implications of adopting the technology on a broader scale.

Section 2: Data Management for Infrastructure Maintenance

Since testing the technology's diagnostic capabilities rather than redesigning data management procedures was the primary focus of the pilot, its narrow scope probably made it challenging to evaluate these factors. A lack of standardised data about the organisation's infrastructure is a constant challenge.

Section 3: Technology Adoption

The pilot involved the deployment of one technological equipment, used to inspect the concrete walls of the Seine lock. A second deployment might happen at the Moselle basin. Its initial deployment was a proof-of-concept approach to evaluating its feasibility in a real-world setting. The successful deployment of this single device represents an initial step toward integrating advanced technologies into waterway infrastructure management, though broader adoption would require further testing and validation.

Section 4: Regulatory Compliance

The pilot did not encounter any compliance-related incidents, as there is currently no established regulatory framework governing the use of lock inspections. This absence of regulatory requirements simplifies the adoption process, as no specific certifications or approvals are needed. Each territory develops its own preventive maintenance plan to manage the upkeep of the assets it oversees. These plans are theoretical exercises, not standardised across territories, and are not mandatory due to budgetary constraints. They serve as a tool for each team to organise its work. Mandatory maintenance plans are beginning to be implemented, but only for critical hydraulic assets, such as dams or dikes, and not for locks. In one living lab, colleagues suggested that if the SIR system could provide comprehensive data, it might become mandatory to use it regularly (e.g., every few years) to monitor the condition of all our infrastructure, particularly critical assets. The supervising Ministry could enforce this, but given the current limitations of SIR technology, it is not feasible at this time.

Section 6: External Impacts and Traffic Volumes

There was no information available regarding the frequency of severe weather events or how they affected the lock. A larger issue in the European Union is the absence of a common definition for extreme weather events and their effects on transportation infrastructure, which is reflected in the absence of data on these occurrences. The lock recorded 9,663 passages in 2023, including 1,180 convoy passages, 1,346 pleasure craft passages, and 7,137 freight movements. Convoy passages dropped to 1,080, freight movements to 6,799, and pleasure craft to 1,339 in 2024, for a total of 9,218 passages.

Section 7 and 8: Navigation Efficiency and Intermodal Integration

There was no information available to evaluate the effect on intermodal integration (e.g., connectivity with rail or road transport) or navigation efficiency (e.g., vessel transit times, lock operation speeds). The pilot's emphasis on infrastructure diagnostics rather than operational or network-wide results suggests why there is no data.

Conclusion

The Subsurface Inspection Radar technology for inspecting the condition of structures could improve maintenance predictions for inland waterway systems, but the data still needs to be fully analysed. It provides non-invasive insights into substructure conditions, potentially enabling early degradation detection, optimised maintenance, and cost savings. The system is technically feasible for data collection and initial processing, but identifying subsurface material layers requires geotechnical and/or soil structure expertise. While data acquisition succeeded, limited in-house analysis capacity has delayed the processing. A closer collaboration with geotechnical, soil- or even bionic experts is needed to translate data into actionable insights for infrastructure managers. It is vital to understand better what materials apart from metals are discovered in the data and what their further impact might be.

Technologies tested in the Italian IWW network

The Italian River Pilot aims to achieve three primary goals: enhancing the reliability of inland waterways, improving their sustainability, and optimising the preventive maintenance of locks and riverbeds. Within the project, technology applications were carried out at two different infrastructure manager operators in Italy, i.e., Agenzia Interregionale per il Fiume Po (AIPo) and Infrastrutture Venete (IV).

Agenzia Interregionale per il Fiume Po (AIPo)

This section provides an overview of the Agenzia Interregionale per il Fiume Po (AIPo) Smart Bulletin technology's operational validation. By extending the forecast period to 10 days and improving event predictability, the Smart Bulletin improves navigation forecasting for the Po River. The operational effects, efficiency improvements, and potential for wider use of this technology in the context of inland waterway (IWW) management are the main topics of the questionnaire answers supplied by AIPo. With an emphasis on the Smart Bulletin, AIPo offered answers tailored to the Po River segment. Where precise measurements were not available, qualified estimations were used to supplement quantitative data.

Technology Overview

A forecasting tool referred to the Smart Bulletin was created for improving the predictability of navigation along the Po River, a free-flowing waterway. The Smart Bulletin uses advanced data analytics, such as machine learning (ML) and statistical algorithms validated with 20 years of historical data, to provide longer and more accurate navigation forecasts than traditional methods that only use daily boat water level measurements. The technology seeks to improve stakeholder satisfaction, maintenance scheduling, and operational efficiency.

Section 1: Infrastructure Status

Capacity: For mean, low, or high-water levels along the Po River, no precise data on vessel capacity—measured in vessels per day—was supplied. The Po River's navigability is greatly impacted by natural hydrological conditions, unlike controlled waterways with lock systems, making it difficult to measure vessel capacity without standardised measurement points. By increasing the predictability of navigable conditions, the Smart Bulletin's deployment—which focuses on water level forecasting—may indirectly support capacity planning even though it does not directly address vessel capacity metrics.

Real-Time Monitoring: Before the Smart Bulletin, water level monitoring along the Po River was done every day using boat-based measurements, which covered the whole stretch from Cremona to the river estuary (100% coverage). Due to the frequency and logistical difficulties of manual measurements, this time-consuming method produced accurate but limited data. By extending water level forecasts to a 10-day horizon and improving the predictability of hydrological events like floods or low-water periods, the Smart Bulletin technology, which uses machine learning (ML) algorithms, improves this process. This extended forecasting capability lessens the need for daily boat operations while maintaining 100% coverage of the river segment. As an alternative to boat-based measurements, the potential application of Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS) was investigated, providing the opportunity for automated, ongoing monitoring. Only in lab settings have the FOS been tested. However, a number of factors, including installation complexity, environmental conditions, and cost considerations, appear to make FOS implementation technically challenging.

Technology Readiness Level: The Smart Bulletin's machine learning algorithms have been validated in an operational setting, showing strong performance in predicting hydrological events and water levels. This validation shows that the technology is developed enough for practical use

and can supply accurate data to assist with river management choices. Nevertheless, there are still issues with completely integrating the Smart Bulletin with currently in use operational systems, like those for infrastructure management or navigation planning. To overcome these integration obstacles, customisation is needed, which includes making sure the technology works with legacy systems, adjusting to site-specific hydrological conditions, and educating staff on how to use it efficiently. To optimise the Smart Bulletin's operational impact and guarantee its smooth integration throughout the Po River's management framework, these improvements are essential.

Unplanned Downtime: Since the Po River lacks fixed infrastructure elements like locks or canal segments that are susceptible to operational or mechanical failures, the idea of unplanned downtime does not apply to it. Because the river flows freely, natural causes like low water levels, shifting sediments, or severe weather events—rather than infrastructure-related outages—are the main causes of navigational disruptions. Because the Smart Bulletin's main purpose is to improve forecasting rather than handle fixed infrastructure maintenance, its effect on this metric is therefore minimal.

Infrastructure Lifespan: Not applicable, as the technology does not directly affect physical infrastructure like lock gates or canal walls.

Maintenance Predictability: By offering longer and more precise water level forecasts, the Smart Bulletin greatly improves the predictability of maintenance scheduling. Better resource allocation for dredging, the most crucial maintenance task, is made possible by this increased predictability. For the Po River to remain navigable, dredging is essential. According to estimates, the technology could enable operators to proactively schedule dredging operations during ideal conditions, increasing the number of navigable days annually from 240 to 250, a 4.2% improvement. By facilitating more steady vessel traffic, this extension of navigable days may improve the river's economic viability. To achieve these advantages, though, the Smart Bulletin's forecasts must be thoroughly incorporated into current maintenance procedures and validated using long-term operational data.

Maintenance Costs: By improving shift management and personnel planning, the Smart Bulletin should lower overall maintenance costs. The technology allows for more effective scheduling of maintenance tasks by offering trustworthy 10-day forecasts, which lessens the need for reactive interventions during unfavourable conditions. Dredging operations, for instance, can be scheduled during times when water levels are stable, which reduces the need for labour and equipment. However, the lack of baseline data and the variation in maintenance practices across various river segments make it difficult to quantify these cost savings. To support these estimates and assess the technology's financial impact, a thorough cost-benefit analysis that considers information on staff hours, equipment usage, and operational disruptions must be conducted.

Section 2: Data Management for Infrastructure Maintenance

Data Accuracy and Processing: By improving shift management and personnel planning, the Smart Bulletin should lower overall maintenance costs. The technology allows for more effective scheduling of maintenance tasks by offering trustworthy 10-day forecasts, which lessens the need for reactive interventions during unfavourable conditions. Dredging operations, for instance, can be scheduled during times when water levels are stable, which reduces the need for labour and equipment. However, the lack of baseline data and the variation in maintenance practices across various river segments make it difficult to quantify these cost savings. To support these estimates and assess the technology's financial impact, a thorough cost-benefit analysis that considers information on staff hours, equipment usage, and operational disruptions must be conducted.

Section 3: Technology Adoption

Technological Objects Installed: One Smart Bulletin system was deployed as part of the pilot implementation on the Po River. This system, designed to provide extended water level forecasts using ML and statistical algorithms, represents a novel approach to predictive hydrological modelling for free-flowing waterways. The installation of a single unit suggests a controlled, proof-of-concept study aimed at evaluating the technology's feasibility and performance in an operational context.

Satisfaction Level: Overall, AIPo expressed satisfaction with the Smart Bulletin system, stating that only minor adjustments are required to meet operational expectations. However, the lack of specific stakeholder feedback or qualitative evaluations limits the ability to pinpoint exact areas that need improvement. The system's ability to provide accurate 10-day water level forecasts, which improve navigational and maintenance planning decision-making, is probably the main reason for user satisfaction. The identified need for minor enhancements could be related to difficulties with user interface optimisation, system integration, or hydrological site-specific adaptation.

Return on Investment: Stakeholder satisfaction, not financial metrics, was the primary metric used to assess the Smart Bulletin's return on investment. This emphasis on qualitative results over quantitative financial returns implies that the technology's operational usefulness and acceptability are currently used to determine its value. AIPo stated that if stakeholder satisfaction is attained, even a negative financial return on investment would be acceptable, underscoring the strategic significance of accurate forecasting. However, evaluating the technology's cost-effectiveness is hampered by the absence of financial ROI data. Quantifying the technology's financial viability requires a thorough economic analysis that considers capital expenditures (such as system installation and hardware costs), operational expenditures (such as maintenance and employee training), and potential cost savings (such as lower labour or dredging costs).

Section 4: Regulatory Compliance

Compliance Incidents: During the Smart Bulletin's pilot program, no incidents connected with compliance were reported. The lack of incidents indicates that the technology complies with Italy's current waterway management regulations. Nonetheless, this result might also be influenced by the absence of a particular compliance framework for predictive hydrological technologies.

Environmental Standards: Since the Smart Bulletin's main purpose is hydrological forecasting rather than mitigating environmental impacts, it does not specifically address any environmental standards. There was no information on how the technology affected environmental indicators like ecosystem health, water quality, or carbon emissions from river management operations.

Inspection Time and Costs: As the technology focuses on predictive modelling rather than physical inspections, its impact on these metrics may be indirect by reducing the need for manual water level measurements.

Section 5: Italian KPIs

An evaluation of the impact was conducted using specific KPIs for the Italian pilot and additional user surveys (Table 4).

132 prediction points were established along the river, confirming improved reliability for potentially increasing the modal share. Users rated the Smart Bulletin, as a notable enhancement to operational communication and planning.

Table 4: (Preliminary) Results of Italian KPIs related to the navigation forecast and the smart bulletin

Technology	KPIs	How the KPI is measured	Measuring data	Baseline	Final
Forecast model	Navigation forecast points along the river	Test	Number of forecast points	0	132
Smart bulletin	Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale)	Measured	Questionnaire in a Living Lab event	N/A	Likert Scale Question1 ⁴ : 4.06 Question 2: 3.35
Smart bulletin	Smart bulletin downloads	Measured	Counter on AIPO web site/service	20	Data available at the end of the project
Smart bulletin	Registered users	Measured	No. of subscriptions (on AIPO platform)	15	Data available at the project's end

In a workshop in Mantova, 63% of users indicated that a 10-day forecast significantly improves planning for the Po River and connected inland waterways. Across various scenarios (normal operations, infrastructure failure, extreme weather), participants rated the technologies' usefulness and reliability as "very high" on a Likert scale. The deviation between forecasts and actual conditions was only 8–11 cm, with navigation condition classification accuracy exceeding 95% due to the algorithms developed in the Digital Twin.

The Italian pilot has been evaluated regarding the technologies' impact using some KPIs, comparing operational results to pre-test estimates.

Section 6: External Impacts and Traffic Volumes

Extreme Weather Incidents: High and low water events, which are important external factors affecting navigability in free-flowing waterways, were recorded during the Smart Bulletin technology pilot project on the Po River. However, no precise information about the frequency, length, or intensity of these occurrences was given. The lack of quantitative indicators, like the frequency of high-water (flood) or low-water (drought) events annually, makes it difficult to evaluate how they affect river operations or how well the Smart Bulletin works to minimise related disruptions. Furthermore, there was no obvious pattern showing that the intensity of high or low water levels increased over time, indicating that the Po River's hydrological variability stays within expected ranges. The Smart Bulletin's 10-day forecasting capability is designed to enhance preparedness for such events by providing predictive insights into water level fluctuations. These forecasts could enable proactive navigation planning and maintenance scheduling, potentially reducing the operational impacts of extreme weather.

Traffic Observations: Key traffic-related metrics, such as the number of vessels, cargo volume, transport work (ton-kilometres), throughput (e.g., vessels per day), and congestion levels before and after the Smart Bulletin's implementation, were not quantitatively reported. It is predicted that the Smart Bulletin's more accurate water level forecasts will make it easier to navigate, which will increase traffic volumes by allowing more reliable vessel operations, especially during times of hydrological variability. However, because there is an absence of baseline and post-implementation traffic data, this hypothesis has not been looked at.

⁴ Q1: Do you think a +10-day forecast smart bulletin improves planning capacity in freight or passenger transport? Q2: Do you think the information contained is sufficient?

Section 7: Navigation Efficiency

Navigation efficiency metrics such as cargo capacity (e.g., maximum load per vessel), operational costs (e.g., fuel or labour expenses), delays (e.g., frequency and duration), and vessel timeliness (e.g., adherence to schedules) were not specifically mentioned. By avoiding low-water conditions that limit cargo capacity or require detours, accurate forecasts can help vessels operate more efficiently overall. Nevertheless, these advantages remain hypothetical in the absence of quantitative evidence. Furthermore, incorporating economic models to evaluate cost savings from fewer delays or better cargo loads would offer a thorough comprehension of the operational advantages of the technology.

Section 8: Intermodal Integration

Modal Share and Passenger Volumes: Passenger volumes and modal share were not presented. However, by making inland waterway transportation more reliable, better forecasting reliability may indirectly improve intermodal integration by allowing freight to move from rail or road to water-based systems, which are frequently more sustainable. Furthermore, even though the Po River's navigation system is not primarily focused on passenger transport, gathering information on passenger vessel activity may shed light on the technology's wider applicability.

Conclusion

The Smart Bulletin demonstrates significant potential for improving navigation forecasting on the Po River. Key operational benefits include:

- **Centralised Communication:** The Smart Bulletin digitises operational communication between authorities, port operators, and waterway users, replacing fragmented traditional methods (e.g., fax, email, phone).
- **Real-Time Alerts:** Its online interface and notification system deliver updates on hydrological conditions, maintenance, malfunctions, or closures, supporting user decision-making.
- **Enhanced Efficiency:** By minimising outdated or inconsistent information, it reduces delays, diversions, or incidents, supporting safer navigation.
- **Extended Forecast Horizon:** The 10-day forecast enhances predictability compared to daily bulletins, supporting better planning for navigation and maintenance.
- **Maintenance Efficiency:** Improved dredging resource allocation could extend navigable days by approximately 4% (from 240 to 250 days) reducing operational disruptions.
- **Stakeholder Satisfaction:** The technology deployment by AIPo prioritises user satisfaction, aligning with AIPo's operational goals.
- **Accessible Interface:** The platform provides a straightforward interface, usable on desktop and mobile devices, suitable for varying technical expertise.
- **Customizable Notifications:** Users can select specific alerts (e.g., low water levels, maintenance, events) relevant to their operations.
- **Scalable Design:** The Smart Bulletin can be adapted for other regions and waterway authorities, aiding standardised communication across TEN-T corridors.

However, challenges remain:

- **Quantification Gaps:** Limited quantitative data on capacity, traffic volumes, and cost savings make it difficult to assess its impact on operations.
- **Implementation Challenges:** The potential use of FOS as an alternative to boat-based measurements requires further expansion due to installation and operational difficulties.

- Customization Needs: While machine learning algorithms are validated, further refinements are needed to optimise integration into AIPo's workflows.

With the potential to be used more widely in other IWW segments, the Smart Bulletin presents a promising tool for improving navigation forecasting on the Po River. Significant operational efficiencies could result from its capacity to increase navigable days and enhance maintenance scheduling. Broader adoption, though, will necessitate:

- A thorough assessment of the effects on traffic volumes, expenses, and vessel throughput.
- Resolving technical issues, like the deployment of FOS.
- Additional verification in various operational settings to guarantee scalability.

Infrastrutture Venete (IV)

The acoustic emission was tested at IV, but the operator has not yet received any results at the time when IV was interviewed. Moreover, IV commissioned the feasibility study on cold ironing. It, therefore, made no sense to use the questionnaire for the interview with IV. In addition, IV provided comments on the operational validation of the technologies, which are summarised further.

Aside from Acoustic Emission (AE), IV has not directly tested any of the four CRISTAL technologies in the project. As for the AE test at the Baricetta lock, the party responsible for the test has not yet provided any feedback to IV. When it comes to improved monitoring and forecasting of water levels, IV is not the appropriate contact, as it oversees the canals between the Po River and the Venice lagoon rather than the Po River itself (refer to the explanatory note below for further details). For inquiries about better water level forecasting and navigability predictions, the project partner APo is the more suitable contact.

Overall, IV is interested in enhancing water level information, as it would improve the river and canal system's usability for users. This could lead to greater resilience and perceived reliability in managing critical situations within the main Northern Italy waterway system (known as the Padano-Veneto inland waterway system), which includes both the IV network and the Po River. However, the benefits for IV are more indirect, with many canal users being tourist boats and cruise ships. Smart buoy developments have not been tested in Italy, but IV can envision deploying such buoys in specific locations, such as the mouth of the waterway and the Adriatic Sea, or other points in its network of rivers and canals, to improve traffic monitoring (since there are no navigation locks to track traffic data in these areas).

IV conducted the feasibility study on cold ironing within this project, but this study is not a technical application and will not be discussed further in 10.3.

For its infrastructure, IV focuses on removing bottlenecks to allow larger ships to navigate through its system.

Technology tested in the Polish IWW network

General Information:

Organisation: The infrastructure operator for Poland waterways was not involved in the CRISTAL project. The information was collected with the help of the Polish project partners, L-PIT and University of Gdansk.

IWW segment(s): Lower Vistula River

Technology tested: In Poland, the newly developed Smart buoys have been tested.

Section 1: Infrastructure Status

- **Capacity:** The Smart Buoys deployed on the Lower Vistula River are equipped to measure water levels, providing critical data for assessing navigability in a free-flowing river system. Additionally, when paired with supplementary equipment installed at bridges, the buoys can measure bridge clearance heights, enabling vessels to safely navigate under low-clearance structures. Six buoys were deployed, covering approximately 70–80% of the Lower Vistula River segment. This coverage provides substantial monitoring of the river’s navigable extent. The buoys’ ability to measure water levels and bridge clearance supports capacity planning by informing operators of navigable conditions, particularly during low-water periods common in Central European rivers. A potential to shift 1.9 million tons of cargo annually seems feasible once minimum navigation channel depths of 2.5 meters are secured, especially in the Odra and Lower Vistula corridors⁵. However, quantitative data on vessel capacity (e.g., vessels per day) were not provided, likely due to the river’s low traffic volume.
- **Disruptions:** During the river pilot phase, three unplanned river closures caused major operational disruptions and extended vessel idle times, particularly during drought conditions that decreased the depth of navigable water. Because there is less navigational activity, there are fewer operational disruptions, like delays or closures, which are usually linked to infrastructure failures in waterways with higher traffic volumes. Therefore, it was not possible to assess the Smart Buoys’ contribution to disruption mitigation in this particular context.
- **Real-time Monitoring:** Water level and, where relevant, bridge clearance height readings are provided by the Smart Buoys in nearly real-time. These measurements aren’t continuous, though, because bridge clearance and hydrological parameters don’t change quickly over time, requiring ongoing observation. Operational efficiency and data relevance are balanced by the buoys’ periodic data collection, which is adequate to record notable changes in river conditions.
- **Technology Readiness Level:** The Smart Buoys were fully deployed and operational in real-world conditions on the Lower Vistula River, achieving a high technology readiness level (TRL8). This successful deployment demonstrates the buoys’ robustness in an operational environment, capable of withstanding the river’s hydrological and environmental conditions. The technology’s readiness suggests it is suitable for broader implementation, though scalability across other river systems requires further validation. Since the Smart Buoys’ main purpose is to facilitate navigation using real-time hydrological and clearance data, they are not intended for infrastructure surveillance or maintenance. The buoys don’t directly prolong the life of infrastructure, in contrast to technologies designed to monitor tangible assets like lock gates or canal walls. They only provide operational support for river navigation, which emphasises the difference between infrastructure and navigational monitoring technologies.

Section 2: Data Management for Infrastructure Maintenance

Monitored issues: The Smart Buoys monitor three key parameters: river water levels, bridge clearance heights, and vessel counts. These parameters are critical for assessing navigability and supporting operational planning on the Lower Vistula River. The integration of these data streams into a cohesive monitoring system represents a significant advancement in real-time data provision for free-flowing waterways.

⁵ Findings from Deliverable D9.2

Prior to the Smart Buoys, water level measurements were conducted manually, requiring significant labour and equipment resources, such as boats and vehicles. The automation provided by the buoys reduces the need for manual measurements, potentially yielding substantial savings in man-hours and operational costs. Quantitative data on these savings were not available, but the transition to automated monitoring is likely to enhance efficiency by minimising logistical overhead.

Bridge clearance measurements, enabled by supplementary equipment installed at bridges, represent a novel data provision not previously available to IWW users on the Lower Vistula. This additional information enhances navigational safety by ensuring vessels can pass under bridges without risk of collision, particularly during high-water events. The introduction of this metric addresses a critical gap in operational data, supporting safer and more efficient navigation.

The vessel counting is also a new feature provided by the Smart Buoys. This capability enables operators to monitor navigational activity, supporting traffic management and planning. However, no quantitative data on vessel counts was given.

Section 3: Technology Adoption

Seventy to eighty percent of the Lower Vistula River was covered by six Smart Buoys. Sensors for measuring bridge clearance and water level are incorporated into the buoys' design, and communication modules are integrated for data transfer.

Satisfaction with the Use of Technology: Stakeholders expressed satisfaction with the Smart Buoys, stating that only minor adjustments were required to meet operational expectations. These stakeholders included representatives from PIT and the University of Gdansk. Effective training and technology integration were highlighted by post-training surveys that showed 73% of ship operators felt comfortable using the digital twin dashboard. Although specific feedback was not given, buoy durability during high-water periods—when debris accumulation in the fall and winter poses a risk of damage—is one possible area for improvement. This environmental issue emphasises the necessity of careful design considerations, such as debris-resistant materials or protective mechanisms.

Return on Investment (ROI): Adopting IWT over traditional road transport is economically viable, suggested by the pilot voyages' net logistics cost savings of 11–18% on door-to-door chains. Automated monitoring may have a positive economic impact by lowering labour and equipment costs, but a thorough cost-benefit analysis is required to assess return on investment. Non-monetary advantages like increased stakeholder satisfaction and navigational safety should also be considered in this analysis.

Section 4: Regulatory Compliance

Regarding the Smart Buoys' operation on the Lower Vistula River, no regulatory requirements or compliance issues were documented. Although it makes deployment easier, the lack of a specific regulatory framework for these technologies could present problems in the future as standards change. However, the test trips revealed a number of regulatory obstacles that limit operational flexibility, especially with regard to cross-border transport laws and vessel approvals.

Section 6: External Impacts and Traffic Volumes

Traffic Observations: Due to the low level of navigational activity in the Lower Vistula, no quantitative data on traffic volumes—such as the number of vessels or the throughput of cargo—were supplied. It is predicted that the Smart Buoys' improved accuracy of water level and bridge clearance data may boost navigational confidence and possibly increase traffic volumes. But because there is a lack of baseline and post-implementation data, this impact cannot be measured.

Section 7: Navigation Efficiency

By solving planning issues in naturally occurring, low-water rivers like the Lower Vistula, the Smart Buoys have the potential to increase the efficiency of cargo transport. Rivers in central Europe frequently experience seasonal low water levels, which limit ship drafts and cargo capacities and make operational planning more difficult. Operators can optimise routes and schedules by using the buoys' real-time data on water levels and bridge clearance, which could decrease delays and increase cargo throughput. Because it automates monitoring tasks, the technology is regarded as cost-effective. Despite high lock-induced variance, 94% on-time reliability was attained, underscoring the necessity of better synchronisation between IWT and other modes of transportation. Nevertheless, no precise information regarding the timeliness, delays, expenses, transit durations, or cargo capacity of the vessel could be supplied.

Section 8: Intermodal Integration:

Since the Smart Buoys are primarily used to support freight navigation forecasting on the Lower Vistula River, no information regarding modal share or passenger volumes was supplied. The technology's direct applicability to passenger transportation or intermodal connectivity with other modes, like rail or road, is limited by its emphasis on freight operations. However, by making inland waterway freight transportation more competitive, improved navigational reliability may indirectly promote intermodal integration by allowing cargo to be moved from rail or road to water. Supply chain optimisation required efficient integration with rail and road transportation, highlighting the necessity of coordinated planning across various modes of transportation.

5.5 Conclusions

The work conducted under Task 10.3 was dedicated to the operational validation of technologies implemented within the CRISTAL project. This assessment focused on gaining specific insights into operational experiences, measuring performance in practice, quantifying efficiency improvements, and predicting the broader adoption potential of the CRISTAL technologies.

The technologies evaluated included four core solutions, assessed where relevant in conjunction with their associated Digital Twin solutions. Two categories of technologies were involved: those assisting infrastructure operators with maintenance planning (Acoustic Emission and Subsurface Inspection Radar) and those enabling operators to provide enhanced information to infrastructure users (Fibre Optic Sensors and Smart Buoys). These were tested across the pilot applications in France (Acoustic Emission, Subsurface Inspection Radar), Italy (Acoustic Emission, Smart Bulletin based on ML and statistical algorithms for the elaboration of manual measurements, since Fibre Optic Sensors were limited to the lab), and Poland (Smart Buoys).

The validation methodology employed a standardised questionnaire and semi-structured interviews with infrastructure operators. This process aimed to gather empirical support for shifts in operational procedures and strategic decision-making by integrating Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) from previous work packages. The questionnaire covered internal aspects (such as infrastructure status, data management, and technology adoption) and external aspects (including traffic dynamics, navigation efficiency, and intermodal integration). Acknowledging the challenge that trials were limited, often being isolated, short-term tests over days or weeks, it was noted that estimating external KPIs and extrapolating long-term effects was particularly difficult.

Key Findings by Pilot Application:

- **French Pilot:** Structural health monitoring of lock gates using the Acoustic Emission (AE) system was rated highly, demonstrating potential for early irregularity detection and predictive maintenance, aligning with VNF's plans to switch to remote control of

infrastructure assets. Structural inspection of locks using Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) technology showed promise for improving maintenance predictability but requires crucial Key Partners, specifically geotechnical or soil structure experts, to interpret the complex data. A significant barrier for the SIR technology may be the limited capability to provide accurate results for depths higher than 1-1.5m, especially in the case of scanning reinforced concrete structures, and the limited ability, depending largely on users' experience, to identify specific subsurface materials without invasive methods.

- **Italian Pilot:** The Smart Bulletin, a forecasting tool using machine learning and statistical algorithms validated with 20 years of historical data, successfully extended navigation forecasts for the Po River to a 10-day horizon. This increased predictability was estimated to potentially increase the number of navigable days annually by 4.2% (from 240 to 250), improving dredging maintenance scheduling. User satisfaction was high, with 63% of users indicating the 10-day forecast significantly improved planning capacity. Fibre Optic Sensor (FOS) implementation, however, was noted as technically challenging due to cost and complexity.
- **Polish Pilot:** Six Smart Buoys were deployed on the Lower Vistula (covering 70–80% of the segment), achieving a high Technology Readiness Level (TRL8). The buoys provided novel data streams like real-time water level, bridge clearance, and vessel counts, leading to potential net logistics cost savings of 11–18% in door-to-door chains via IWT adoption over road transport. Nevertheless, the validation highlighted that the technology's effectiveness was critically constrained by the waterway's fundamental navigability, evidenced by three unplanned river closures during drought conditions.

5.5.1 Validation

The operational validation of the CRISTAL technologies has provided some valuable insights into their performance across the pilot sites in France, Italy, and Poland. The analysis of practical experiences from the implementation of Acoustic Emission and Subsurface Inspection Radar technologies revealed promising outcomes.

While good practises with improvements in technology adoption and data management were noted, gaps in quantitative data hindered a more comprehensive assessment. While the operators are able to predict some internal future effects on their own operations, their ability to estimate in a qualified way the effects on external impacts like traffic volumes appears to be very limited. For many KPIs, they don't have a base scenario at hand to compare with.

The findings indicate that the technologies have the potential to enhance infrastructure monitoring and maintenance scheduling. Most mentioned impact of better maintenance schedules is, that navigability in days per year might be increased, however in one digit percentage shares levels. This is achieved by a better planning of the infrastructure operators' personnel shifts and thus a better allocation of their tight resources for maintenance and infrastructure surveillance.

However, the lack of a broader operational context and insufficient data availability limits the possibility to predict long-term impacts and efficiencies more precisely.

5.5.2 Reflections on Research

The research conducted through Task 10.3 highlights both the potential benefits and challenges of implementing new technologies in real-world IWW environments. Interviews with infrastructure operators revealed some enthusiasm for the new technologies, though concerns about data collection, regular use at a greater scale, and the uncertainty of ROI were prevalent.

The study underscores the importance of structured data gathering and the need for better-defined base scenario performance indicators to measure the recent and future predicted impact of these technologies. Despite the limitations encountered, the research contributes to a growing body of knowledge on integrating advanced monitoring systems within waterway management.

Recommendations would include to conduct further studies to quantify impacts on vessel capacity, traffic volumes, and cost savings. Likewise, solutions should be explored to the likely FOS implementation challenges to enhance real-time monitoring. Operators should be engaged to refine the CRISTAL technologies' integration into their operational workflows, ensuring alignment long-term goals of modal shift and higher IWW reliability.

5.5.3 Transferability to Future Research

The findings from the operational validation provide a foundation for future research on the broader application of CRISTAL technologies.

Future studies should focus on developing standardised methodologies for data collection and analysis to facilitate cross-comparison among different infrastructure projects. Furthermore, the insights gained from the pilot projects can guide the design of subsequent studies aimed at assessing the scalability of these technologies in diverse operational contexts. Establishing collaborative frameworks with infrastructure operators will enhance the capacity for ongoing evaluation and refinement of the technologies deployed in the CRISTAL project.

Key considerations for future research include:

Scalability Across River Systems: The Smart Bulletin and Smart Buoys demonstrate applicability to free-flowing rivers with low infrastructure, such as the Po and Lower Vistula. Their forecasting and monitoring capabilities could be adapted to other rivers with similar hydrological profiles, such as the Danube or Elbe, provided site-specific customizations (e.g., algorithm calibration for local conditions or buoy design for debris resistance) are implemented. Comparative studies across multiple river systems could validate scalability and identify universal versus context-specific benefits. Acoustic Emission and Subsurface Inspection Radar could be used in many other locations without much need for adaptation.

Integration with Broader Transport Networks: The technologies' potential to enhance intermodal integration, particularly for freight transport, warrants further exploration. Future research should quantify modal share shifts and connectivity with rail and road networks, using data from intermodal hubs and transport models. This could position inland waterways more as a sustainable alternative to other modes, aligning with European Union goals for green transport.

Enhanced Data Collection and Analysis: Future research should use standardised KPIs for traffic, efficiency, and costs as well as automated monitoring systems (such as AIS for vessel tracking and hydrological sensors for weather events) to fill in the current data gaps. The effects of the technologies on navigation and maintenance results could be measured using statistical techniques like regression analysis or time-series models. Robust datasets to evaluate resilience to extreme weather would be provided by long-term research spanning several hydrological seasons.

Economic and Environmental Assessments: Comprehensive cost-benefit analyses, incorporating capital and operational expenditures alongside savings from automation and optimised planning, are critical to evaluate financial viability. Additionally, assessing the technologies' contributions to environmental sustainability (e.g., reduced emissions from optimised navigation or dredging) could align them with regulatory and policy priorities.

Stakeholder Engagement and Regulatory Frameworks: Structured stakeholder surveys and user-centred design approaches can refine the technologies' usability and address operational challenges, such as system integration or durability. Monitoring emerging regulatory frameworks for hydrological technologies will ensure compliance and facilitate broader adoption.

Technological Enhancements: Monitoring capabilities could be improved by investigating complementary technologies like fibre optic sensors or sophisticated buoy designs that are resistant to debris. A comprehensive management ecosystem for inland waterways might be developed by integrating these with current systems, such as navigation software or weather models. The growing need for structural health monitoring could result from enhanced automated interpretation or identification of flaws in the locks concrete walls.

Through the examination of these domains, subsequent investigations can expand upon the core discoveries of the CRISTAL project, promoting the advancement and implementation of advanced technologies to maximise navigation, sustainability, and resilience in inland waterway systems.

6. Sustainability Validation

6.1 Context

CRISTAL’s goals of shifting 20% of freight to inland waterways, increase network reliability by 80% and preserve at least half of its transport capacity under extreme weather events, creates a complex sustainability validation challenge. Task 10.4 addresses this by synthesising evidence from pilot’s assessments and qualitative expert judgments, into a single metric, the Sustainability Index (SI).

Achieving such ambitious targets requires a framework that can bring together both pilot assessments and expert knowledge while accounting for uncertainty. A Bayesian Network provides this framework (Figure 9). At its core, a Bayesian Network is a probabilistic graphical model represented as a directed acyclic graph (DAG), where each node corresponds to a random variable (here, a Key Performance Indicator such as Weather Resilience, Logistics Continuity or Energy Consumption) and each directed edge represents a dependency between them (Drton and Maathuis, 2017; Qazi *et al.*, 2018; Ghuge and Akarte, 2024). For instance, an arrow from Governance Effectiveness to Carbon Emissions indicates that the probability distribution of emissions depends on the governance state. These dependencies are quantified by Conditional Probability Tables (CPTs), which specify the probability of each node’s states given every combination of its parent nodes’ states (Pearl, 1986). Root nodes without parents carry marginal priors, which in our case are based on baseline assessments from the Italy, Poland, and France pilots and supplemented by literature-informed estimates where necessary.

Figure 9: Bayesian Network Framework

A simplified network with variables {A, B, C, D, E, F} has been considered (Figure 10). Nodes A, B, and C have no incoming edges and are associated with priors $P(A)$, $P(B)$, and $P(C)$. Directed edges

define conditional probabilities, $P(D|A)$, $P(E|B,D)$, and $P(F|E,C)$, and the joint distribution factorizes accordingly (Pearl, 1986). When new evidence arrives, Bayesian inference applies Bayes' theorem to update the prior distributions with posterior likelihoods that better reflect reality (Hosseini and Barker, 2016). This process allows computing marginal probabilities, such as $P(F)$, by summing over all other variables, thereby quantifying the likelihood of specific sustainability outcomes irrespective of underlying uncertainties (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Simplified Bayesian Network example

By integrating expert-informed CPTs and transparent graphical representation, CRISTAL's Bayesian Network not only underpins the detailed calculation of the SI but also supports scenario and sensitivity analyses. Stakeholders can trace the pathways by which enhancements in resilience reduce emissions or how shifts in public perception influence modal split. Through this process, this evidence-based methodology ensures that the SI not only measures what has been achieved but also quantifies our confidence in those achievements, guiding informed decision-making as CRISTAL's inland waterway innovations are implemented across Europe.

More details and further materials pertinent to this chapter are stored in:

- Annex 4. Bayesian full questionnaires
- Annex 5. KPI definitions and network structure thresholds
- Annex 6. Full CPTs and Priors

6.2 Sustainability Validation Scope and Methodology

Scope

Task 10.4 focused on assessing how CRISTAL solutions influence the sustainability of inland waterway systems at the three pilot sites in Italy, France, and Poland. However, the purpose of this validation is not to assess separately the impact of solutions such as sensors, platforms or innovative models. Instead, it aimed to examine how these solutions that are implemented together (Figure 11) for achieving the objectives of improving resilience, enhancing operational reliability and increasing modal share, impact the overall sustainability of the inland waterways

systems. By taking a holistic approach, the assessment provides a comprehensive understanding of the combined effect of technological interventions on the efficiency and performance of the IWW systems.

Figure 11: Implemented CRISTAL solutions in each pilot site

The evaluation provides a comprehensive assessment of the sustainability performance of the CRISTAL pilot cases, considering the life cycle of the implemented solutions and emphasising the added value of coordinated technological implementation in supporting long-term, sustainable transport objectives. The analysis covers the three pillars of sustainability, economic, environmental, and social, with the goal of determining how the integrated solutions enhance economic efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and generate societal benefits, thus offering a robust estimation of the CRISTAL project's overall contribution to sustainable inland waterway transport.

To achieve this, task 10.4 develops and applies a Sustainability Validation Tool designed to assess pilot performance across the three sustainability pillars within a unified framework. The tool integrates heterogeneous inputs, combining pilot assessments with structured expert judgment, and processes them through a multi-criteria, uncertainty-aware methodology. Indicators are scaled and normalised, stakeholder weights are elicited through pair-wise comparison methods, and dependencies are encoded in an elicitation-based Bayesian Network. These elements are then aggregated into a True Sustainability Index (TSI), providing a transparent and evidence-based benchmark of the pilots' sustainability outcomes.

Methodology for Sustainability Validation

The assessment of the sustainability performance of the project's pilot implementations is realised through a Bayesian Network (BN) technique that integrates evidence (expert judgments, pilot priors) and operationalises the WP's multi-criteria decision-making plan, stakeholder weighting, and integration across economic, environmental, and social pillars, into a single decision output: the **Sustainability Index (SI)**. The framework distinguishes between **Parent**

KPIs, which represent upstream system attributes, and **Child KPIs**, which reflect the downstream outcomes influenced by those attributes. Parent KPIs capture foundational capabilities, while child KPIs convey the influence on the Sustainability Index that the project seeks to improve. Structuring the model in this way enables a direct measurement of how improvements in core system dimensions impact key performance outcomes.

List of Parent KPIs

The BN uses twelve Parent KPIs that capture upstream system capabilities spanning operational continuity, resilience, governance, material choices, and service performance. In brief, the parent KPIs include: Continuity under disruption; Weather resilience; Logistics continuity (digitalisation and asset monitoring); Use of recycled materials in infrastructure; Level of EU regulatory compliance; Shipment waiting time; Corridor functionality under disruption; Recovery time following incidents; Governance effectiveness; Shipment delay; Accidents; and Public perception of IWT and logistics services. Full names, operational definitions and the three-state discretisation for each Parent KPI are provided in Annex 5. KPI definitions and network structure thresholds.

List of Child KPIs

Outcomes are summarised by five Child KPIs that represent final sustainability performance: operational efficiency, modal shift rate, infrastructure resilience, carbon-equivalent emissions, and energy consumption. The full operational definitions and measurement units are listed in Annex 5. KPI definitions and network structure thresholds.

Network structure

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) within complex systems such as multimodal freight logistics do not operate in isolation. They form a causal network, where changes in one KPI can propagate through the system, affecting others. In the context of sustainability assessment, identifying and understanding these dependencies is crucial to:

- Reveal indirect effects (e.g. improving governance may eventually reduce emissions),
- Avoid unintended trade-offs (e.g. efficiency gains leading to more emissions),
- Enable system-level optimisation rather than siloed improvements.

This causal structure is typically represented as a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG), which maps how parent KPIs influence child KPIs, and how even some child KPIs may act as intermediaries, influencing other child KPIs, as long as no circular dependencies are created. The full DAG (node list and complete edge list) and the machine-readable adjacency matrix are provided in Annex 5. KPI definitions and network structure thresholds while a high-resolution figure of the network is presented in Figure 12 following. The directed relationships between KPIs represent critical causal pathways through which sustainability goals are advanced or hindered. These connections reflect systemic dependencies that must be understood to enable targeted, high-impact interventions. For instance, greater Weather Resilience and Continuity Under Disruption reduce downtime during adverse events, thereby improving Operational Efficiency. Similarly, stronger Infrastructure Resilience ensures more reliable operations, limiting emissions from delays and detours. Social and institutional factors also shape sustainability outcomes. Improved Public Perception can facilitate the acceptance of alternative transport modes, enabling modal shift. Understanding these influence chains allows policymakers to prioritise actions with the greatest systemic leverage. Bayesian modelling supports this process by quantifying dependencies and enabling dynamic policy evaluation under uncertainty.

Bayesian technique

The Bayesian technique used in CRISTAL is an elicitation-based Bayesian Network. The approach transforms structured expert judgment and pilot team knowledge into a coherent, uncertainty-aware model of how upstream capabilities drive downstream sustainability outcomes. The network's causal structure and the five most influential drivers of sustainability were defined through the first expert questionnaire (Questionnaire 1 – Expert survey for causal relations among KPIs). Each KPI is represented as a node with three ordered states, normalised so that higher values consistently indicate more sustainable performance, including for cost-type indicators such as emissions and delays. This discretisation provides comparability across heterogeneous indicators while keeping the model interpretable for stakeholders.

Pilot-specific prior beliefs for root or lightly parented KPIs were elicited through the second questionnaire completed by teams in Italy, Poland, and France, capturing baseline expectations for each pilot context (Questionnaire 2). Conditional dependencies were parameterised via the third questionnaire: for each state of a parent KPI, specialists identified the single most likely state of the corresponding child KPI (Questionnaire 3). These modal selections were then converted into full probability rows using probability smoothing that assigns most of the probability to the chosen state while preserving non-zero support for adjacent states to reflect residual uncertainty in expert judgement. For children influenced by multiple parents, parental effects were combined using canonical, monotone aggregation rules and calibrated to maintain expected relationships; for example, improving operational efficiency should not, all else equal, increase energy consumption.

Inference proceeds by propagating the elicited priors and conditional relationships through the network to obtain model-implied distributions for all KPIs and for the latent Sustainability Index. These results should be interpreted as prior-predictive beliefs consistent with expert knowledge and pilot context rather than as fits to measured outcomes. The same framework supports prospective analysis: stakeholders can impose scenarios such as extreme weather or infrastructure failure and examine how beliefs shift across the network, test the sensitivity of sustainability outcomes to individual drivers, and evaluate policy options such as stronger governance or compliance while tracing their downstream effects on energy use and emissions.

For reporting and decision-making, the network's probabilistic outputs are summarised as a Sustainability Index. This is a transparent aggregation of the five most influential KPIs identified by experts, using their model-implied expectations on the common normalised scale and stakeholder-approved weights. Weights can reflect expert priorities, the model's sensitivity of sustainability to each KPI, or a hybrid of the two, preserving the clarity expected in multi-criteria decision-making while leveraging the causal and uncertainty-aware nature of the Bayesian model. The Sustainability Validation tool implements this process end-to-end, ingesting elicited priors and conditional probability tables along with scenario assumptions, and returning KPI distributions, the latent index, the Sustainability Index with uncertainty ranges, and traceable visualisations of the causal graph and sensitivity diagnostics.

6.3 Bayesian Network Implementation

The methodology was designed and implemented between months 24 and 36 by CERTH. It adopted an elicitation-based Bayesian Network approach that integrates structured expert judgement and pilot knowledge into a coherent, uncertainty-aware framework. The goal was to translate stakeholder beliefs about system capabilities, causal dependencies, and expected

outcomes into a transparent model that produces prior-predictive sustainability results and a reportable Sustainability Index (SI).

Model Structure

The model separates upstream Parent KPIs (system capabilities) from downstream Child KPIs (performance outcomes), as listed above in Sub-section 6.2. Each KPI is an ordinal node with three states; labels are KPI-specific (e.g., High/Moderate/Low or Favourable/Neutral/Unfavourable) and are conceptually normalised so the favourable state always maps to greater sustainability. Full state labels, thresholds and mapping rules are provided in Annex 5. KPI definitions and network structure thresholds.

Elicitation Process

The methodology comprises three successive questionnaires, each targeting a distinct layer of the Bayesian model.

1. **Network structure** (Questionnaire 1): Seven experts identified the KPIs most directly influencing sustainability. The top five in terms of votes, namely: Operational Efficiency, Modal Shift Rate, Infrastructure Resilience, Carbon Emissions Reduction, and Energy Consumption, were designated as SI drivers. Experts also mapped causal relationships by indicating which KPIs directly influence others. For each source KPI, the top three targets were retained as outgoing edges, forming the basis of the directed acyclic graph (Figure 12).
2. **Priors** (Questionnaire 2): Around eleven participants per pilot (Italy, Poland, France) provided probability-based beliefs about KPI thresholds (e.g., 20% modal shift, 50% operational continuity, 80% navigability in extreme weather). Responses were pooled across pilots to produce a single global prior per KPI (e.g. Table 8). Duplicate or overlapping prompts were combined to avoid double counting. Probabilities were then mapped into three discrete states (favourable, neutral, unfavourable) using KPI-specific thresholds. This ensured compatibility with the Bayesian network while preserving the intent of each prompt. Because the questionnaire did not allow respondents to indicate negative impacts, priors were often optimistic (e.g., Operational Efficiency \approx 95% favourable, 5% neutral, 0% unfavourable).
3. **Conditional Probability Tables** (Questionnaire 3): Ten logistics experts specified, for each parent-state, the most likely child-state. These modal responses were expanded into full CPT rows. For children with multiple parents, effects were combined multiplicatively and scaled by the influence weights derived in Questionnaire 1, then normalised into valid probability vectors (see Annex 6. Full CPTs and Priors). This method allows CPTs to assign non-zero probabilities to adverse child outcomes even when parents perform well, thereby reintroducing downside risk omitted from the priors. In other words, even if the parents are believed to perform well, the CPTs encode the experts' view that there remains a credible chance of worsening.

The final **directed acyclic graph** (Figure 12) was pruned and oriented to preserve acyclicity and interpretability and to support valid probabilistic inference, with capability-type parents preceding performance-type children.

Inference and Outputs

All results are prior-predictive. Inference propagates pooled priors from Questionnaire 2 through CPTs from Questionnaire 3 within the fixed structure defined by Questionnaire 1. Outputs are

probability distributions for every KPI and for the latent SI, consistent with expert knowledge and pilot context rather than fitted data.

For reporting, these distributions are summarised as a Sustainability Index aggregating the five expert-selected driver KPIs. Each driver's three-state distribution is converted into a normalised score by taking the expectation across states, with favourable, neutral, and unfavourable mapped to high, intermediate, and low values. Directionality is handled consistently so that low energy use or high emissions reduction contributes positively. The aggregate SI is then formed by applying global weights derived from the first questionnaire's influence votes, normalised to sum to one. This preserves transparency in line with multi-criteria decision-making while leveraging the causal propagation encoded in the network, and it naturally reflects any downside probability injected by the CPTs into the driver KPIs.

Implementation and Reproducibility

The model and inference were implemented in Python using a Bayesian Network library for representation and variable elimination, with standard scientific packages for data handling and graph rendering. Priors, CPTs, and the network structure are stored as structured files suitable for version control, and the full diagram, representative CPT excerpts, and pooled priors are included as annexed artifacts to ensure reproducibility Annex 6. Full CPTs and Priors.

Limitations and Checks

The model reflects expert beliefs distilled through a transparent process but remains sensitive to elicitation design choices (e.g., pooled priors, optimistic bias, no probability smoothing). This limitation is mitigated by explicit documentation of questions, thresholds, and mappings; by enforcing an acyclic structure consistent with the capability-to-outcome direction of influence; and by the planned introduction of basic robustness checks in the analysis stage.

To build confidence in the results before deployment, three lightweight checks requiring no additional data and complementing the risk-aware role of the CPTs, were applied. First, one-at-a-time perturbations of each parent KPI were tested to reveal the most influential levers and show where small deteriorations could disproportionately affect outcomes. Second, weight robustness was examined by varying SI weights within plausible ranges to see whether conclusions or rankings changed, addressing concerns about subjectivity. Third, two scenarios were run, setting Weather Resilience to an adverse state and Governance Effectiveness to an improved state, to confirm that causal pathways aligned with domain expectations. Together with the CPT-based injection of downside probability, these checks provide a balanced picture of expected performance and residual risks.

Taken together, this methodology provides a rigorous and transparent way to synthesise expert and practitioner knowledge into a coherent sustainability assessment for CRISTAL. It documents how beliefs were elicited, how they were encoded in a causal network, how optimistic priors were balanced with risk-aware conditional dependencies, and how results are aggregated into an actionable index, while clearly flagging the assumptions and limitations.

Findings

Identification of Variables and Bayesian Network Structure

Following surveys and workshops, twelve Parent and five Child KPIs were selected for the Bayesian Network. Experts validated variables, dependencies, and the directional flow, ensuring alignment with European IWT objectives. Parent and Child KPIs form the Directed Acyclic Graph

(DAG) depicted in Figure 12 with probabilistic relationships defined in Conditional Probability Tables (CPTs).

Figure 12: CRISTAL's Directed Acyclic Graph

Distributions for the five driver KPIs

The posterior distributions for the five driver KPIs, presented in Table 5 indicate a general inclination toward favourable outcomes, with moderate downside probabilities retained via the CPTs.

Table 5: Posterior Summary for Child KPIs

KPI	Decrease (%)	No Change (%)	Increase (%)	Score (-1...1)	Score (%)	Weight	Contribution
Operational Efficiency	9.0	33.6	57.4	0.483	74.2	0.194	0.094
Modal Shift Rate	1.9	48.1	49.9	0.480	74.0	0.226	0.108
Infrastructure Resilience	0	37.5	62.5	0.625	81.3	0.161	0.101
Carbon Emissions Reduction	2.7	43.0	54.3	0.516	75.8	0.194	0.100
Energy Consumption	3.7	37.6	58.7	0.550	77.5	0.226	0.124

The Sustainability Index (SI) was computed by aggregating the posterior distributions of the five driver KPIs using stakeholder-approved weights. Contributions are relatively balanced, with Energy Consumption (0.124) and Modal Shift Rate (0.108) providing the largest influence due to

both favourable posterior outcomes and high weights (0.226 each). Infrastructure Resilience (0.101) and Carbon Emissions Reduction (0.100) provide meaningful support, while Operational Efficiency (0.094) reinforces the overall sustainability profile. The SI reflects a composite score of 0.76, indicating above-average performance.

Key Outcome

A composite sustainability score of **0.76** on a normalised 0–1 scale is generally regarded as **above average** and indicative of relatively **strong sustainability performance**. For instance, the JRC report's map paints countries scoring in the green band (high sustainability) at the top of the scale, implying values well above 0.7 (Dobranskyte-Niskota, 2009).

Causal insights from the CPTs

Although priors were generally optimistic, the CPTs capture potential downside risks. For instance, a configuration for Carbon Emissions with elevated Energy Consumption assigns $\approx 27\%$ probability to deterioration, $\approx 46\%$ to neutral, and $\approx 28\%$ to improvement. This illustrates how local weaknesses, such as increased energy use, can propagate to environmental outcomes even when most KPIs are strong. The network preserves expected pathways: resilience and continuity support efficiency, which in turn reduces energy use and emissions, while modal shift to IWT directly lowers energy and emissions.

Risk and sensitivity outlook.

The KPI risk–influence diagram (see Figure 13) indicates overall system robustness. Continuity Under Disruption is the only borderline case, with risk ≈ 0.22 and influence ≈ 0.32 , warranting monitoring. Weather Resilience shows very high influence (≈ 0.70) but negligible risk, highlighting strong leverage potential. Logistics Continuity (0.35) and Operational Efficiency (0.32) exhibit modest risk (≈ 0.12) yet remain within safe bounds.

KPI outcomes further support this stability: Operational Efficiency is favourable in 57.4% of scenarios, Modal Shift Rate increases in 49.9%, Infrastructure Resilience is high in 62.5%, Carbon Emissions reduction is achieved in 54.3%, and Energy Consumption decreases in 58.7%. Carbon Emissions, Energy, and Modal Shift Rate remain in the low-risk, moderate-influence quadrant, confirming safe leverage opportunities.

Together, these insights suggest that the system is largely resilient, with most KPIs likely to remain favourable. Targeted attention to Continuity Under Disruption and sustained efforts on resilience and efficiency ensure robust sustainability performance while minimising the risk of adverse outcomes.

Sensitivity Analysis

The sensitivity analysis explored how small shifts in key performance indicators (KPIs) affect the **Sustainability Index (SI)**. The graph presented in Figure 14 reveals that one-at-a-time perturbations of ± 5 –10 percentage points revealed a nearly linear response: a 5% deterioration in any KPI typically lowers the SI by about 0.02, while a 5% improvement raises it by about 0.01. Doubling the perturbation produced proportional effects (-0.03 to $+0.02$), confirming stability. Among the five drivers, Energy Consumption and Operational Efficiency proved marginally more sensitive, suggesting that gains in efficiency and reductions in consumption are particularly impactful for system performance.

Figure 13: Risk and sensitivity

Figure 14: Sustainability gradient vs perturbation

At a system level, the model remains stable under small input variations, with no single KPI dominating outcomes. This implies that risks are distributed and that sustainability performance is best supported by balanced progress across operational, modal, resilience, and environmental

dimensions. Still, targeted attention to energy-related levers offers the greatest potential for amplifying gains.

Figure 15: Sensitivity analysis of the driving KPIs

Diving into detail, operational Efficiency, largely driven by Shipment Delay and Waiting Time and reinforced by continuity factors (see Figure 15), faces substantial systemic risk: worst-case CE scores reach -0.95 , with even mild scenarios at -0.58 , collectively representing over 27% probability. Modal Shift Rate is mainly influenced by Weather Resilience (0.75) and Public Perception (0.72), showing a 49.9% probability of medium/high increase, with worst-case scores down to -0.83 . Infrastructure Resilience depends entirely on Weather Resilience, with 62.5% probability of high resilience. Carbon Emissions are most affected by Energy Consumption (0.54), Modal Shift Rate (0.46), and Shipment Waiting Time (0.34), yielding a baseline reduction in 54.3% of cases (score 0.516). Energy Consumption is dominated by Operational Efficiency (0.77), showing a 58.7% probability of decrease. The graph highlights how KPI interactions and feedback shape performance, emphasising the levers critical to sustaining the Sustainability Index.

6.4 Summary

Task 10.4 of the CRISTAL project, focused on assessing the sustainability performance of the pilot cases implemented at inland waterway (IWW) sites in Italy, France, and Poland. The main objective was to evaluate the combined impact of CRISTAL solutions on the three pillars of sustainability: economic, environmental, and social. Specifically, the task sought to synthesise pre- and post-pilot operation data into a single, interpretable metric, the Sustainability Index (SI), which could quantify the overall contribution of CRISTAL interventions to the sustainability of inland waterway transport systems.

Methodological Approach

To achieve this objective, Task 10.4 developed a Sustainability Validation Tool, implemented using an elicitation-based Bayesian Network (BN) framework. The BN serves as a probabilistic graphical model where nodes correspond to KPIs and directed edges capture causal relationships. Parent

KPIs represent upstream system capabilities, while Child KPIs capture downstream performance outcomes. Conditional Probability Tables (CPTs) quantify how child KPIs respond to changes in their parent KPIs, allowing the propagation of uncertainty.

The elicitation process involved three questionnaires administered to experts and pilot teams:

1. **Network Structure Identification:** Experts selected the most influential KPIs and identified the causal dependencies among them, resulting in a DAG linking upstream capabilities to sustainability outcomes.
2. **Prior Probability Elicitation:** Pilot's teams provided beliefs regarding KPI performance.
3. **Conditional Probability Table Specification:** Experts indicated the most likely outcomes for child KPIs given parent states. Responses were converted into full probability distributions, preserving non-zero probabilities for adverse outcomes to maintain realistic downside risk.

The BN framework integrates these inputs into a multi-criteria decision-making process, scaling and normalising indicators and applying stakeholder-derived weights to produce the final Sustainability Index. The SI aggregates the five most influential KPIs, into a single composite metric.

Implementation

The Bayesian Network was implemented in Python, using standard libraries for network representation, variable elimination, and data handling. Priors, CPTs, and network structure were stored as structured files to ensure reproducibility. The resulting model enables computation of KPI distributions, the latent SI, and uncertainty ranges, as well as visualisation of causal pathways and sensitivity diagnostics. Three lightweight model checks were applied: one-at-a-time KPI perturbations, robustness of SI weights, and scenario tests (e.g., adverse weather or improved governance), confirming system behaviour aligned with expert expectations.

Findings: Sustainability Index and KPI Outcomes

The Sustainability Index, computed by aggregating weighted expectations across the five drivers, resulted in a normalised score of 0.76, indicating above-average sustainability performance.

Posterior summaries for the five driver KPIs show a tilt toward favourable outcomes. Energy Consumption and Modal Shift Rate emerged as particularly influential due to a combination of favourable outcomes and high stakeholder-assigned weights.

- **Operational Efficiency:** 57.4% favourable outcomes, contributing 0.094 to the SI.
- **Modal Shift Rate:** 49.9% favourable outcomes, contribution 0.108.
- **Infrastructure Resilience:** 62.5% high resilience, contribution 0.101.
- **Carbon Emissions Reduction:** 54.3% improvement, contribution 0.100.
- **Energy Consumption:** 58.7% reduction, contribution 0.124.

Overall, SI reflects a balanced contribution across operational, environmental, and social dimensions, confirming the effectiveness of CRISTAL solutions in improving inland waterway sustainability.

Sensitivity Analysis and Recommendations

Sensitivity analysis examined how small perturbations in key driver KPIs affect the SI. One-at-a-time ± 5 –10% changes showed nearly linear responses: a 5% deterioration in any KPI typically lowers the SI by ~ 0.02 , while a 5% improvement raises it by ~ 0.01 . This confirms system stability

and indicates that sustainability outcomes are robust to modest variations in individual KPIs. Among the drivers, Energy Consumption and Operational Efficiency are slightly more sensitive, suggesting targeted improvements in efficiency and energy reduction can yield the largest positive impact.

Detailed sensitivity insights include:

- **Operational Efficiency:** Highly sensitive to Shipment Delay and Waiting Time; worst-case cumulative scores reach -0.95 .
- **Modal Shift Rate:** Influenced mainly by Weather Resilience (0.75) and Public Perception (0.72); probability of medium/high increase 49.9%.
- **Infrastructure Resilience:** Fully dependent on Weather Resilience; high resilience probability 62.5%.
- **Carbon Emissions Reduction:** Driven by Energy Consumption (0.54), Modal Shift Rate (0.46), and Shipment Waiting Time (0.34); reduction achieved in 54.3% of scenarios.
- **Energy Consumption:** Dominated by Operational Efficiency (0.77); decrease probability 58.7%.

The sensitivity analysis highlights critical levers: improving Energy Consumption and Operational Efficiency, alongside strengthening Weather Resilience and Public Perception, offers the greatest potential to enhance CRISTAL's sustainability outcomes.

Key takeaways

Key takeaways for CRISTAL include:

1. **Balanced Progress Across KPIs:** The SI benefits from coordinated improvements across operational, environmental, and social dimensions; no single KPI dominates outcomes.
2. **Leverage Opportunities:** Enhancements in Energy Efficiency and Operational Efficiency provide the most immediate returns in sustainability.
3. **System Robustness:** The network is resilient under small perturbations, suggesting interventions can be incrementally optimised without risk of systemic failure.
4. **Policy and Operational Guidance:** Focused measures on Continuity Under Disruption, Weather Resilience, and Public Perception can further stabilise and improve SI outcomes, providing actionable guidance for future scaling of CRISTAL solutions.

6.5 Conclusions

Validation

Task 10.4 produced a coherent, uncertainty-aware validation of CRISTAL's sustainability performance across the Italy, France and Poland pilot sites. To translate heterogeneous evidence into a single decision-ready quantity, we developed a Sustainability Validation Tool based on an elicitation-driven Bayesian Network (BN). The BN explicitly represents causal relationships among twelve upstream capability KPIs and five downstream driver KPIs. Experts supplied the network structure and Conditional Probability Tables (CPTs), while pilot teams contributed prior beliefs; indicators were scaled, normalised and combined with stakeholder-derived weights in a multi-criteria decision-making framework to produce the Sustainability Index (SI).

Aggregating weighted expectations across the five drivers produced an SI of **0.76** on a 0–1 scale, indicating above-average sustainability performance for the bundled CRISTAL interventions.

Posterior summaries show a predominance of favourable outcomes: Operational Efficiency favourable in 57.4% of runs (contribution 0.094), Modal Shift Rate favourable in 49.9% (contribution 0.108), Infrastructure Resilience high in 62.5% (contribution 0.101), Carbon Emissions Reduction improved in 54.3% (contribution 0.100), and Energy Consumption decreased in 58.7% (contribution 0.124). Energy Consumption and Modal Shift Rate are particularly influential due to both positive posteriors and comparatively large stakeholder weights, underscoring their system-level importance. Detailed diagnostics further show that Operational Efficiency is especially sensitive to shipment delays and waiting times, Modal Shift depends strongly on Weather Resilience and Public Perception, and Infrastructure Resilience is tightly coupled to Weather Resilience. Carbon emissions respond most to changes in energy use, modal shift, and waiting times.

Taken together, these results deliver two clear messages. First, CRISTAL produced a balanced, above-average sustainability outcome as captured by the SI. Second, targeted operational and policy actions offer the most effective pathways to raise the SI further.

Reflections on Research

Task 10.4 highlights both the opportunities and challenges of applying Bayesian Networks to sustainability validation in multimodal freight logistics. On the positive side, the BN framework successfully integrated heterogeneous evidence streams into a single coherent structure, providing not only a composite index but also insight into the causal pathways linking upstream capabilities to downstream outcomes. The transparency of the DAG representation enhanced stakeholder trust and interpretability, while the elicitation process ensured that local expertise was systematically incorporated.

At the same time, the research revealed practical limitations. Structured elicitation proved resource-intensive, requiring multiple rounds of expert input and careful design to avoid bias. The optimistic nature of priors, a by-product of questionnaire framing, underscores the difficulty of capturing downside risks without observational counterbalance. Moreover, pooling priors across pilots provided simplicity but sacrificed granularity that could have highlighted contextual differences.

Conceptually, the BN approach proved particularly strong in distinguishing between performance expectations and risk profiles, two dimensions often conflated in traditional evaluation. By explicitly encoding uncertainty, Task 10.4 moves beyond deterministic reporting toward a probabilistic, risk-aware assessment that is better aligned with real-world decision-making.

Transferability to Future Research

The methodology developed in Task 10.4 provides a transferable framework for sustainability assessment in transport and logistics that extends beyond the scope of CRISTAL. At its core, the approach relies on a Bayesian Network (BN) structure that can be adapted to diverse project contexts. By redefining the set of key performance indicators (KPIs), updating prior distributions, and tailoring conditional probability tables (CPTs), the model can be recalibrated to reflect different system characteristics.

Several features enhance the transferability of this methodology. First, the modular design allows the reconfiguration of Parent and Child KPIs while preserving the causal framework, thereby enabling adaptation to projects with distinct sustainability objectives. Second, the BN supports scenario analysis, providing the capacity to test the implications of policy interventions, external stressors, and system trade-offs, an asset for both strategic planning and risk management. Third,

the scalability of the elicitation process ensures that the framework can be implemented with varying levels of stakeholder engagement, ranging from small pilot projects to multi-country assessments. Finally, the model aligns closely with European Union policy priorities, particularly those related to modal shift, emissions reduction, and system resilience, ensuring direct applicability to Horizon Europe research agendas and national decarbonisation strategies.

Future research can build on this foundation in three main directions. First, incorporating real-time sensor and pilot data into the BN updating process would enhance the empirical robustness of model predictions. Second, refining the weighting schemes through multi-criteria decision analysis and participatory stakeholder processes would strengthen transparency and legitimacy. Third, applying the framework to cross-project benchmarking would enable systematic comparisons across European sustainability initiatives, supporting evidence-based policy learning.

Taken together, these extensions point to a methodological pathway that is both generalisable and policy-relevant. Task 10.4 has thus established not only a tool for project-specific sustainability assessment but also a broader blueprint for advancing risk-sensitive, evidence-informed decision-making in the European transport and logistics domain.

7. General Framework for Validation of Inland Waterway Interventions

7.1 Context

Task 10.5, led by the Newcastle University (UNEW) with support from Fraunhofer, represented the culmination of the validation efforts conducted across Work Package 10 (WP10). The primary objective of this task was to synthesise the methodological insights and approaches derived from Tasks 10.1 through 10.4. By integrating these findings, the task aimed to develop a common approach that extends beyond the specific CRISTAL pilots and innovations, thereby delivering a General Framework for Validation of IWW Interventions. This framework serves as a foundational methodology, acting as a guide for future Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) research and innovation projects.

The mandate for this framework arose directly from the comprehensive validation structure of CRISTAL, which was designed to provide resilience validation, technology evaluation, confirmation of business models, pilot performance versus Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and sustainability impact assessment.

The necessity for a general framework was underpinned by the complexity observed during the validation of the CRISTAL innovations, which were categorised into physical sensor technologies (Acoustic Emission (AE), Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR), Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS), and Smart Buoys (SB)) and digital integration systems (Digital Twins (DTs) and the Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS)). The framework is designed to capture the lessons learned regarding four core validation aspects:

1. **Technology Evaluation:** Determining performance criteria and readiness levels.
2. **Business Model Viability:** Assessing the ability of models (defined via Business Model Canvases, BMCs) to sustainably identify, deliver, and capture value.
3. **Operational Performance:** Defining a common operational framework of KPIs to assess deployment quality and identify barriers.
4. **Sustainability Impact:** Assessing performance against economic, environmental, and social pillars.

Ultimately, the General Framework must provide a blueprint that enables future IWW innovation projects to systematically structure their validation process, ensuring they align technical capability with commercial viability, social acceptance, and EU policy goals.

7.2 Literature Review

The existing literature on Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) highlights that, while IWT is recognised as a sustainable mode of transport, offering advantages in reducing emissions and congestion, its development is fundamentally constrained by physical infrastructure and institutional maturity. The need to transition the sector to modern intermodal chains requires first addressing the **boundary condition** of ensuring appropriate waterway parameters. Subsequently, it requires the implementation of **ICT systems** like River Information Service (RIS) to standardise and streamline data transmission between stakeholders (administration, port managers, shipowners).

The selected sources provide extensive published literature concerning Inland Waterway Transport (IWT), primarily through two systematic literature reviews (SLRs) and one academic paper focusing on RIS implementation in Poland.

Overview of IWT Published Literature

Academic interest in the modernisation and technological innovation of IWT has grown due to the necessity of achieving a sustainable transport system. IWT is widely acknowledged as a sustainable, efficient, and strong alternative to road and rail transport modes. This mode of transport is characterised by its substantial transport capacity, low energy use, and reduced environmental impact compared to alternatives.

Key Themes and Research Focus Areas

Academic research on IWT tends to concentrate on **three main categories** of development and challenges:

1. **Modernisation and Greening the Fleet:** This domain focuses on improving technical and economic performance, including new vessel designs, energy efficiency, the use of alternative fuels (such as CNG, GTL, Biofuel, methanol, ethanol, and hydrogen), and reducing emissions and carbon footprints.
2. **Information and Communication Technology (ICT):** Research addresses digitalisation, automation, and the implementation of ICT systems to enhance safety and efficiency. A significant focus is the River Information Service (RIS) system.
3. **Infrastructure and Operational Challenges:** This covers issues related to infrastructure quality, bottlenecks, maintenance, and climate change resilience.

Two systematic literature reviews provide structural context to the IWT field:

1. Gbako et al. (2024) - Systematic Literature Review of Technological Developments and Challenges (Gbako *et al.*, 2025):

- **Scope:** This review analysed 94 articles published between 2010 and 2022.
- **Growing Interest:** Research interest in IWT issues, challenges, and technological innovations is increasing.
- **Geographical Focus:** A significant proportion of studies were conducted in Europe (63 papers), followed by China (23 papers), and the United States (11 papers). This geographic distribution is attributed to the prosperity of maritime trade connected with inland shipping in these regions and strategic investment support.
- **Fragmentation:** Despite growing interest, the literature is generally considered fragmented.
- **Technological Gaps:** Major areas of ongoing concern include incorporating artificial intelligence into decision-making, adopting blockchain technology, developing new technologies for fleet adaptation to climate change, and improving maintenance and rehabilitation technologies.

2. Calderón-Rivera et al. (2024) – Review on Sustainable Development of Inland Waterways Transport: (Calderón-Rivera, Bartusevičienė and Ballini, 2024)

- **Scope:** This review analysed 51 papers focusing specifically on sustainable development of IWT systems.
- **Definition of Sustainable IWT:** While few papers propose a specific definition, the concept generally promotes better environmental practices and considers socio-economic aspects. One definition states that sustainable IWT is where freight increase meets lower environmental and economic costs, while being resilient to climate change and promoting social equity.
- **IWT as a System:** The IWT system is defined by three fundamental, inter-related physical elements: waterways, inland fleet (vessels), and ports (inland river ports and seaports).

- **Challenges:** The necessity to conduct a comprehensive analysis specific to each basin is imperative due to the distinct geographical, social, economic, and political conditions inherent to each waterway. The global focus shows a geographic bias towards Europe and Asia, limiting the generalisability of findings.

Specific Focus on RIS Implementation in Poland

One paper in particular details the application of the **River Information Service (RIS) system** (Niedzielski, Durajczyk and Drop, 2021).

- **Role of IWT:** IWT should be included in the modern intermodal transport chain to contribute to reducing harmful emissions.
- **Development Stages:** Activities in this area should proceed in two stages:
 1. Meeting the boundary condition by ensuring appropriate parameters of the waterway (e.g., transit depth, bridge clearance).
 2. Implementing ICT systems (such as RIS) to standardise and streamline data transmission among stakeholders (administration, port managers, shipowners, etc.).
- **RIS Function:** RIS is a comprehensive transport management system planned for full implementation by the European Commission by 2030. It provides a service package aimed at optimising traffic and transport flows, improving safety, and supporting environmental protection.
- **Challenges in Poland:** Inland shipping is largely neglected in Poland, mainly due to the poor condition of the waterway infrastructure. Despite its advantages (low unit cost, low environmental impact), issues like low bridges preventing two-layer container transport and the lack of sufficient transit depth for navigation limit the capacity for containerised cargo. The quantitative benefits of RIS implementation could not be checked in practice due to the current condition of Polish waterways.

Key Findings from Literature Reviews

The implementation of RIS systems is widely discussed for improving transport efficiency and safety, and the European Commission plans its full implementation by 2030. However, the successful uptake of these digital systems is not solely a technical problem. Research has shown that comprehensive analysis specific to each basin is imperative due to the distinct geographical, social, economic, and political conditions inherent to each individual waterway. For instance, Polish efforts to activate inland navigation are dependent on government strategies to gradually improve navigation conditions, including upgrading the Odra Waterway to at least Class IV. The complexity of factors like low bridges, insufficient transit depth for container transport, and institutional fragmentation necessitates that any validation methodology must be sensitive to local contextualisation.

This reinforces the strategic role of the General Framework (Task 10.5): to provide a standardised yet adaptable methodology capable of integrating empirical operational data with qualitative insights regarding the institutional and commercial environments.

7.3 Reflections on Validation

The validation activities conducted in Tasks 10.1 to 10.4 revealed several fundamental methodological challenges and critical insights that necessitate the generalised framework produced by Task 10.5.

Limitations of Short-Term Trials (Tasks 10.1 and 10.3): Operational validation demonstrated that field trials were typically restricted, isolated, and short-term (spanning only days or weeks). This constraint severely hampered the ability to measure external Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as traffic volumes, or to reliably extrapolate long-term effects. This highlighted a critical gap: operators often lacked a defined base scenario against which to compare the new technology's impact. Furthermore, the study underscored that the *effectiveness* of testing a technology such as the Smart Buoys (TRL8) was critically constrained by the waterway's fundamental **navigability**, especially during drought conditions.

Challenges in Quantification and Commercial Viability (Task 10.2): Validation of the Business Model Canvases (BMCs) confirmed the inherent difficulty in quantifying costs and revenues during the early design phase. Stakeholders in France and Italy consistently provided low scores for the "Finance" block of the SCMS BMC and requested "proper numbers". The preliminary Social Cost-Benefit Analysis (SCBA) for the SCMS showed that net benefits were highly sensitive to initial assumptions regarding cargo volumes and the baseline unreliability of the existing transport system. This emphasised that business model validation must move beyond theoretical perceived value to achieve quantitative realised value.

The Primacy of Context and Governance (Task 10.4 & Living Labs): The experience across the pilots proved that the success of technological adoption is inextricably linked to the local institutional and physical context.

- The Italian pilot found that effective technological adoption (like the Smart Bulletin) requires organisational alignment, leading to the co-creation of the "Manifesto for Sustainable Development of the Padano-Veneto IWW". This showed that a strong sense of shared mission and sound organisational structures can outperform pure digitalisation efforts.
- The Polish pilot clearly illustrated that the validation of the business model viability of Smart Buoys was severely limited if the fundamental conditions for navigation were not met.
- The French pilot found that bureaucratic barriers due to the size of the organisation remained a hindrance, even though VNF was willing to adopt digital technologies.

Integration of Uncertainty (Task 10.4): The development of the Sustainability Validation Tool using a Bayesian Network (BN) successfully synthesised heterogeneous inputs (expert judgment and empirical priors) into a probabilistic Sustainability Index (SI). This innovative approach moved validation beyond deterministic reporting toward a risk-aware assessment, which is essential when addressing climate resilience and complex system changes.

Generalisation of Validation Framework

The General Framework for Validation of IWW Interventions (Task 10.5) is designed as an integrated and adaptable methodology based on the systematic process and specific tools developed within CRISTAL. It mandates four essential phases for any future IWW intervention assessment:

1. Contextualisation and Governance Foundation: The framework adopts the **Living Lab (LL) Methodology** (Phase 1: Contextualisation and Phase 2: Engagement). This is essential for aligning the validation with the specific **geographical, social, economic, and political conditions** of the basin. The LL approach ensures that the governance and business models are co-created with stakeholders (gate actors), addressing upfront the institutional maturity and organisational alignment required for success, as demonstrated by the Italian pilot's Manifesto. This process must explicitly identify the core stakeholders/actors and address institutional complexity.

2. Business Model Rationalisation and Quantification: The **Business Model Canvas (BMC)** methodology, as adapted for the IWT sector, remains the central tool for testing the rationale of how an organisation "creates, delivers, and captures value" (Phase 3: Design). The framework emphasises addressing the early-stage quantitative gap identified in CRISTAL by requiring:

- **Early Quantification:** Prioritising the collection and forecasting of **costs and revenue streams** (ROI) early in the design process to move to Phase 4 (Implementation).
- **Value Differentiation:** Explicitly evaluating the difference between the **perceived value** (speculative anticipation) and the **realisable value** (empirical observation) of the innovation.
- **Stakeholder Specificity:** Analysing how the BMC blocks (e.g., Key Partners, Customer Segments) vary depending on whether the technology is a physical sensor or a digital platform (DT/SCMS).

3. Standardised Operational Performance Assessment (KPIs): The framework mandates the establishment of a **common operational framework of KPIs** with predefined **baseline scenarios** prior to technology deployment. This is critical to overcome the limitations of short-term trials. The framework covers technologies aimed at **maintenance planning** (AE, SIR) and those enabling **enhanced information to users** (FOS, SB). It seeks to quantify operational performance metrics such as efficiency gains and maintenance predictability.

4. Risk-Sensitive Sustainability and Impact Assessment: The framework incorporates the **Sustainability Validation Tool** based on the elicitation-based **Bayesian Network (BN)** methodology (Task 10.4). This tool provides the robust, uncertainty-aware mechanism required to evaluate long-term impacts:

- **Integration of Inputs:** The BN allows the synthesis of **heterogeneous inputs** - empirical data (priors) and structured expert judgment (Conditional Probability Tables (CPTs)) - into a coherent probabilistic model.
- **Output Metric:** The final outcome is the normalised **Sustainability Index (SI)**, which provides a transparent and evidence-based benchmark against the three pillars of sustainability (economic, environmental, social). This method facilitates evidence-informed policy learning by providing both performance expectations and risk profiles.

7.4 Transferability to Future Research

The framework established by Task 10.5 provides a transferable blueprint for the future direction of IWW research and innovation. The core mixed-methods validation framework, combining the BMC, Living Labs, quantitative input, and the BN, offers a robust and replicable template for validating innovations across the wider transport and logistics sectors. Specific findings that should inform future research include:

- **Digital Integration:** Future research on digital platforms (DTs and SCMS) should focus not on them as standalone products, but on their integration strategies and the governance models needed to enable cooperation among traditionally siloed transport sectors, transforming the synchro-modal promise into commercial reality.
- **Longitudinal Studies:** The validated business models developed in Task 10.2 provide a crucial baseline against which future performance can be measured. This sets the stage for longitudinal studies (Phase 5: Manage) to track how business models evolve as technologies mature, markets change, and stakeholder relationships adapt.

- **Sustainability Assessment:** The BN structure is highly adaptable and can be applied to diverse contexts by redefining KPIs and causal paths, supporting risk-sensitive and evidence-informed policy learning across Europe.

Complementarity and Comparison with BoostLog⁶: The General Framework directly complements and provides methodological depth to key research gaps identified by the **BOOSTLOG** project (Bas van Bree *et al.*, 2023).

- **Sustainability Measurement and Reporting:** The CRISTAL BN framework offers a practical solution for operationalising several *BoostLog* recommendations. It provides a robust methodology for the implementation of sustainability measurement schemes and specifically for the aligned measurement of carbon emissions of digitalised logistics. The BN methodology's ability to integrate heterogeneous data and expert judgment provides a foundational, risk-aware tool for establishing comparability and accountability, which aligns with *BoostLog*'s goal to define high potential R&I gaps.
- **Digitalisation and Automation:** CRISTAL's deep dive into the business models and operational performance of platforms (SCMS) and technologies feeding them (Smart Buys, AE) directly informs *BoostLog*'s key recommendations on implications and adjustments based on the increasing automation of logistics operations and real-time and decentralised data sharing along supply chains across different domains. The CRISTAL findings highlight the specific governance structures and financial quantification needed to make these digital concepts market-viable.
- **Network Resilience:** CRISTAL's focus on measuring Continuity Under Disruption and Infrastructure Resilience in Task 10.4 lays the groundwork for addressing *BoostLog*'s area of logistics network design for resilience. The CRISTAL framework ensures that future R&I in resilience is assessed against operational, commercial, and sustainability metrics in a unified manner.

7.5 Conclusion

Task 10.5 has achieved its objective by synthesising the validation methods and findings from Tasks 10.1 through 10.4 into a formalised **General Framework for Validation of IWW Interventions**. This document provides a blueprint for advancing future IWW research and innovation beyond the CRISTAL project. The framework integrates the requirements for systematic assessment across technical, operational, commercial, and impact domains.

The core components of this generalised validation framework mandate:

- A rigorous **technical evaluation** of innovative solutions involving new technologies, through a **well-designed testing plan**, to validate their technical feasibility, which is a pre-requisite for further implementation and market uptake.
- The use of the **Living Lab (LL) methodology** to ensure validation is anchored in local geographical and institutional contexts.
- **Iterative Business Model Canvas (BMC) refinement** (Phase 3 and 4), prioritising the move toward quantitative estimation of costs and benefits to validate commercial viability.

⁶ The BOOSTLOG project: Boosting the impact of freight transport and logistics EU funded research – ALICE Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe. <https://www.etp-logistics.eu/boostlog/>

- The establishment of a **standardised framework of operational KPIs** coupled with the definition of clear baseline scenarios to overcome the measurement limitations of short-term pilots.
- The application of the **Bayesian Network (BN)** methodology to integrate diverse data sources and expert judgment, resulting in the risk-sensitive Sustainability Index (SI).

This generalised framework is designed to ensure that future IWW interventions are not only technologically feasible but also commercially viable, institutionally supported, and aligned with European sustainability goals, complementing broader R&I agendas such as those defined in the *BoostLog* project.

The General Framework delivered by Task 10.5 represents an opportunity for advancing systematic, evidence-informed decision-making within the European transport and logistics sector. By codifying the lessons learned across the CRISTAL pilots, this framework formalises a transferable methodology that successfully addresses the challenge of assessing complex, multi-stakeholder IWW innovations.

The framework critically reinforces two key findings: first, the absolute necessity of contextual and governance alignment for technological success, demonstrating that organisational factors often precede purely technical capabilities; and second, the need to systematically integrate uncertainty and risk into performance evaluation using robust probabilistic tools like the Bayesian Network.

By providing a clear structure for quantification and impact assessment, the framework helps future research and policy decision-makers prioritise strategically on high-impact areas, such as enhancing resilience and ensuring IWT infrastructure capacity meets operational needs. This robust, generalised approach ensures that research and innovation investments are leveraged to maximise system-wide performance and support the institutionalisation of IWT as a resilient and sustainable transport mode in Europe.

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Annexes

Annex 1. Technical Requirements and Testing Plans

Annex 1.1 Technical Requirements and Testing Plan for AE

Technical Requirements for AE

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
Functional Requirements (FR)					
AE-FR-01	The system shall detect acoustic emissions related to structural anomalies.	Sensitivity to detect mechanical elastic waves in the metal.	Detect emissions > 20 dB against background noise at <1ms latency.	Fully	• Passed
AE-FR-02	The system shall localise the source of emissions on the gate surface.	Within a radius of 0.5m for prediction of microcracks and other causes of failure on gates parts and 2.5 m direct impact from a foreign object	Localisation microcrack error prediction <0.5m. Localisation impact detection error <2.5m.	Fully	• Passed
AE-FR-03	The system shall log and timestamp acoustic events for post-analysis.	Data storage compatible with cloud services.	Log 99.9% of events in real-time.	None	• Passed • Tested in Lab
AE-FR-04	Scalability on the number of pzt sensors across the water-lock gate	Adding multi-channel AE loggers or many from the used 4 channel logger.	Sensor scalability	Partially	• Passed
AE-FR-05	Detecting metal microcracks before major metal crack failures and detecting upcoming out of the normal operation failures.	Detecting metal microcracks before major metal crack failures and detecting upcoming out of the normal operation failures (by positioning sensors close to gate parts under inspection various kind of failures can be detected, e.g. near pistons or at the bottom of the gate buildup of canal precipitations)	Types of gates failures	Partially	• Passed
AE-FR-06	The inspection system shall provide the end-user with the	The system provides streaming with confidence levels (assessments) on detected	N/A	Partially	• Passed

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
	necessary assessment data for making appropriate decision in response to upcoming failures in the gate	microcracks and/or out of normal operation patterns, the raising frequency or raising amplitude of which in comparison to past AE recordings is an assessment indication which triggers the heuristic experience of the end-user deciding on a possible nearby predictive maintenance cycle.			
Non-Functional Requirements (NFR)					
Operability Requirements (NFR-OP)					
AE-NFR-OP-01	The system shall be portable and easily installable and dismantlable.	Installation time < 60 minutes.	Deployment within 60 minutes.	Fully	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed
AE-NFR-OP-02	The AE system ought to be flexible enough to accommodate various use cases linked to various kinds of water lock gates.	There are several types of gates the system must be adaptable to be placed in various types of gates	Adaptability to water lock's gates	Partially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed • Fully tested on more lock gates than expected
AE-NFR-OP-03	Minimum disruption of water lock's operation	Minimum disruption to overall water lock gates allowing during inspection the passage of ships	Minimum water lock's operational disruption	Fully	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed
AE-NFR-OP-04	In site raw inspection data process producing the confidence levels of upcoming failures within a reasonable amount of time.	Portable libraries processing current data in the same laptop as the one of the AE logger and comparison with past inspections (historical data)	Max 3 hours for results	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed
AE-NFR-OP-05	Transporting results in the Data Management wirelessly and instantly.	Transmitting produced data to the Data Management	Fast Data transmission	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
AE-NFR-OP-06	AE Recording Adjustment, onsite operators can customise the location of the sensors in reasonable time.	In a periodic scale sensors can be placed in various locations across various critical points in the gate mainly in inspecting gate's various parts possible good normal operation deviation.	Customised prediction attention mechanism	Partially	• Passed
AE-NFR-OP-07	Emergency Quit. In the event of an emergency, pressing a single button will be sufficient to completely stop the system.	In an emergency, pressing a single button will be sufficient to stop the AE logger and stop the recordings.	Instant full stop	Fully	• Passed
AE-NFR-OP-08	Ensuring sensors' good acoustic conductance.	On site auto testing of sensors' good acoustic conductance with the metal gate.	Auto testing sensors' good acoustic conductance at the inspection point	Fully	• Passed
AE-NFR-OP-09	The system shall operate continuously for a minimum of 6 hours. (no recharge)	Power backup or extended battery support.	6+ hours of operation without recharge.	Fully	• Passed
Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety Requirements (NFR-RAMS)					
AE-NFR-RAMS-01	Immunity to climate change. Regardless of the weather and other environmental factors, the inspection system must be able to function in the lock environment.	All equipment must perform at full nominal capacity under environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, rain, snow, and sun exposure. If components are shielded, the shielding must be sufficient to ensure the system operates effectively despite environmental challenges.	The system should operate normally during recording within its specified operational limits and not be affected by adverse climate conditions (e.g., logger unit under water operation).	Partially	• Passed
AE-NFR-RAMS-02	The inspection system must have a minimum IP65 Ingress Protection level to operate effectively in a locked environment.	The system must comply with IP65 requirements (as per EN 60529:1992+A2:2013) to withstand frequent exposure to solid particles and water in a lock environment.	For prototype: No noticeable ingress of foreign fluids/particles For commercial: IP65	Partially	• Passed
AE-NFR-RAMS-03	The inspection system's mean time between failures should	A minimum allowable term of operation, which excludes the interval between	{Mean Time Between Failures} > 1000 hours of operation for	Partially	• Passed

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
	be as short as feasible while still allowing infrastructure scanning within the access period.	inspections, should be exceeded by the inspection system's mean time between operating failures.	failures that can be corrected within 1 hour		
AE-NFR-RAMS-04	Sensors and cables of AE system, must be readily maintained and customisable as part of the inspection system.	Preventive and corrective maintenance, including the installation and setup of new components, should be simple and rapid in order to minimise any disturbance in the case of failure.	Time to perform preventative and corrective maintenance: < 1 hour/1000 hours of operation	Partially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed
AE-NFR-RAMS-05	The operation of the inspection system must not provide an unacceptable risk to the general public, employees, property, or environment.	The operation of the inspection system cannot completely eliminate all dangers to the environment, property, employees, and the general public. However, by taking the right precautions when installing the sensors and turning on the AE logger, such hazards should be reduced. Any danger resides during the installation of the sensors not during operation.		Partially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed
Security Requirements (NFR-SEC)					
AE-NFR-SEC-01	Secure transmission channel	Secure transmission channel for sending data towards the database	Secure Data Transmission	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed • Tested in Lab
AE-NFR-SEC-02	Authorised user access	Preventing unauthorised access (or modification at source) of commercially exploitable/sensitive data, and unauthorised access, or submission of malicious code, to the database and systems connected to it.	Data Transmission authorisation	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed • Tested in Lab
Compatibility Requirements (NFR-COMP)					

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
AE-NFR-COMP-01	Compatible with DT	The AE output must be compatible with the DT, i.e. must confirm to the agreed formats so that the output can be stored by the database, and accessed and displayed by the DT	Verify the prototype outputs that the database stores and that DT displays.	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed • Checked after on-site tests in pilot
AE-NFR-COMP-02	Interpretability for resulting data intuitively by non AE experts.	In order for end users (gate engineers) with little to no system knowledge to examine the output data and determine the criticality of the anomalies the system has detected in a fair length of time, the data and HMI should be provided in a way that is reasonably accessible.	End user (gate engineers) can identify all significant anomalies detected in the scan results.	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed • Checked after on-site tests in pilot
AE-NFR-COMP-03	It will be feasible to use the main power supplies in Europe to provide the electricity required to run or charge the system.	The system must be able to be powered by European main power supplies, either directly from the mains (or a generator/isolated power supply with mains equivalent output) or through proprietary transformers or converters.	Verify that the system can be powered by the main power source.	Fully	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passed

Testing plan for AE

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
On-site testing					
AE-OS-01	Sensitivity of acoustic detection	Measured sensitivity to detect signals > 20 dB.	Signal strength (dB)	AE-FR-01	Passed, great sensitivity
AE-OS-02	Sensor scalability	Ability to deploy many AE logger at the same time and ability of the system to parse parallel such recordings.	Number of loggers and sensors per logger deployed	AE-FR-04	Passed, virtually the number is infinite depends on the capacity

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
					of the WiFi and the power of the hosting laptop
AE-OS-03	Kind of failure defects	Detecting metal microcracks before major metal crack failures and detecting upcoming out of the normal operation failures (by positioning sensors close to gate parts under inspection various kind of failures can be detected, e.x. near pistons or at the bottom of the gate buildup of canal precipitations)	Sensors applicability to various sources of defects	AE-FR-05	Passed, on site various simulated failures where applied and fully detected.
AE-OS-04	The system shall be portable and easily installable and dismantlable.	Installation time < 60 minutes.	Measuring time of installation	AE-NFR-OP-01	Passed, the fact that a single operator visited different locks and deployed the AE alone is a proof of portability.
AE-OS-05	The AE system ought to be flexible enough to accommodate various use cases linked to various kinds of water lock gates.	There are several types of gates the system must be adaptable to be placed in various types of gates	Generality of system installability and models trainability	AE-NFR-OP-02	Passed, as long the gate is metallic for proper transmission of the AE, the system has no problem.
AE-OS-06	Minimum disruption of lock's operational	Minimum disruption to overall lock gates allowing during inspection the passage of ships	Testing gate's smooth operability during AE recording.	AE-NFR-OP-03	Passed, during the on site visits many boats were passing along with the operation of the system.
AE-OS-07	In site raw inspection data process producing the confidence levels of upcoming failures within a reasonable amount of time.	Portable libraries processing current data in the same laptop as the one of the AE logger and comparison with past inspections (historical data)	Ability of the libraries to run on a laptop or common PC.	AE-NFR-OP-04	Passed, the time of producing results measured in real processing

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
AE-OS-08	Transporting results in the Data Management wirelessly and instantly.	Transmitting produced data to the Data Management	Connecting and transmitting data to the Data Management through onsite laptop.	AE-NFR-OP-05	Passed, the time of producing results measured in real processing
AE-OS-09	AE Recording Adjustment. onsite operators can customise the location of the sensors in reasonable time.	In a periodic scale, sensors can be placed in various locations across various critical points in the gate mainly in inspecting gate's various parts possible good normal operation deviation.	Ability to seamlessly move the sensors and the logger to various position across and along the lock gate	AE-NFR-OP-06	Passed, during sensor installation the time was measured and found to be very short
AE-OS-10	Emergency Quit. In the event of an emergency, pressing a single button will be sufficient to completely stop the system.	In an emergency, pressing a single button will be sufficient to stop the AE logger and stop the recordings.	Availability of stop button to stop the AE recording system	AE-NFR-OP-07	Passed, close the emergency button of the power supply.
AE-OS-11	Ensuring sensors' good acoustic conductance.	On site auto testing of sensors' good acoustic conductance with the metal gate.	Testing on site an auto sensor testing system measuring good acoustic conductance	AE-NFR-OP-08	Passed, the build-in auto sensor testing AST was used
AE-OS-12	The system shall operate continuously for a minimum of 6 hours.	Power backup or extended battery support.	Measuring the time of system's continuous operation	AE-NFR-OP-09	Passed, all on site visits / measurements where more than 6 hours.
AE-OS-13	Immunity to climate change. Regardless of the weather and other environmental	All equipment must perform at full nominal capacity under environmental conditions such as temperature, humidity, rain, snow,	Proper casing, available cable for harsh environment	AE-NFR-RAMS-01	Passed, by design the casing from the manufacturer is immune to the climate change.

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
	factors, the inspection system must be able to function in the lock environment.	and sun exposure. If components are shielded, the shielding must be sufficient to ensure the system operates effectively despite environmental challenges.	and sensors datasheet compliance		
AE-OS-14	The inspection system must have a minimum IP65 Ingress Protection level to operate effectively in a locked environment.	Checking with the manufacturer that indeed it is a IP65 design or a suitable casing enhancing on ward the IP65 is feasible	Manufacturer compliance or IP65 casing	AE-NFR-RAMS-02	Passed, in some cases during on site measurements it was raining, and the system was operating.
AE-OS-15	Sensors and cables of AE system, must be readily maintained and customisable as part of the inspection system.	Preventive and corrective maintenance, including the installation and setup of new components, should be simple and rapid in order to minimise any disturbance in the case of failure.	The way for preventive maintenance over sensors and cables; evaluating the time for the maintenance.	AE-NFR-RAMS-04	Passed, in lab testing of changing the cables and distinguish degradation.
AE-OS-16	The operation of the inspection system must not provide an unacceptable risk to the general public, employees, property, or environment.	The operation of the inspection system cannot completely eliminate all dangers to the environment, property, employees, and the general public. However, by taking the right precautions when installing the sensors and turning on the AE logger, such hazards should be reduced. Any danger resides during the installation of the sensors not during operation.	Reporting the possible points of danger during installation and operation and evaluating the level of danger.	AE-NFR-RAMS-05	Passed, the local waterlock gates used the system and found to be safe
AE-OS-17	It will be feasible to use the main power supplies in Europe to provide the electricity required to run or charge the system.	The system must be able to be powered by European main power supplies, either directly from the mains (or a generator/isolated power supply with	Connecting to lock power supply and verify normal AE logger operation	AE-NFR-COMP-03	Passed, on site used close by power inlet and powerbank

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
		mains equivalent output) or through proprietary transformers or converters.			
Functional					
AE-OS-18	System logging and timestamping	Real-time logging under operational conditions.	Percentage of events logged (%)	AE-FR-03	Passed, the AEwin has a fine build in such system
AE-OS-19	Localisation accuracy	Accuracy of pinpointing emission source.	Error radius (m)	AE-FR-02	Passed, in the lab localising defect with PLBs between sensors
AE-OS-20	Output failure assessment report	Providing constant assessments from streaming input AE recordings.	Numericability of the output	AE-FR-06	Passed, the output of the algo is percentage number which by test on proper AE proved to change upon failure signals.
AE-OS-21	The inspection system's mean time between failures should be as short as feasible while still allowing infrastructure scanning within the access period.	A minimum allowable term of operation, which excludes the interval between inspections, should be exceeded by the inspection system's mean time between operating failures.	Reporting possible failures in time length of operation without failure	AE-NFR-RAMS-03	Passed
AE-OS-22	Authorised user access	Secure transmission channel for sending data towards the database	Evaluating the used protocol of communication with the data management server	AE-NFR-SEC-02	Passed, in lab testing data stream with SSL
AE-OS-23	Secure transmission channel	Preventing unauthorised access (or modification at source) of commercially exploitable/sensitive data, and unauthorised access, or submission of	Evaluating the used protocol of wireless transmission	AE-NFR-SEC-01	Passed, in lab testing utilising DMS access with password

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
		malicious code, to the database and systems connected to it.			
Post-pilot tests					
AE-PS-01	Compatibility with DT	The AE output must be compatible with the DT, i.e. must confirm to the agreed formats so that the output can be stored by the database, and accessed and displayed by the DT	Designing properly the developed software and testing it.	AE-NFR-COMP-01	Passed, simple data transfers to the DMS and testing the quality of the received data
AE-PS-02	Interpretability for resulting data intuitively by non AE experts.	In order for end users (gate engineers) with little to no system knowledge to examine the output data and determine the criticality of the anomalies the system has detected in a fair length of time, the data and HMI should be provided in a way that is reasonably accessible.	Programming the software in producing an explainable confidence level of failure	AE-NFR-COMP-02	Passed, the algo by itself provides an intuitive image representation of deviation percentage, will consulting people outside the team to interpret them.

Annex 1.2 Technical Requirements and Testing Plan for SIR

Technical Requirements for SIR

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
Functional Requirements (FR)					
SIR-FR-01	The inspection system shall provide the end-user (IM) with the necessary data for making appropriate decision in response to potential risks associated with inspection results.	The data saved by the system shall be suitable, in terms of format, content and accuracy, so that the end-user could easily assess the characteristics of any features identified and, therefore, make their own assessment of the hazards and risks associated with the health of the structure, based on the inspection results. The data shall be complete in terms of the size, estimated material category, and location (in the physical infrastructure) of the detected features.	N/A	Partially Through tests SIR-PS-02 primarily, also PS-03 to PS-07	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System produces images and media which can be interpreted by the end-user to assess the condition of the structure • No independent assessment of structure condition or defects to compare system outputs to
SIR-FR-02a	The returned processed data from a scan shall have sufficient resolution to enable the majority of significant defect to be identified.	The resolution of subsurface features recovered from 3D Visualisation should be sufficient to allow the end-user to readily distinguish healthy from unhealthy wall substructure.	The system shall detect features/ abnormalities with dimensions of at least 100mm in both axis perpendicular to the direction of the radar emission. OR discriminate between features of different materials, with the same dimensions.	Partially Through test SIR-PS-02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System outputs and lab tests indicate features/ abnormalities with dimensions of at least 100mm detected, and lab tests show indicated size of detections representative of size of features. • No independent assessment of size of features in IWW structure scanned.

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
SIR-FR-02b	Features, within the required resolution limits, will be reliably detected and identified in the returned processed data.	Features, within the required resolution limits specified in requirement SIR-FR-02a, will be detected and identified in the returned processed data with a sufficient degree of reliability for the end-user to have sufficient confidence in the results as an indicator of the health of the structure.	80% of features within the required resolution limits shall be detected	Partially Through test SIR-PS-02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System outputs and lab tests indicate features/ abnormalities within resolution limits detected, and lab tests show all qualifying features detected representative of size of features. • No independent assessment of number of qualifying features in IWW structure scanned.
SIR-FR-03	The system should be able to discriminate between, and classify features in terms of their material composition.	The features in the returned processed data should be classified according to their material composition. The system should be able to discriminate between features mostly composed of, metal, air-filled voids, and water-filled voids, and assign the appropriate material classification label to the feature data.	The assignment of material type label should be correct for 80% of features.	Partially Through test SIR-PS-04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material classification limited to expert interpretation of the outputs, system does not classify the material. • Lack of independent material classification of materials for comparison, and limited number of scans to gather sufficient data for calibration and training automated material classification models.
SIR-FR-04	The accuracy of the positional data component of the scan	The accuracy of the component of the scanning data associated with the position at which the radar return values were	Accuracy of position given by scan data - /+50mm within a	Fully Through tests SIR-OS-20, SIR-PS-05	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The precision of the location of the features given by the outputs and

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
	data shall be sufficient to enable any features identified in the scans to be located on the physical structure.	recorded, and therefore the location of any features identified from those scan results, shall be sufficient for the location of the feature to be identified on the physical structure. The context for the accuracy being that of identifying localised areas on large structures.	quadrant, and ± 1 m in relation to the reference point for the whole structure		<p>scanning process is sufficient to locate the features on the IWW structure within ± 1 m.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The precision of the outputs is sufficient to find the corresponding location on the IWW structure, however no independent assessment of accuracy of location of detected features, although visual signs of one defect (water seeping from IWW structure) did correspond with position of detected features.
SIR-FR-05	The size characteristics determined by the system for the features detected and identified shall be accurate	The 3D representation of the detected features in the returned processed data shall be sufficiently accurate for the data to be considered a reasonable estimation for the size characteristics of the feature	Accuracy of volume of features $\pm 50\%$	Partially Through tests SIR-PS-02 and SIR-PS-06	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accuracy validated just through lab tests by comparing size of features detected with technology vs physical objects of known size. For on site results, no independent assessment of size of features in IWW structure scanned.
SIR-FR-06	The radar scanning process shall enable	Radar imaging should penetrate behind the contact surface to a sufficient depth range as	1-3m	Partially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System outputs show features detected at

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
	features to be detected, at the required accuracy and resolution, at a sufficient depth below the surface of the structure to detect the most common types of significant defects	to resolve structural features of interest within/behind lock walls.		Through tests SIR-PS-02 and SIR-PS-07	<p>more than 1m behind contact surface.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> No independent assessment of depth of features in IWW structure scanned. Due to compromise of depth and resolution selected, 1m close to maximum depth of detection for lock walls
Non-Functional Requirements (NFR)					
Operability Requirements (NFR-OP)					
SIR-NFR-OP-01	The inspection system shall be operationally efficient, i.e., it should be able to inspect a lock chamber within an appropriate timeframe, during a scheduled maintenance.	The system shall be capable to carry out a full inspection of a lock chamber (including processing of results) in a specified period of time, so that it won't require the extension of actual scheduled maintenance timeframe. Considering that the actual timeframe for scheduled maintenance of locks is, on average, 10 days, it is envisaged that the system should be able to complete the inspection in up to 8 days.	Max. inspection time: 8 days	Partially Through test SIR-OS-07	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Based on average time per 1m² scanned with the experimental rig, the inspection times was estimated for locks of different sizes. The KPI cannot be achieved with the prototype rig in the case of medium and large size locks. Prototype system is more suited to scanning localised sections where problems suspected or as samples. Mechanical system of experimental setup and scanning

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
					procedure can be improved significantly to increase scanning speed without reducing scan quality.
SIR-NFR-OP-02	The inspection system should be adaptable to work for different use cases associated to different types of locks and dams.	The system should be designed so that it could be used for inspecting any part of a lock chamber (sidewalls, bottom, earthwork, etc.), of any type of lock (narrow- and wide-gauge), as well as the dam structures. E.g., a modular design is recommended.	N/A	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The experimental rig was specifically designed for inspection of vertical lock walls, as this was the priority use case. However, the design may be changed to allow for being used on different use cases, such as dams.
SIR-NFR-OP-03	The inspection system should be transportable in a LGV and the components manually movable	For reasons of practicality and cost, it should be possible to transport the disassembled system to site in a Light Goods Vehicle (LGV/van), and each of the disassembled components should be within the manual handling capability of 2 persons	Check/assess Y/N	Fully Through test SIR-OS-09	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not tested, however, all components could be loaded into a larger LGV. For tests larger system components delivered in HGV due to being most efficient long distance international shipping option.
SIR-NFR-OP-04	It should be possible to setup and dismantle the system within a reasonable timeframe	It should be possible to setup the inspection system from transported state, to be ready to commence first scan within a reasonable length of time, it shall also be possible to dismantle the system for transport within a reasonable amount of time.	Less than 4 hours	Fully Through tests SIR-OS-01 and SIR-OS-02	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> System initial setup and commissioning to approximately 1, 8-hour work shift. Reconnecting electronics each day took less than 1 hour.

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First use of experimental system, expected to improve with further refinement and operator familiarity.
SIR-NFR-OP-05	Raw inspection data transfer. It shall be possible to transfer the data from the SIR scanning system to the SIR processing system within a reasonable amount of time.		24 hours	Fully Through test SIR-PS-09	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All raw test inspection data transferred within at most a few hours over broadband internet. Expect dataset for a full lock, to be transferable within 24 hours depending on connection speed. • Full dataset for lock not generated, and outcome dependent on many computer and communication systems not related to SIR.
SIR-NFR-OP-07	Scan Parameter Adjustment. It should be possible for on site operators to customise scan settings in reasonable time.	It should be possible for on site operators to customise scan settings in reasonable time with a reasonable level of intuitiveness and engage scan with single button push	N/A	Partially Through test SIR-OS-19	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjustment of main scan parameters not tested. • Insufficient resources to experiment with different scan parameters or implement methods to alter them (e.g. increased scanning speed), especially with delayed

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
					feedback from processing scans.
SIR-NFR-OP-08	Emergency Stop. It shall be possible to fully halt the apparatus in the event of emergency with a single button push.	It shall be possible to halt the scanner positioning apparatus (stopping movement of the apparatus) and interrupt the scanning (stop radar emissions) in the event of emergency with a single button push.	Full stop within 1 second.	Fully Through different tests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This essential feature (required for safety purposes) was integrated in the prototype, tested and it worked as expected.
SIR-NFR-OP-09	It should be possible onsite to track progress of the inspection (across quadrant and across full lock) 'at a glance' from the system interface	This feature should be enabled by the radar controller and its operating software, or by interface of additional control system for operating the radar on the rig (if any).	N/A	Partially Through tests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The progress of inspection on specific quadrants was approximately tracked and monitored through the existing radar interface. Further improvement of this feature was not needed for project's experimental work.
SIR-NFR-OP-10	The internal power supply of the apparatus shall be sufficient to power it for a typical work shift, and be rechargeable overnight.	The aspects of the apparatus running off internal power supplies should have sufficient power stored at the start of a work period to power that aspect of the apparatus for a typical work shift, and it shall be possible to recharge that power supply to be ready for the next day's inspection.	t>8 hour running (full working day), t<5 hours recharging	Fully Through test SIR-OS-12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Components running on internal power had sufficient power for 8-hour work shift, and it was possible to recharge them before the next days shift (less than 16 hours.)
SIR-NFR-OP-11	Data Processing and 3D Visualisation Turn-Around Timeframe	It should be possible to process and 3D visualise recovered quadrant data on a	1-4 Weeks	Partially Through test SIR-OS-09	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from test scans was processed on commercial

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
		commercial PC in a reasonable timeframe following data acquisition.			PC. Processing time not measured. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Processing of test scan data involved development and refinement of the processing process, therefore detail timings for established process not available.
SIR-NFR-OP-12	Scanning operations should need as small as possible area of, and around the structure being scanned dedicated to the scanning procedure at any one time.	It should be possible to conduct other works, with minimal disruption, in other areas of the structure being scanned (e.g. lock chamber), whilst any particular area of the structure is being scanned.	N/A	Partially Through test SIR-OS-09	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lock used in test scan remained available for use by waterway traffic, only requiring suspension of scanning and lifting out SIR rig for vessels to pass. Work on other parts of the lock could continue during scanning. Scanning lowest areas of lock wall next to bottom of lock would require the lock to be fully drained (closed to traffic).
Reliability, Availability, Maintainability and Safety (RAMS) Requirements (NFR-RAMS)					
SIR-NFR-RAMS-01	Climate immunity. The inspection system shall be able to operate in the lock environment,	All pieces of equipment should be able to operate with full nominal performance in relation to environmental conditions, with regard to the level of protection from the	SIR shall operate normally during inspection and not be affected by climate	Partially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operated under some relevant conditions (e.g., rain, humidity, and low temperatures). Not

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
	regardless the weather and other environmental conditions.	environment afforded by their installation location, including: 1. Temperature 2. Humidity 3. Rain 4. Snow 5. Exposure to sun Some components and/or subsystems may be protected from the environment; in this case the protection should be suitable for resisting the environmental effects so the system can continue to function in those conditions.	(within operational limits (e.g. not operated in heavy rain, etc.))		tested under conditions such as exposure to sun, high temperature, etc. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The experimental prototype was not subject to controlled environmental testing, as this was beyond the project's scope.
SIR-NFR-RAMS-02	The inspection system shall have an appropriate Ingress Protection level (min IP65), so that it could operate in lock environment	Frequent exposure to solid particles and, especially, to water is expected in lock environment, therefore, the system shall be designed to comply with IP65 requirements, as specified in EN 60529:1992+A2:2013	For prototype: No noticeable ingress of foreign fluids/particles For commercial: IP65	Partially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The prototype was fabricated using components rated IP65 or higher. Also, the system was operated in relevant conditions (inc. heavy rain). Standard testing was not carried out, as this was beyond the project's scope.
SIR-NFR-RAMS-03	The Mean time between failure (MTBF) of the inspection system should be as low as possible, and consistent with enabling	The MTBF for the inspection system should be greater than a minimum acceptable period of operation (defined as not including time between inspections). Acceptable failure rate varies between the seriousness of the failure (how easy it is to recover from	For the prototype, MTBF > 12 hours of operation for failures that can be corrected within 1 hour, and MTBF > 64 hours	Partially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The overall operating time was about 20hrs over 3 days. Just 2 minor failures that have been fixed in less than 1 hr

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
	scanning of infrastructure within the access period.	it) and between the prototype and a commercial system. Note: Failure in this context is a deviation from the normal level of performance or ability to operate and detect defects. If does not relate to the reliability with which the system will detect defects when functioning normally.	operation between failures that can be corrected within 24 hours. For commercial system MTBF > 100 hours and 300 hours for the same failure levels, respectively.		each have occurred in this period, which is in line with the requirement.
SIR-NFR-RAMS-04	Maintainability: The inspection system components shall be easily maintainable and configurable	To minimise LCC and disruption in event of failure, preventive, and corrective maintenance, including installation and configuration of replacement components, should be quick and easy.	Prototype: Time to perform preventative and corrective maintenance: < 1 hour/24 hours of operation, and < 24/100 hours of operation	Partially	
SIR-NFR-RAMS-05	The overall health and safety risk to staff, public, property and the environment from the operation of the inspection system shall be at an acceptable level.	It is not possible to entirely eliminate all risks to staff, public, property and the environment, from the operation of the inspection system. However, such risks should be minimised through system design and operating/maintenance procedures to an acceptable level.	N/A	Partially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No detectable harm was caused to staff, public, property and the environment, from the operation of the inspection system • Reasonable precautions were taken for the tests, however, risks of full deployment on commercial scale not fully assessed.
Compatibility Requirements (NFR-COMP)					

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
SIR-NFR-COMP-01	Compatible with DT	The SIR output must be compatible with the DT, i.e. must confirm to the agreed formats so that the output can be stored by the database, and accessed and displayed by the DT	Check/confirm prototype outputs stored by database, and displayed by DT	Fully	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SIR-related data (both raw and processed data) are compatible for being transferred and stored on the DT and/or Data Broker. Also, the format of media files allows for their display on the DT interface.
SIR-NFR-COMP-02	Dates and Timestamps on SIR internal and output data must be accurate	The SIR system, or operating procedures (e.g., auto or manual check/set of system time respectively), should ensure that the dates and timestamps on the internal and output data are accurate, to ensure that inspection data can be placed with an accurate chronology for the structure	Check/confirm that the timestamps on the system output data correspond to the date and time the scans were carried out	Fully	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Date and time stamps in collected raw data is a standard feature of the equipment and its software. These have been checked and were always accurate.
SIR-NFR-COMP-03	SIR Output Media Interoperability and Navigability to Non-Radar Experts. Interoperability and navigability of returned SIR output data media should be sufficiently accessible to non-radar expert end-users.	End-users (infrastructure expert that are not experts in radar-based scanning) with minimal experience and familiarity with the system should be able to navigate the output data to identify and assess the criticality of the anomalies detected by the system in a reasonable amount of time, therefore the presentation of the data and HMI should be fairly intuitive. The performance of the system in this respect is more linked to navigation of the data than the assessment of the results, which might take longer on a case-by-case basis.	End-user (infrastructure expert) can identify all significant anomalies detected in the scan results, within a total period of 5 minutes, plus 2 minutes per anomaly.	Partially	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SIR output media has been presented to representatives of end-user group (IWW engineers), and was considered useful and understandable for indicating condition of IWW infrastructure. Accessing and navigating through processed data is fairly easy offline (i.e., when data available on end-user computer).

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Navigation of SIR output in HMI/DT pending full implementation of end-user access to data.
SIR-NFR-COMP-04	It shall be possible to supply the power needed to operate of charge the system from European main power supplies.	It shall be possible to supply the power needed to operate of charge the system from European main power supplies. This should be either directly from the mains (or generator/isolated power supply with mains equivalent output) or via proprietary transformers or converters.	Check/Confirm that system can be run from mains power supply(s)	Fully	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SIR system powered from regular mains electricity supply for scans, and battery powered components used charged from same.
SIR-NFR-COMP-05	The radar-based system shall comply with radar frequency regulations	The SIR System shall comply with radar frequency regulation ETSI TR 102 554 V1.1.1 (2006-11)	Compliance check Y/N	Fully	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The SIR system used standard radar equipment, which is homologated and compliant with standard requirements.

Testing plan for SIR

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
On-site testing					
SIR-OS-01	Measurement of time to deploy	Time from arrival on site to starting first scan	Time to deploy	SIR-NFR-OP-04	210 Minutes first deployment (including transport of mounted rig to lock, safety training, etc.); (excludes assembly of rig frame, which required ~4 hours). 60 minutes start of further testing days.

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SIR-OS-02	Measurement of time to pack up	Time from finishing last scan to packing up to leave	Time to pack up	SIR-NFR-OP-04	Approximately 3 hours, including transport of rig to workshop, disassembly and packing of mechanical structure and electronic subsystems. However, these were not packed as for further transport purposes, as the planning of next activities was not agreed on.
SIR-OS-03	Measurement of time to scan row/column	Time for scanning of each row/column from initiation to completion (excluding time to set up or moving the equipment)	Time to scan row/column	SIR-NFR-OP-01	Times not measured with high accuracy, due to prioritisation of other measurements. Based on average of times measured, it was estimated as: ~2:25 mins for horizontal scans/transects; ~3:06 mins for vertical scans/transects (higher due to use of manual controller combined with electronic one).
SIR-OS-04	Measurement of operational time to scan row/column	Time between the same point in scanning processes of two consecutive rows/columns.	Operational time to scan row/column	SIR-NFR-OP-01	Times not measured with high accuracy, due to prioritisation of other measurements. Based on average of times measured, it was estimated as: 2:50 mins for horizontal scans/transects; 3:40 mins for vertical scans/transects (higher due to use of manual controller combined with electronic one (including time for repeated scans due to software errors)),
SIR-OS-05	Measurement of time to scan quadrant	Time for quadrant scan from initiation to completion (excluding time to set up or moving the equipment)	Time to scan quadrant	SIR-NFR-OP-01	Times not measured with high accuracy, due to prioritisation of other measurements. Based on quadrants scanned continuously (no experimental stops, errors, etc.): 150-170 mins.

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
					Time was lower for later scans, indicating improvement with familiarity.
SIR-OS-06	Measurement of operational time to scan quadrant	Time between the same point in scanning processes of two consecutive quadrants.	Operational time to scan quadrant	SIR-NFR-OP-01	Times not measured with high accuracy, due to prioritisation of other measurements. Based on quadrants scanned subsequently: 175-205 mins. However, scanned quadrants non-consecutive in location, so required more time to reposition crane that wouldn't be required for every change between Qs.
SIR-OS-07	Measurement of average time to scan m ²	Average time to scan 1m ² for multiple quadrants - excluding deployment and pack up time.	Average time to scan m ²	SIR-NFR-OP-01	Considering context explained above (SIR-OS-05, 06, and 08): For wall scanning: between 44 – 51 mins (including relocation of rig) For ground scanning: ~3:02 mins (average value)
SIR-OS-08	Measurement of time to change quadrant	Time between completion of a scan and initiation of the next one.	Time to change quadrant	SIR-NFR-OP-01	Times not measured effectively, due to other experimental activities required in this timeframe. Based on quadrants scanned subsequently (with minor stops between them): between 25-35 mins. This time was higher when the crane had to be repositioned so that to operate the rig safely to the following locations.
SIR-OS-09	Assessment of transportability	Measure the minimum transport requirements for the equipment	Total volume, greatest/ limiting dimensions	SIR-NFR-OP-03	The requirements have been checked in advance (dimensions, volume, and weight); however, a random appropriate vehicle was contracted instead, due to logistics reasons (availability and price)

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SIR-OS-10	Check Safety - Emergency Stop	Perform emergency stop of scanning mechanism and radar emissions.	Safety - Emergency Stop	SIR-NFR-OP-08	Checked in commissioning tests (with rig not positioned over the lock wall). Not advisable during radar operation.
SIR-OS-11	Assessment of scan progress tracking	Check ability of user to track progress of scan.	Scan progress tracking	SIR-NFR-OP-09	The scan progress was tracked and monitored through the radar software interface. This method can only provide approximate results.
SIR-OS-12	Assessment of endurance	Check if battery powered elements of scanning system have sufficient power to 8 hour shift of continuous scanning (including moving between scans), and can be fully recharged overnight between shifts	Batteries endurance (maximum powering time)	SIR-NFR-OP-10	Endurance of battery powered components was sufficient for scanning process carried out in experimental conditions.
SIR-OS-13	Measurement of technology deployment footprint	Measure areas occupied by scanning equipment and team during scan	Area of footprint required (sqm/m ²)	SIR-NFR-OP-12	The footprint was measured in different phases: mounting of rig in workshop: ~40 sqm rig on the lock shore, measuring equipment and staff deployed: ~30 sqm rig positioned on the wall, measuring equipment and staff deployed: ~16 sqm
SIR-OS-14	Assessment of power compatibility	Check equipment can be powered or charged from mains/generator supply in test location	Powering compatibility (power, frequency, types of connectors, etc.)	SIR-NFR-COMP-04	SIR system powered from regular mains electricity supply for scans at test location.
SIR-OS-15	Assessment of reliability	Record, total operating time, and any failures/unavailability, and their duration.	Reliability metrics (time to failure, etc.)	SIR-NFR-RAMS-03	SIR rig operated approx. 24 hours. 41 instances of failing to record valid measurement and repeat/restart, 5 reboot of radar software, 1 cable failure, 1 rig frame distortion from handling.

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SIR-OS-16	Assessment of maintainability	Record any repair (reconfigure, recalibrate, reboot as well as mechanical repair/reconnection), actions taken, time taken.	Maintainability metrics (time to repair, etc.)	SIR-NFR-RAMS-04	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 reboot of radar software, approx. 2mins each. • 1 cable failure, 20 mins. • 1 distortion of rig frame rendering rig inoperable not repaired (near end of scanning schedule)
SIR-OS-17	Assessment of climate immunity	Record weather conditions throughout tests. Record any observations regarding water ingress, operational difficulties (touch screen operation and visibility, etc.)	Climate immunity	SIR-NFR-RAMS-01 SIR-NFR-RAMS-02	SIR system was able to collect data in outdoor conditions (specifically damp European winter weather) without being significantly affected by the environment or ingress of water. However, no specific testing of limits or specific exposure levels was carried out.
SIR-OS-18	Assessment of Scan Parameter Adjustment	Adjust scan parameters and carry out at least partial scans with different parameters. Tests have two purposes: A: Provide data for validating against req. SIR-NFR-OP-07 (that parameters can be varied) B: Experimental purposes to determine optimum/best compromise (detail vs. time) of parameters. Resolution/effectiveness of scan/imaging outputs assessed and used in validation of req. SIR-FR-01 to 03, and SIR-FR-04 to 06.	Scan Parameter Adjustment	SIR-NFR-OP-07	Not tested on site. However, the variation of scanning parameters was tested in advance, in experimental conditions, and the effects have been reported in other deliverable reports (D2.2 and D8.3).
Functional					

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SIR-OS-19	Visual inspection of lock and manual measurement of features	Features should be scanned by default, known, or surface penetrating features should be priorities for scanning. Features/defects should be measured for reference, surface area, max surface depth, depth of "probe" (qualitative assessment of probe resistance to insertion), any others?	Characteristics of identified features of interest (e.g., cracks, voids, material deterioration, etc.).	SIR-FR-02a SIR-FR-02b SIR-FR-03 SIR-FR-04 SIR-FR-05	No independent assessment of features in IWW structure scanned. Some features have been observed on the wall surface (e.g., cracks with water draining from them, lack of material), which did correspond with feature detected subsurface in the region of those locations. However, no independent assessment of features in IWW structure were available for comparison, and the investigation of characteristics of observed features was, practically, unfeasible.
SIR-OS-20	Locate on infrastructure the location data corresponds to	Select a data point for both a feature/defect and nominal data point/scan location (e.g. scan point 27 in Q4). Record where those data points were collected from. Measure ground truth of locations and compare with location/coordinates according to data.	Local and GPS coordinates for reference location and for scanned quadrants.	SIR-FR-04	Just selecting a nominal point in the data, extracting the corresponding coordinate/location data and locating that point on the structure does not demonstrate accuracy as there is no indication of if the location arrived at on the infrastructure is the one where the data was recorded (if it has no distinctive features). Use of local coordinates was tested and used, and it is the most reliable solution for referencing the inspection results. Use of GPS coordinates was partially tested, however, it proved to be unpractical due to difficulty in creating reference point that could be correlated in both SIR data and independent measurement method.
Post-pilot tests					

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SIR-PS-01	Time to process data and produce imaging	Keep some data unprocessed to measure processing time on after establishing the methodology and process when processing initial data sets.	Time (to process data)	SIR-NFR-OP-11	On average ~1.5 hrs for each specific volume corresponding to a quadrant or area. The time was improved once the data handler got familiarised with the process. Also, it depends on how the scanning was operated.
SIR-PS-02	Effectiveness of scanning and imaging. End-user feedback.	Assessment of if/extent to which processed data provides the end-user with useful and accurate information to assess condition of infrastructure	N/A (qualitative only)	SIR-FR-01 SIR-FR-02a SIR-FR-02b	SIR output media has been presented to representatives of end-user group (IWW engineers). Considered useful and understandable for indicating condition of IWW infrastructure.
SIR-PS-03	Accuracy of scan data and visualisations	Compare processed data to observations, measurements and any records of features or repairs. Joints, cracks, voids etc.	Requires detailed visual inspection and measurement of lock and collection of any structural or repair information about the lock	SIR-FR-02a SIR-FR-02b SIR-FR-03 SIR-FR-04 SIR-FR-05	No independent assessment of features in IWW structure scanned.
SIR-PS-04	Accuracy of material composition classification by SIR	Compare classification of materials by the scan data processing, with specific or general information about the composition of the lock	Percentage of no. of Fols for which the material was correctly estimated	SIR-FR-03	Material classification of features not carried out. Not enough data for training state of the art process in this application.
SIR-PS-05	Further accuracy of location of features by SIR	Compare location of features in SIR data with locations of corresponding features from visual inspection. Additional to comparisons made when on site.	Differences between Fol position located with SIR and actual position on structure (distances, in m)	SIR-FR-04	No independent assessment of features in IWW structure scanned.

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SIR-PS-06	Accuracy of feature size characteristics	Part A: Compare size of general structural features of specifically or generally known size (e.g. joints, rebar, etc.) with size of features given by SIR Part B: Compare size of any known defects with size given by SIR.	Deviation of estimated volume of FOL vs its actual volume (as %)	SIR-FR-05	Just volume of overall Fols in a scanned volume was estimated through the data processing tool. No independent assessment of features in IWW structure scanned.
SIR-PS-07	Depth SIR able to resolve image of features	Part A: Evaluate maximum depth at which general structural features of specifically or generally known size (e.g. joints, rebar, etc.) can be detected/discerned by SIR, and any variation in accuracy or confidence with depth. Part B: Evaluate depth at which any known defects were detected by SIR and or discernible in imaging. Including any variation in accuracy, clarity, or confidence with depth.	Maximum depth (m) for which Fols can be accurately detected	SIR-FR-06	Features detected at distances of up to and just over 1m from lock wall contact surface by SIR. No independent assessment of distance of features from lock wall.
SIR-PS-08	Compatibility and integration with digital systems.	Part A: Demonstrate transfer of raw and/or processed data to Data Warehouse T5.2 and Smart Inland Waterway Monitor/Digital Twin T5.3. Part B: Accessibility (warehouse and DT) and visualisation of data and results (DT only) on data warehouse and DT.	N/A	SIR-FR-01 SIR-FR-02a SIR-FR-02b SIR-NFR-COMP-01 SIR-NFR-COMP-03	Manual transfer to Data Warehouse successful. Automated transfer from SIR to DW not tested as it was out of scope.

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SIR-PS-09	Data Transfer	Measure time to transfer raw scanning data from scanning system to processing system. Either measure time for a dataset for a whole lock, or extrapolate from time to transfer a dataset for a smaller portion of a lock.	Measurands characteristic to data communication (throughput, delay, latency, jitter, reliability, and security)	SIR-NFR-OP-05	Not tested.

Annex 1.3 Technical Requirements and Testing Plan for SB

Technical Requirements for SB

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
Functional Requirements (FR)					
SB-FR-01	Environmental sensing: hydrology	Measure water depth, near-surface current velocity, water temperature, buoy tilt	Depth accuracy $\leq \pm 0.1$ m; velocity accuracy $\leq \pm 0.1$ m/s; temp accuracy $\leq \pm 0.5$ °C; tilt resolution $\leq 1^\circ$	Yes	Tested on Warta River in Poznań and then confirmed at final location, measurements accuracy can be verified fully.
SB-FR-02	Atmospheric sensing	Record ambient temperature and basic weather conditions (if module fitted)	Ambient temp accuracy $\leq \pm 0.5$ °C; uptime $\geq 99\%$ during active hours	Yes	Tested in lab environment. Buoy capable of carrying weather station was never built.
SB-FR-03	Vessel detection via AIS	Detect/ingest AIS Class A/B messages near buoy	AIS decode success rate $\geq 98\%$; time to first AIS ≤ 60 s after radio on	Yes	Time to first AIS dependent on transmitters in range, but confirmed during lab tests
SB-FR-04	Bridge clearance ingest	Receive clearance from bridge device (AIS AtoN/custom message) and forward	Clearance latency buoy \rightarrow server ≤ 60 s (P95); data match rate with bridge $\geq 99\%$	Yes	Confirmed by lab tests and then verified on live system.
SB-FR-05	Configurable sampling	Support configurable measurement interval ≥ 3 min session, ≤ 10 min period	Config push success $\geq 99\%$; schedule adherence $\geq 99\%$	Yes	There may be slight delays to the schedule due to communication problems, depending on the environment.
SB-FR-06	Local data redundancy	Log data to uSD while also publishing to server	% records present in uSD and server $\geq 99.5\%$ match	Yes	Due to SD card capacity limitations, it is necessary to manage the recording history, but the most recent recordings are always kept.
SB-FR-07	Real-time publish	Publish telemetry/events via GSM/LTE MQTT	Telemetry E2E latency ≤ 120 s P95; publish success $\geq 99\%$	Yes	Data is published as soon as it reaches the buoy, however sensors are taking measurements in certain time intervals.

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
SB-FR-08	Remote configuration	Update BUOY.TXT, CLIENT.TXT, WORKDAYS.TXT via MQTT	Config apply time ≤ 60 min; rollback available	Yes	Configuration adjustments are tested, rollback is not available once changes are applied.
SB-FR-09	GNSS positioning	Provide GNSS fix for asset geotag and timebase	TTFF (warm) ≤ 60 s P95; position error ≤ 10 m (open sky)	Yes	Tested and confirmed during lab tests and on site.
SB-FR-10	State machine operation	Init \rightarrow Idle \rightarrow Measure \rightarrow Process \rightarrow Transmit	Missed scheduled cycle rate = 0 during active hours	Yes	Fully tested on every stage of development.
SB-FR-11	Event reporting	Immediate publish of vessel events when detected	Event publish latency ≤ 30 s P95; duplicate rate $< 1\%$	Yes	Events are processed and sent out immediately, tested.
SB-FR-12	External integrations	Forward data to SCMS, vessel tracking, EPCIS endpoints	HTTP 2xx delivery ratio $\geq 99\%$; schema conformance = 100%	Yes	Data forwarding is confirmed by receivers from SCMS and vehicle tracking EPCIS data is also checked by LPIT in the database.
SB-FR-13	Bridge device measurement	Radar/laser clearance measurement on schedule	Clearance accuracy $\leq \pm 0.2$ m; 4 cycles/day success $\geq 99\%$	Yes	Accuracy was tested and determined at a known location prior to deployment. This largely depends on the quality of the bracket that mounts the device to the bridge.
SB-FR-14	Deck buoy (test aid)	Receive NOMAD2 AIS and relay for QA during campaigns	Reception rate within 2.5 km $\geq 95\%$ of transmitted packets	Partially	Largely dependent on environmental conditions and requires carefully considered location.
SB-FR-15	Security (protocol level)	Use broker auth and topic scoping	Auth success rate 100%; unauthorised attempts blocked	Yes	SB system uses RabbitMQ implementation which is well known and widely tested against all possible threats, however it also was tested during SB development.
Non-Functional Requirements (NFR)					
Operability Requirements (NFR-OP)					
SB-NFR-OP-01	Environmental robustness	Operate in splash, rain, freeze/thaw, vibration	MTBF ≥ 6 months field; IP rating of insert $\geq IP67$	Partially	Isolation from environmental conditions is ensured, but it is difficult to determine MTBF under test conditions when changes or

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
					corrections to hardware and software are necessary.
SB-NFR-OP-02	Energy autonomy	Run on 12 V/24 Ah battery for targeted campaigns	≥ 52 days with ≤ 4 h/day active OR meet per-campaign duty; avg idle current ≤ 1 mA	Yes	Tested during operation on site, however the work cycle is based on number of measurements during the day rather than summarized time of operation.
SB-NFR-OP-03	Duty-cycle efficiency	Optimise on-time: 3-min measure / 10-min period	Wh/day \leq budget from simulations; P95 current during measure ≤ 450 mA	Yes	Tested and confirmed.
SB-NFR-OP-04	Comms resilience	Operate with intermittent GSM; store-and-forward	Backfill completeness $\geq 99\%$ within 24 h of link restore	Yes	Confirmed, data buffer capacity depends on software implementation and hardware limitations.
SB-NFR-OP-05	Scalability	Support >50 buoys/bridge nodes on one broker	Broker topic throughput ≥ 10 msgs/s sustained; no topic collision	Yes	This level of workload for the broker implementation used is negligibly small, we have a large margin for system expansion.
SB-NFR-OP-06	Maintainability	Tool-less access; modular boards/sensors	Mean service time (battery swap) ≤ 20 min; module swap ≤ 10 min	Partially	Tool-less access is not possible due to the need to seal the outer casing, but by removing the internal module rack, modules can be replaced quickly.
SB-NFR-OP-07	Data quality	Validate, de-duplicate, timestamp, unit consistency	% records passing QC $\geq 99\%$; clock drift $< \pm 2$ s/day	Yes	Not a single case of data duplication or timestamp problem was observed.
SB-NFR-OP-08	Safety & compliance	AtoN, AIS, radio, and buoyage compliance	Zero regulatory non-conformities; certified components where applicable	Yes	All components are available for sale on the EU market, the devices are fully compliant with the relevant EU regulations.
SB-NFR-OP-09	Interoperability	MQTT topics + HTTP payloads documented & versioned	Backward compatibility across 1 minor version;	Yes	Only supported and fully standard compliant software was used in the implementation.

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
			schema version present 100%		
SB-NFR-OP-10	Privacy	No personal data; vessel IDs handled per maritime norms	PII incidents = 0; AIS usage per regulations	Yes	Yes, however in real life scenarios there is no way to enforce the standards on board equipment as it is entirely under the control of shipowners.

Testing plan for SB

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SB-T-ENV-01	Depth accuracy	Compare buoy depth vs. calibrated reference (staff gauge/echo sounder)	Error $\leq \pm 0.1$ m (P95); drift over 24 h	SB-FR-01, SB-NFR-08	Reference measurement taken with tape measure which is much simpler and provides accurate outcome as well.
SB-T-ENV-02	Current velocity accuracy	Tow tank or controlled river reach with ADCP reference	Error $\leq \pm 0.1$ m/s (P95)	SB-FR-01, SB-NFR-08	Due to the lack of tow tank, measurements were taken using the float method.
SB-T-ENV-03	Water temperature accuracy	Ice bath / 3-point calibration (0/20/30 °C)	Error $\leq \pm 0.5$ °C; stability over 48 h	SB-FR-01, SB-NFR-08	Laboratory tests of one device were taken. Sensor measurements were compared to readings from an electronic thermometer.
SB-T-ENV-04	Buoy tilt sensing	Static tilt jig at 0/5/10/20°	Resolution $\leq 1^\circ$; linearity $R^2 \geq 0.98$	SB-FR-01, SB-NFR-08	Laboratory tests of one device were taken. Sensor measurements were compared to readings from an inclinometer.
SB-T-ATM-01	Ambient temp sensing	Chamber test -10...+45 °C	Error $\leq \pm 0.5$ °C;	SB-FR-02, SB-NFR-01	Measurement error of one device was taken. Manufacturer's parameters were met.

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SB-T-AIS-01	AIS decode performance	Replay Class A/B traffic; live over-air near harbour	Decode success $\geq 98\%$; first fix ≤ 60 s after radio on	SB-FR-03, SB-NFR-03	Tested during firmware development. Compared times of arrival on MQTT broker.
SB-T-BRG-01	Bridge clearance ingest	Bridge radar \rightarrow AIS AtoN \rightarrow buoy \rightarrow server	Latency buoy \rightarrow server ≤ 60 s (P95); match rate $\geq 99\%$ vs. bridge logs	SB-FR-04, SB-FR-13, SB-FR-12	Tested during firmware development.
SB-T-SCH-01	Configurable sampling	Push BUOY.TXT/WORKDAYS.TXT updates over MQTT	Apply ≤ 60 min; adherence $\geq 99\%$ to schedule	SB-FR-05, SB-FR-08, SB-FR-10	Tested during firmware development. No configuration was missed.
SB-T-STR-01	Storage redundancy	Induce GSM outages; compare uSD vs. server	Record match $\geq 99.5\%$; no gaps after backfill	SB-FR-06, SB-NFR-04	Automatic comparison of buoy storage and database were made.
SB-T-MQTT-01	Real-time publish latency	Edge \rightarrow broker \rightarrow server under good/poor RSSI	E2E telemetry ≤ 120 s (P95); publish success $\geq 99\%$	SB-FR-07, SB-NFR-04	In case of poor RSSI device stores data and sends it later. Process takes more than 120 seconds.
SB-T-GNSS-01	Positioning & timebase	Open-sky and urban canyon	TTFB warm ≤ 60 s (P95); CEP50 ≤ 10 m	SB-FR-09	The values declared by the manufacturer meet the requirements.
SB-T-SM-01	State machine reliability	72 h cyclic run; scheduled windows	Missed cycles = 0; transitions per spec	SB-FR-10, SB-NFR-10	State machine was tested after development process during one month continuous work in controlled environment.
SB-T-EVT-01	Event reporting latency	Vessel passes within 2.5 km	Event latency ≤ 30 s (P95); duplicate $< 1\%$	SB-FR-11, SB-FR-03	Tested during firmware development.
SB-T-EXT-01	External endpoints	SCMS + vessel API + EPCIS POSTs	HTTP 2xx $\geq 99\%$; schema 100% conformant	SB-FR-12, SB-NFR-11	Successful transmission confirmed.
SB-T-ENG-01	Energy autonomy (campaign)	Duty cycle: 3-min/10-min; active ≤ 4 h/day (52 d sim)	Avg idle ≤ 1 mA; meet ≥ 52 d or campaign target	SB-NFR-02, SB-NFR-03	Tested during firmware development. Power consumption monitored by multimeter.

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
SB-T-RES-01	Store-and-forward resilience	24 h no-cell; restore link	Backfill $\geq 99\%$ within 24 h of restore	SB-NFR-04, SB-FR-06	Test in the anechoic chamber were made.
SB-T-RUG-01	Environmental robustness	IP67 insert; rain spray; vibration; freeze/thaw	No water ingress; normal ops; MTBF projection ≥ 6 mo	SB-NFR-01	After real environment tests no water was found inside sealed module.
SB-T-MTN-01	Maintainability	Battery swap; module swap drills	Battery swap ≤ 20 min; module swap ≤ 10 min	SB-NFR-06	The process was performed several times during maintenance work in December 2024. All time targets were met.
SB-T-DQ-01	Data quality & QC	Unit checks, time sync, de-dup in pipeline	$\geq 99\%$ records pass QC; clock drift $< \pm 2$ s/day	SB-NFR-08, SB-NFR-10	Tested and confirmed-
SB-T-SCL-01	Scalability on broker	Emulate 50+ nodes at 10 msg/s	No topic collision; broker stable; $< 1\%$ drop	SB-NFR-05, SB-NFR-11	It has not been tested as the broker is well known implementation and those values lays well within its capabilities.
SB-T-OBS-01	Health/alerts	Simulate low battery, sensor fault, link loss	Health ping ≤ 10 min; alert ≤ 5 min	SB-NFR-10	There was no test dedicated to check this however proper operation was confirmed during SB testing.
SB-T-SEC-01	Protocol security	Broker auth, topic ACLs, port scans	100% auth; unauthorised blocked; no open topics	SB-FR-15, SB-NFR-09	Tested and confirmed.
SB-T-PRV-01	Privacy & AIS policy	Log review; AIS retention policy	PII incidents = 0; compliant usage	SB-NFR-12, SB-NFR-09	AIS devices are fully compliant with maritime and other regulations and operates accordingly to declaration provided by manufacturers.

NOTE: Test procedures for specific tests

Test Code	Procedure Description	Equipment / Tools Required
SB-T-ENV-01	Deploy buoy in controlled depth site. Compare sensor readings to staff gauge/echo sounder reference.	Calibrated depth gauge, echo sounder, buoy

SB-T-ENV-02	Tow buoy in flume/tank with ADCP baseline. Record sensor vs. reference velocity.	ADCP, tow tank/river section, buoy
SB-T-AIS-01	Replay AIS traffic in lab and test over-air with vessels in harbour. Measure decode success & latency.	AIS traffic generator, vessels with AIS, buoy
SB-T-BRG-01	Mount bridge device, trigger clearance readings, verify relay via AIS AtoN to buoy → server.	Bridge radar, AIS AtoN, buoy, server logs
SB-T-ENG-01	Run long-term duty cycle sim (3-min/10-min, ≤ 4 h/day). Track current draw & battery SOC.	Current logger, battery analyzer, buoy
SB-T-SEC-01	Attempt broker login without credentials; scan ports; verify topics access control.	MQTT broker, penetration test tools

Annex 1.4 Technical Requirements and Testing Plan for FOS

Technical Requirements for FOS

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
Functional Requirements (FR)					
FOS-FR-01	The system shall detect variations of the height of the sediments accumulated on the active surface	The system operates as a scale, with FBG sensors embedded in weighing pads to measure sediments load. According to the density of the sediments typical at the installation section, the height of the columns of sediments is provided	YES Measurement range: from 0m to 5m	YES, in simulated condition with reference loads considering sediment density from PO pilot	Fully satisfying KPI set up for tests in simulated environment in laboratory (as testing in the pilot was out-of-the-scope of the project).
FOS-FR-02	The system shall provide real-time data acquisition with an error of ± 30 cm in the full measurement range 0 – 500cm.	Adopting metrology, error is stated instead of resolution and sensitivity. The stated error is referred to a precise knowledge of the density of the sediments. The uncertainty on the density of the sediments affects the error.	YES Error ± 30 cm in the measurement range from 0m to 5m	YES, in simulated condition with reference loads considering sediment density from PO pilot	Fully satisfying KPI but tested in simulated environment in laboratory, testing in the pilot was out-of-the-scope of the project.
FOS-FR-03	The system shall ensure continuous monitoring without the need for electrical power supply at the measurement point.	Technology based on optical passive principle, no local power supply needed.	NO	N/A	Fully
FOS-FR-04	The system shall withstand prolonged submersion in riverbed conditions without variation of the error	Design and production shall consider underwater condition at the location of installation, in particular with respect to the expected water flow regime in exceptional environmental conditions.	YES, 25 years	Partially, in simulated condition: 6 months with no recalibration	Tested in simulated environment in laboratory (testing in the pilot was out-of-the-scope of the project).

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
FOS-FR-05	Data collected shall be transmitted to the CRISTAL Data Acquisition System and Digital Twin in standard JSON format.	Ensures interoperability with CRISTAL framework.	As per the CRISTAL general specification	NO	Not tested. No critical issues can be expected.
Non-Functional Requirements (NFR)					
Operability Requirements (NFR-OP)					
FOS-NFR-OP-01	The system shall be operationally efficient in outdoor and underwater environments with varying flow and sediment pace accumulation.	Environmental resilience is key to operation. The mechanical structure of the system and the civil engineering works for its installation shall be adequate for the most severe expected operating conditions	YES To be worked out with respect to standard civil and mechanical engineering construction regulation for the selected installation site	NO	To be engineered and tested for in real situ application. No critical issues are expected for the FBG sensing part. Critical issues can arise for the mechanical part in case of most severe installation sites.
FOS-NFR-OP-02	Installation and dismantling of the system shall be achievable in less than 6 hours per single device by a team of 2 operators.	Important for practical deployment in rivers. The figure is given for the active system itself (one device) with no consideration of the accessory civil engineering works (foundation, deploying of protected backbone fibre optic cables)	YES Setup/dismantling time ≤ 6 hours per device	NO	To be tested. Special engineering solutions could be necessary for specific sites (high current flow, high depth)
FOS-NFR-OP-03	The sensors shall have a minimum operational lifespan of 5 years with minimal maintenance.	Durability is critical for cost-effectiveness.	YES ≥ 5 years operational lifespan	NO	To be tested. No critical issues are expected.
FOS-NFR-OP-04	The system should be easily scalable both in dimension of the active plate and in the multiplicity of devices	Scalability ensures wider applicability.	NO; a practical limit of $2 \times 2 \text{m}^2$ can be assumed for the active plate of each device. No	NO	Scalability is reached by multiplicity of units deployed with the necessary pattern. No

Req. code	Requirement Definition	Additional details/ description	KPIs definitions (if any)	Evaluated from Pilot(s) results	Status/ Outcome
	arranged as a pattern, across different riverbed sections.		limit applies to the multiplicity of the devices		limit to multiplicity occurs.
FOS-NFR-OP-05	The system shall maintain the error under temperature variations from $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.	Ensures stability in seasonal conditions.	YES Error $\pm 30\text{ cm}$ in the range from $-10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $+40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$	NO	To be tested. No critical issues are expected, as the system has built-in temperature compensation of the FBG signal. FBG compensation technology already tested in the range here of interest.

Testing plan for FOS

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
On-site (laboratory) tests					
FOS-OS-01	Measurement of time to install	Deployment of the system on the submerged foundation, connections, power-on, handshake with DAQ/interrogator	Time to install	FOS-NFR-OP-02	One working day estimated (no test on pilot was done). Assuming civil engineering work underwater ready.
FOS-OS-02	Measurement of time to pack up	From acquisition stop to safety and restoration of navigability/bank	Time to pack up	FOS-NFR-OP-02	One working day, estimated.
FOS-OS-03	Baseline stabilisation time	Time to reach stable baseline (drift $<$ threshold) after immersion	Time to stable baseline; baseline drift (dB/h or $\mu\epsilon/h$)	FOS-NFR-OP-05	Depends on environmental condition, 48 hours typical time, subject to variation to ensure thermal equilibrium of the system with the water.

Test Code	Measurement/ Assessment	Additional details/ description	Test Measurands/ Metrics	Reqs Relevant to Assessment	Outcome and discussion
FOS-OS-04	Site power compatibility	Power supply, actual consumption	Avg/peak power (W),		Avg power consumption at the site where the acquisition system is installed, 300W, No power supply necessary at the installation site.
FOS-OS-05	Data link & latency	Telemetry check (4G/5G/LoRa/Ethernet) and end-to-end latency	Packet loss %, data latency (s)	FOS-FR-05	Sensors are physically connected to the remote acquisition system by fibre optic, thus no data loss can be reliably assumed. Data acquisition system is assumed to be installed with adequate LAN/ethernet connection.
FOS-OS-06	Mounting robustness in flow	Check fastenings, cable protection, friction and vibrations in current	Displacements (mm), events of slack/abrasion		FOS tested in laboratory only. Environmental condition shall address the physical installation according to the actual conditions of the installation site.
FOS-OS-7	Cross-sensitivity (temp/strain/pressure)	Thermal compensation	Dependence of the height of the pile up on temperature	FOS-FR-05 FOS-NFR-OP-05	Full thermal compensation is achieved, residual error not significant. Assessment refers to laboratory measurements.
Post-pilot tests					
FOS-PS-01	Time to process & publish	Time from download to map/time series ready	Processing time delay	FOS-FR-05	Processing is done in real time. Delay in results availability to user may depend on the publishing system only
FOS-PS-02	Accuracy vs inspections/records	Comparison with independent measurement	RMSE	FOS-FR-01 FOS-NFR-OP-05	resolution of +/- 30 cm

Annex 2. BMC SCMS Validation Surveys

Italian SCMS BMC Validation Survey Results

CRISTAL BMC IT

24 - 25 Jul 2025

Poll results

slido

Table of contents

- Please select the choices that best describe your organisation [select all that apply].
- Please select the statements that you think apply to your organisation with regard to a potential CRISTAL SCMS [select all that apply].
- How appealing is the CRISTAL SCMS offer to your organisation, where 5 is *very* appealing and 1 is *not all* appealing.
- How well have we captured all the elements of the offer, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- If there are any customer benefits missing from the offer, please add them as 1-3 words here:
- How well have we captured all the elements of the Demand Side, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- How well have we captured all the elements of the Supply Side, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- How well have we captured all the elements of the Finance, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- If there are any elements missing from the
- Finance, please add them as words here:
- With regard to resilience during extreme weather and man-made events, how well will the SCMS [alone] help, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- If the CRISTAL SCMS was fully implemented, what growth in traffic do you think it may attract to inland waterways. [Use your own locale and experience.]
- Please select the statements that you NOW think could apply to your organisation with regard to a potential CRISTAL SCMS [select all that apply].
- Did we run this event well? Please rank us below, using the emoji faces as a guide!

slido

Multiple-choice poll

Please select the choices that best describe your organisation [select all that apply]. 0 1 1
(1/2)

slido

Multiple-choice poll

Please select the choices that best describe your organisation [select all that apply]. 0 1 1
(2/2)

slido

Multiple-choice poll

Please select the statements that you think apply to your organisation with regard to a potential CRISTAL SCMS [select all that apply].

0 1 1

We are actors in inland waterways.

We are stakeholders in inland waterways but PASSIVE.

We are stakeholders in inland waterways and ACTIVE.

We are not actors in inland waterways

slido

Rating poll

How appealing is the CRISTAL SCMS offer to your organisation, where is 5 is *very* appealing and 1 is *not all* appealing.

0 1 1

Score: 4.2

slido

Rating poll

How well have we captured all the elements of the offer, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

0 1 1

slido

Wordcloud poll

If there are any customer benefits missing from the offer, please add them as 1-3 words here:

0 1 1

disponibilità nei porti

Rating poll

How well have we captured all the elements of the Demand Side, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

0 1 1

slido

Rating poll

How well have we captured all the elements of the Supply Side, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

0 1 1

slido

Rating poll

How well have we captured all the elements of the Finance, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

0 1 1

slido

Wordcloud poll

If there are any elements missing from the Finance, please add them as words here:

0 1 1

Rating poll

With regard to resilience during extreme weather and man-made events, how well will the SCMS [alone] help, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

0 1 1

slido

Multiple-choice poll

If the CRISTAL SCMS was fully implemented, what growth in traffic do you think it may attract to inland waterways. [Use your own locale and experience.]

0 1 1

(1/2)

No increase

0 %

+5%

0 %

+10%

27 %

+20%

18 %

+30%

45 %

slido

Multiple-choice poll

If the CRISTAL SCMS was fully implemented, what growth in traffic do you think it may attract to inland waterways. [Use your own locale and experience.]

(2/2)

0 1 1

+40% and higher
 9 %

slido

Multiple-choice poll

Please select the statements that you NOW think could apply to your organisation with regard to a potential CRISTAL SCMS [select all that apply].

0 1 1

We could be actors in inland waterways.
 45 %

We could be stakeholders in inland waterways but PASSIVE.
 45 %

We could be stakeholders in inland waterways and ACTIVE.
 9 %

We could not be actors in inland waterways
 0 %

slido

Rating poll

Did we run this event well? Please rank us below, using the emoji faces as a guide!

0 1 1

slido

French SCMS BMC Validation Survey Results

CRISTAL BMC VNF

24 - 27 Jul 2025

Poll results

slido

Table of contents

- Please select the choices that best describe your organisation [select all that apply].
- Please select the statements that you think apply to your organisation with regard to a potential CRISTAL SCMS [select all that apply].
- How appealing is the CRISTAL SCMS offer to your organisation, where 5 is *very* appealing and 1 is *not at all* appealing.
- How well have we captured all the elements of the offer, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- If there are any customer benefits missing from the offer, please add them as 1-3 words here:
- How well have we captured all the elements of the Demand Side, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- How well have we captured all the elements of the Supply Side, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- How well have we captured all the elements of the Finance, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- If there are any elements missing from the

slido

Table of contents

- Finance, please add them as words here:
- With regard to resilience during extreme weather and man-made events, how well will the SCMS [alone] help, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.
- If the CRISTAL SCMS was fully implemented, what growth in traffic do you think it may attract to inland waterways. [Use your own locale and experience.]
- Please select the statements that you NOW think could apply to your organisation with regard to a potential CRISTAL SCMS [select all that apply].
- Did we run this event well? Please rank us below, using the emoji faces as a guide!

slido

Multiple-choice poll

Please select the choices that best describe your organisation [select all that apply]. 004
(1/2)

Infrastructure managers

Logistics service providers

Information system providers

Technology developers

Barge operators

slido

Multiple-choice poll

Please select the choices that best describe your organisation [select all that apply].
(2/2)

004

Terminal operators

0 %

City/Local/Regional government

0 %

National or EU level government

0 %

Trade or research association

0 %

Research centre or University

0 %

slido

Multiple-choice poll

Please select the statements that you think apply to your organisation with regard to a potential CRISTAL SCMS [select all that apply].

003

We are actors in inland waterways.

100 %

We are stakeholders in inland waterways but PASSIVE.

0 %

We are stakeholders in inland waterways and ACTIVE.

0 %

We are not actors in inland waterways

0 %

slido

Rating poll

How appealing is the CRISTAL SCMS offer to your organisation, where 5 is *very* appealing and 1 is *not all* appealing.

0 0 4

slido

Rating poll

How well have we captured all the elements of the offer, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

0 0 4

slido

Wordcloud poll

If there are any customer benefits missing from the offer, please add them as 1-3 words here:

004

N/A
data related to railways network & offer
leaves road: careful
cargoroute IWW
anticipate

Rating poll

How well have we captured all the elements of the Demand Side, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

004

Score: 4.5

slido

Rating poll

How well have we captured all the elements of the Supply Side, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

0 0 4

slido

Rating poll

How well have we captured all the elements of the Finance, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

0 0 4

slido

Wordcloud poll

If there are any elements missing from the Finance, please add them as words here:

004

N/A approximate cost
proper numbers
development costs

Rating poll

With regard to resilience during extreme weather and man-made events, how well will the SCMS [alone] help, where 1 is not at all well and 5 is comprehensively.

004

slido

Multiple-choice poll

If the CRISTAL SCMS was fully implemented, what growth in traffic do you think it may attract to inland waterways. [Use your own locale and experience.]

(1/2)

004

No increase

0 %

+5%

50 %

+10%

50 %

+20%

0 %

+30%

0 %

slido

Multiple-choice poll

If the CRISTAL SCMS was fully implemented, what growth in traffic do you think it may attract to inland waterways. [Use your own locale and experience.]

(2/2)

004

+40% and higher

0 %

slido

Multiple-choice poll

Please select the statements that you NOW think could apply to your organisation with regard to a potential CRISTAL SCMS [select all that apply].

003

We could be actors in inland waterways.

We could be stakeholders in inland waterways but PASSIVE.

We could be stakeholders in inland waterways and ACTIVE.

We could not be actors in inland waterways

slido

Rating poll

Did we run this event well? Please rank us below, using the emoji faces as a guide!

004

Score: 4.8

slido

Polish SCMS BMC Validation Survey Results

The quantitative survey, or quantitative polling, regarding the Polish Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS) Business Model Canvas (BMC) was conducted on **April 14, 2025**.

This quantitative stakeholder polling was part of the larger Polish Living Lab BMC Workshop, which took place on **Monday, April 14, 2025**, at the University of Gdańsk.

Please select the answer that best describe your organization.	Sum - Count	Percentage
Barge Operators / Captains	2	9.09%
Infrastructure Managers	2	9.09%
Logistics Service Providers	4	18.18%
National or EU Authorities	3	13.64%
Other	1	4.55%
Research Centre or University	8	36.36%
Terminal Operators / Port Authorities	1	4.55%
Trade or Research Associations	1	4.55%
Total Result	22	

Please select the answer that best describe your organization.

Please select the statements that apply to your organisation in the context of a potential CRISTAL SCMS system.	Sum - Count	Percentage
We are active participants in IWT.	3	12.50%
We are active stakeholders in IWT.	1	4.17%
We are not participants in IWT.	1	4.17%
We are not stakeholders in IWT.	3	12.50%
We are stakeholders in IWT and we are ACTIVE.	9	37.50%
We are stakeholders in IWT, but in a PASSIVE way.	7	29.17%
Total Result	24	

How attractive is the CRISTAL SCMS offering to your organisation?
 Where 5 means very attractive and 1 means not attractive at all

How well have we managed to cover all elements of the offer?
 Where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'comprehensively'

If any customer benefits are missing from the offer, please state them in 1-3 words:
Possibility of interfacing with other systems
Predictability
Ship monitoring
Relationship to non-commercial systems, cost and schedule
Social
Not attractive from a commercial logistics operations point of view

How well have we captured all the elements of the demand side?
 (Where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'comprehensively').

If any demand-side items are missing, please provide them here:
Customers of all these transport companies
Cargo collectors, universities
Operators of integration platforms, e.g. Sixfold, Transporeon, Project 44
Primary cargo managers
Private water users
NGOS
Operators of integration platforms, e.g. Sixfold, Transporeon, Project 44
Seaports, companies operating on the river
End users of the transport service.

How well did we capture all the elements of the supply side?
Where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'comprehensively'

If any supply-side items are missing, please provide them here:
It is ok
There is no shortage of
All elements are well described.
Technologies, carriers
Risks associated with data availability

How well did we capture all the financial elements?
 Where 1 means 'not at all' and 5 means 'comprehensively'

If any financial elements are missing, please provide them here:
Purchase of equipment
Nothing missing
Investment costs and its impact on the business model
Can it be subsidised?
The user if given a choice will choose the free applications available.
National co-financing/use by road authorities

If the CRISTAL SCMS system were fully implemented, what increase in traffic do you think it would attract to IWT? [Please base this on local experience.]	
Case	IWT traffic increase
1	10.00%
2	20.00%
3	10.00%
4	10.00%
5	0.00%
6	5.00%
7	10.00%
8	10.00%
9	0.00%
10	10.00%
11	5.00%
12	5.00%
13	5.00%
14	10.00%
15	0.00%
16	30.00%
17	10.00%
18	5.00%
19	20.00%
20	20.00%
21	5.00%
average	9.52%
median	10.00%

Please select statements that NOW may apply to your organisation in the context of a potential CRISTAL SCMS [please tick all that apply].	Percentage
a. We could be participants in inland navigation.;	28.00%
b. We could be stakeholders in inland navigation, but in a PASSIVE way.;	32.00%
c. We could be stakeholders in inland navigation and be ACTIVE .;	28.00%
d. We could not be participants in inland navigation.;	12.00%

Annex 3. CRISTAL Task 10.3 Questionnaire (for operational validation)

Introduction

The purpose of this questionnaire is to contribute to the operational validation of the technologies deployed in the Cristal project.

The overall goal is to answer questions like:

- **Which concrete experiences were made while running the pilot technologies?**
- **How did things practically work out in operations?**
- **Which efficiency gains became evident?**
- **Which outlook can be estimated regarding a wider application of the Cristal technologies?**

When talking about “technologies”, we refer to those technologies introduced through Cristal, always in accordance with the connecting Digital Twin solutions as a technology application, if implemented.

French pilot - VNF	Italian pilot - AIPO, IV	Polish pilot - L-PIT, UniGDA
1. AE <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) <input type="checkbox"/>	1. (FOS) – Navigation bulletin ⁷ <input type="checkbox"/> 2. AE <input type="checkbox"/>	1. Smart buoy

Please tick ONE technology and then complete this questionnaire for this one technology chosen. If you have deployed more than one technology, please fill out a separate questionnaire for the second technology.

For questions that require a quantitative answer, please specify how it was measured.

Where you do not have exact values, please indicate a qualified estimation and state if so. Always note estimations with an (E).

If you are unable to answer a particular question, skip it.

Please indicate your organisation and the inland waterway (IWW) segment that you have been adopting the specific technology for. (we don't want data or estimates for the whole IWW network, since this would very likely blur any achieved insights)

Organisation: _____

IWW segment(s): _____

⁷ Since the FOS are a laboratory test and could be a tool for a better navigation forecast, I would like to ask the Italian pilot rather regarding their concrete product development of a better navigation forecast.

The questionnaire is structured into 8 sections. The questions and sections originate from the agreed KPIs and some extended which are useful to obtain for a better understanding of the issues.

Internal effects: The infrastructure operations

Section 1: Infrastructure Status

What is the capacity of the IWW segment before and after introducing the technology? Please indicate the capacity for the mean water level, a low-water level and a high-water level (choose and define low and high yourself) in number of vessels per day. If no exact numbers of vessels are available, please give a qualified estimation.

1.1 What are the capacities of the IWW segment before and after introducing the technology? Please indicate in vessels per day.

		Before	With Cristal impact also indicate anticipated forecast year
Usual capacity	Mean Water level (draught in meters):	No vessels / day:	No vessels / day:
Low water capacity	Deviation from mean water level:	No vessels / day:	No vessels / day:
High water capacity	Deviation from mean water level: (draught in meters)	No vessels / day:	No vessels / day:

1.2 What type of disruptions re. the use of the infrastructure did you experience before and after the introducing the technology, apart from water levels? How do the disruptions impact the capacity/ availability of the IWW segment? Please indicate how the disruptions are measured, e.g. in number of vessels per day. If no direct measurement is possible, please briefly elaborate the impact in a few sentences.

Type of disruption	Impact on the capacity Base scenario	Impact on the capacity With Cristal impact	Measured in (indicate unit)

1.3 What is and will be the status of the real-time infrastructure and water level monitoring?

Please, indicate what kind of infrastructure/monitoring is in place, what is being measured, how often it is measured, e.g. number of updates per day, and how much percent of river segment is covered by it. If no percentage is available, please give a qualified estimation.

Type of measurement Which infrastructure element	Frequency of measurement (e.g. real-time / daily)	% of the river segment covered Before	% of the river segment covered With Cristal impact, indicate forecast year
Real time infrastructure monitoring			
Water level monitoring			

1.4 On a scale of 1 to 5, what is the OPERATIONAL readiness level of the technology (not the TRL system)? Please select the option that best represents the readiness level for your individual requirements.

- 1. Basic concept or idea – not yet ready for deployment
- 2. Proof of concept (early-stage testing and validation)
- 3. Prototype developed and tested in a controlled environment
- 4. Validated in an operational environment
- 5. Fully deployed and operational in real-world conditions

Please stress where the technology fits well and where you see further demand for customisation /improvements

1.5 Does unplanned downtime of locks and river/canal segments occur on your IWW segment? Please indicate the average unplanned downtime in days:hours:minutes per lock and/or segment per year.

Specification of lock/segment	Average unplanned downtime Before	Average unplanned downtime With Cristal impact, indicate forecast year

If no exact measurement is available, please briefly elaborate whether unplanned downtime has changed with the introduction of the technology.

1.6 What is the estimated infrastructure lifespan before and after introducing the technology? Please indicate in years. If no exact number is available, please give a qualified estimate.

Type of infrastructure, e.g. lock gates, lock walls, canal walls	Lifespan in years before	Lifespan in years before With Cristal impact -estimate

1.7 Can the technology impact the predictability of maintenance scheduling (effective facility and asset management)? Please describe the impact.

1.8 Will the technology decrease the overall maintenance costs? Please stress

Section 2 : Data Management for Infrastructure Maintenance

Has or will data accuracy and completeness improve? Have the data processing time or costs improved?

Monitored infrastructure asset	Way of monitoring	Any improvement of data accuracy with Cristal Impact, in % change to base scen., state forecast year	Any improvement of data processing time with Cristal Impact, in % change to base scen., state forecast year	Any improvement of data processing costs with Cristal Impact, in % change to base scen., state forecast year

Section 3: Technology Adoption

3.1 How many specific technological objects have been installed within the context of Cristal? Please indicate in absolute numbers if possible.

Type of technological object	Number of objects installed

3.2 On a scale from 1 to 5, how satisfied are you with the technology regarding its usage in your operations? Please select the number that best represents your level of satisfaction.

- 1. Very Dissatisfied – The technologies did not meet expectations or created significant challenges.
- 2. Dissatisfied – The technologies were below expectations and caused some issues.
- 3. Neutral – The technologies met expectations but without any standout performance or issues.
- 4. Satisfied – The technologies worked well and met expectations with minor improvements possible.
- 5. Very Satisfied – The technologies exceeded expectations and significantly improved operations.

Please comment on the above statement

3.3 Which return on investment (ROI) do you expect from the technology, if any? Please briefly elaborate on how you expect a ROI. If possible, indicate the ROI in %.

Section 4: Regulatory Compliance

4.1 What type of compliance-related incident did you experience before and after introducing the technology? Please list the types of incidents, how they were measured and what was measured.

Type of Compliance Incident	Measurement	Frequency/Quantity Before	Frequency/Quantity With Cristal impact change to base scen., state forecast year

4.2 Are there any environmental standards that you need to meet that are tackled by the technology and processes can be improved or eased by the technology? Please describe.

Environmental Standard	Measurement	Impact of technology

Please stress

4.3 Can the technology decrease the time (and the costs) required for regular inspections?

Monitored infrastructure asset	Way of monitoring	Time With Cristal impact change to base scen., state forecast year in %	Costs With Cristal impact change to base scen., state forecast year in %

Please stress

Section 5: Italian KPIs (only Italian pilot)

5.1 What is the number of Italian User Reservations of Navigation Lock by Multimodal Platform?
 Before: _____ With Cristal impact: _____

5.2 What is the number of Italian Navigation Bulletin downloads?
 Before: _____ With Cristal impact: _____

5.3 What is the number of Italian registered users?
 Before: _____ With Cristal impact: _____

5.4 What is the number of Italian Navigation forecast points along the river?
 Before: _____ With Cristal impact: _____

External effects

Section 6: External impacts and Traffic volumes

6.1 How many extreme weather incidents are detected per year? If possible, please indicate the type of incidents and the frequency per year. If no exact numbers are available, please list the different types of possible incidents and give a qualified estimation about their frequency.

Extreme Weather Incident	Frequency

6.2 Traffic observations before and after Cristal Impact (use estimates, if necessary)

	Before	With Cristal impact change to base scen., state forecast year
Number of vessels tracked by a traffic management system		
Cargo volume is transported on your IWW segment in tonnes		
Transport work in tkm		
Overall vessel throughput on your IWW segment (number)		
Congestion level at critical points such as locks (av. Number of vessels queuing per day)		

Section 7: Navigation Efficiency

	Before	With Cristal impact change to base scen., state forecast year
How many vessels were on time on your IWW segment in %		
Delays/Waiting times (actual-estimated time of arrival as absolute value per shipment)		
Operational costs of a fixed route on the river segment? Please indicate in euro/cargo-unit/km or give a qualified estimation. For instance, 10€/TEU/km. The cargo unit could be TEU for containers, or tons for bulk cargo. Please use the latest available data		
Overall corridor/ segment transit time (in hours) to calculate travel time reduction Define corridor (origin-destination pair)		
Cargo capacity per vessel (%)		

Section 8: Intermodal Integration

	Before	With Cristal impact change to base scen., state forecast year
Modal share of IWW in the region of your IWW segment in %		
Passenger volumes in your IWW segment in pax number		

Annex 4. Bayesian full questionnaires

Questionnaire 1 – Expert survey for causal relations among KPIs

CRISTAL Expert Assessment Questionnaire

Objective:

This questionnaire is part of Task 10.4 – Sustainability Validation in the CRISTAL project. Its purpose is to gather expert knowledge to support the construction of a Bayesian Network model, which will serve as a probabilistic decision-support tool for evaluating the Sustainability Index (SI) of multimodal freight transport solutions.

Instructions:

For each KPI listed in the table:

1. Direct Impact on Sustainability Index (SI):

- Tick the box if you believe the KPI has a direct influence on the overall sustainability outcome.
- Leave it unticked if the influence is only indirect or negligible.

2. Causal Influence on Other KPIs:

- In the columns labeled "Directly Influences the Following KPI," select from the drop-down list any other KPI that you believe is directly affected by the current KPI. This will help define the causal structure of the Bayesian Network (i.e., the directional edges between nodes).

Why your input matters:

Bayesian methodology allows us to incorporate both uncertainty and expert judgement in modeling how Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) contribute to sustainability. Your expert opinion will help define:

- Which KPIs have a direct influence on overall sustainability (SI).
- How KPIs interact and influence one another within the system.

Notes:

- The table includes three columns for listing influenced KPIs, but this **does not mean** each KPI must influence three others — it may influence only one or two.
- There are no right or wrong answers — the goal is to reflect your expert understanding of the interdependencies in the transport system.
- All responses will be treated confidentially and will only be used for the purposes of model building and validation.

Example:

If "Operational Efficiency" (KPI 1) improves "Shipment Delay Reduction" (KPI 13) and "Energy Consumption" (KPI 15), then you would:

KPI	direct impact on SI	Directly influences	Directly Influences	Directly Influences
Operational Efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/>	Shipment Delay Reduction	Energy Consumption	

Figure 16: Instructions provided to experts for filling the survey for causal relations among KPIs

	Which of the following KPIs do you consider to have a <i>direct</i> influence on the overall Sustainability Index (SI)? <i>(Please tick all that apply)</i>	Please indicate for each KPI which <i>other KPI(s)</i> it directly influences.	Please indicate for each KPI which <i>other KPI(s)</i> it directly influences.	Please indicate for each KPI which <i>other KPI(s)</i> it directly influences.
		<i>(Fill in the cells below — leave blank if no direct influence exists)</i>		
KPI	Tick if direct impact on SI	Directly Influences the Following KPI	Directly Influences the Following KPI	Directly Influences the Following KPI
Operational Efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Modal Shift Rate	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Continuity Under Disruption	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Weather Resilience	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Infrastructure Resilience	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Logistics Continuity	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Recycled Materials Use	<input type="checkbox"/>			
EU Compliance Level	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Shipment Waiting Time	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Corridor disruption Functionality Rate	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Recovery time	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Governance Effectiveness	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Shipment Delay	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Carbon Emissions Reduction	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Energy Consumption	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Accident Reduction	<input type="checkbox"/>			
Public Perception	<input type="checkbox"/>			

Table 6: Questionnaire for defining causal relations

Questionnaire 2 – Pilot teams for empirical priors

Table 7: Questionnaire for defining empirical priors

#	Revised	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Excessively
1	To what extent will the integrated system improve operational efficiency and achieve an 80% reliability target during disruptions (weather/human factors)?					
2	What is the probability that the system will lead to at least a 20% modal shift to inland waterways?					
3	What is the probability that the system will maintain at least 50% operational continuity during disruptions across the multimodal network?					
4	Given an extreme weather event, what is the likelihood that the system maintains inland waterway navigability above 50%?					
5	How much will the system improve navigability during infrastructure failure events?					
6	How likely is the system to maintain 80% operational continuity in the logistics network during disruptions?					
7	How likely is the system to increase the use of recycled materials by 30% in transport infrastructure?					
8	How likely is the system to facilitate compliance with EU legislation during construction, maintenance, and operation of infrastructure (e.g., for hydraulic structures)?					
9	How likely is the system to reduce shipment waiting times in inland waterway transport?					
10	How likely is the system to ensure 50% network functionality during weather- or human-induced disruptions?					
11	How likely is the system to maintain efficient operations and ensure network functionality during weather- or human-induced disruptions?					
12	To what extent will the governance models developed in CRISTAL enable cross-border,					

#	Revised	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Excessively
	cross-modal, or inter-institutional collaboration to meet project targets?					
13	How likely is the integrated system to reduce waiting times/relays for shipments in inland waterway transport?					
14	To what extent will the system reduce carbon emissions associated with freight transport operations?					
15	How much will the system decrease energy consumption?					
16	To what extent will the system reduce accidents in river transportation operations?					
17	How much will the system improve public perception of inland waterways as a reliable and resilient transport mode?					

Questionnaire 3 – Specialists populated CPTs

CRISTAL
Expert Assessment Questionnaire

Objective:
This questionnaire is part of Task 10.4 – Sustainability Validation in the CRISTAL project. Its purpose is to collect expert estimates of conditional probabilities that define how changes in one KPI affect the likelihood of different states (High, Moderate, Low) of another KPI. These probabilities will populate the Bayesian Network's Conditional Probability Tables (CPTs).

Why your input matters:
Bayesian methodology requires not only knowing which KPIs influence others but also quantifying how strongly they do so under different conditions. Your expert judgments will help us determine: "Given Parent KPI A is in state X, which state of Child KPI B is most likely?"

Instructions:

1. Structure of the Table:
Parent KPIs (green rows) each have three possible states (see list below). Child KPIs (blue columns) each have three possible states of their own. For each parent-child pair, you are asked to assess how the state of the Parent affects the expected value of the Child.

2. Your Task:
For each Parent KPI, consider three possible states: High, Moderate, and Low. For each state of the Parent KPI: Choose the most likely expected state of the Child KPI. Use the Drop-down Lists:

Notes:
No "Correct" Values: These are expert estimates, if you're uncertain, choose the best guess and note your confidence if the form allows.
Confidentiality: All responses remain confidential and are used solely for Bayesian model construction and validation.

KPI definitions
The full definitions for each KPI are listed below. You can also view them in the "Conditional Probabilities" spreadsheet by selecting any KPI cell.

Example:
Parent = Operational Efficiency at "medium/high increase" → choose the single most likely state of the Child KPI "Energy Consumption" from its three options.

KPI	value	Energy Consumption	
		medium/high increase (positive impact)	medium/high decrease (positive impact)
Operational Efficiency	medium/high increase (positive impact)	For a medium/high increase (positive impact) Operational Efficiency, Energy Consumption is going	medium/high decrease (positive impact)
	no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)	For a no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact) Operational Efficiency, Energy Consumption is going to face	no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)
	medium/high decrease (negative impact)	For a medium/high decrease (negative impact) Operational Efficiency, Energy Consumption is going	medium/high increase (negative impact)

Figure 17: Instructions provided to experts for populating CPTs

Table 8: Example of the CPTs table provided to experts for populating

	Parent KPI	Value	Child KPI 1		Child KPI 2		Child KPI3
			Energy Consumption	Operational Efficiency	Carbon Emissions	Operational Efficiency	Logistics Continuity
1	Operational Efficiency	medium/high increase (positive impact)		medium/high increase (positive impact)		medium/high increase (positive impact)	
		no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)		no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)		no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)	
		medium/high decrease (negative impact)		medium/high decrease (negative impact)		medium/high decrease (negative impact)	

Annex 5. KPI definitions and network structure thresholds

Parent KPIs

Twelve Parent KPIs were distinguished (each with three discrete states). Their names and definitions are presented in Table 9: List of parent KPIs.

Table 9: List of parent KPIs

KPI	Definition
Continuity Under Disruption	Reflects the ability of the river/logistics system to maintain operations during unexpected disruptions (e.g., strikes, equipment failure). Measured by average capacity levels maintained (%) during such events.
Weather Resilience	Measures the system's capacity to continue operations during extreme weather conditions. Includes early warning systems and infrastructure preparedness. Captured as % of incidents anticipated or mitigated per month.
Logistics Continuity	Represents the uninterrupted flow of logistics operations, supported by digitalisation and asset management. Measured through the percentage of digitally connected and monitored logistics assets.
Recycled Materials Use	Assesses the use of recycled materials in construction and maintenance of IWT infrastructure. Expressed as a percentage of total materials used.
EU Compliance Level	Reflects adherence to EU regulatory frameworks, particularly on environmental, safety, and transport standards. Typically tracked by number or percentage of regulations fully implemented.
Shipment Waiting Time	Captures inefficiencies in loading, unloading, or transit processes. Calculated as the average difference between actual and estimated arrival times (in hours or days per shipment).
Corridor Disruption Functionality Rate	Indicates the part of the transport corridor that continues to operate during system-wide disruptions. Typically reported as the % of the network that remains functional.
Recovery time	Measures how efficiently the logistics system recovers from disruptions, factoring in speed and effectiveness of the response. This may relate to TRL of implemented recovery technologies or system-level metrics.
Governance Effectiveness	Assesses the development and implementation of governance frameworks. Tracked by the number of new or updated models adopted in the project.
Shipment Delay	Monitors the difference between scheduled and actual delivery time. Based on comparison with baseline delay data over time
Accidents	Monitors safety performance along the corridor, measured as the number of reported incidents or accidents per month.
Public Perception	Captures the public's view of inland navigation and related logistics services, typically using survey responses from social acceptance studies.

Child KPIs measure final performance outcomes.

Their names and definitions are presented in Table 10.

Table 10: List of Child KPIs

KPI	Definition
Operational Efficiency	Measures how effectively logistics resources are used in freight transport, typically quantified as tonnes transported per kilometre (tonnes/km). Higher efficiency indicates better use of transport capacity and lower cost per unit.
Modal Shift Rate	Tracks the share of freight shifted to inland waterway transport (IWT) from more polluting modes (like road or air). Expressed as a percentage of total freight transported.
Infrastructure Resilience	Assesses the robustness and adaptability of transport infrastructure (e.g., waterways, ports, terminals) under adverse conditions. Quantified by the proportion of infrastructure covered by real-time monitoring and its ability to retain function during disruptions.
Carbon Emissions Reduction	Monitors greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, expressed in CO ₂ -equivalent per tonne-kilometre. A decrease in this KPI indicates environmental improvement.
Energy Consumption	Indicates the total energy consumed per tonne-kilometre (toe/tkm) of transported freight. Lower values suggest greater energy efficiency.

Causal paths between KPI

Table 11 shows selected causal paths between KPIs as defined in the current Bayesian Network framework. These relationships were determined through expert elicitation and system modelling.

Table 11: Causal paths between KPIs

KPI Influencing Others	Influenced KPI 1	Influenced KPI 2	Influenced KPI 3
Operational Efficiency	Energy Consumption	Carbon Emissions	Logistics Continuity
Modal Shift Rate	Carbon Emissions	Energy Consumption	Operational Efficiency
Continuity Under Disruption	Operational Efficiency	Logistics Continuity	Corridor disruption Functionality Rate
Weather Resilience	Continuity Under Disruption	Infrastructure Resilience	Modal Shift Rate
Infrastructure Resilience	Logistics Continuity	Continuity Under Disruption	Operational Efficiency
Logistics Continuity	Operational Efficiency	Shipment Waiting Time	Carbon Emissions
Recycled Materials Use	Carbon Emissions	Public Perception	Energy Consumption
EU Compliance Level	Public Perception	Accident Reduction	Logistics Continuity
Shipment Waiting Time	Operational Efficiency	Shipment Delay	Carbon Emissions
Corridor disruption Functionality Rate	Logistics Continuity	Continuity Under Disruption	Carbon Emissions

KPI Influencing Others	Influenced KPI 1	Influenced KPI 2	Influenced KPI 3
Recovery time	Logistics Continuity	Corridor disruption Functionality Rate	Carbon Emissions
Governance Effectiveness	EU Compliance Level	Corridor disruption Functionality Rate	Public Perception
Shipment Delay	Operational Efficiency	Logistics Continuity	Energy Consumption
Carbon Emissions	Public Perception	EU Compliance Level	Governance Effectiveness
Energy Consumption	Carbon Emissions	Public Perception	EU Compliance Level
Accident Reduction	Public Perception	Operational Efficiency	Shipment Delay
Public Perception	Governance Effectiveness	Modal Shift Rate	

KPI-specific state definitions

The directed relationships between KPIs represent critical causal pathways through which sustainability goals are advanced or hindered. These connections reflect systemic dependencies that must be understood to enable targeted, high-impact interventions.

Table 12: KPI-specific state definitions

KPI	States		
Operational Efficiency	medium/high increase (positive impact)	no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)	medium/high decrease (negative impact)
Modal Shift Rate	medium/high increase (positive impact)	no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)	medium/high decrease (negative impact)
Continuity Under Disruption	High	Moderate	Low or no continuity
Weather Resilience	High	Moderate	Low or no resilience
Infrastructure Resilience	High	Moderate	Low or no resilience
Logistics Continuity	High	Moderate	Low or no continuity
Recycled Materials Use	High	Moderate	Low or no use
EU Compliance Level	High	Moderate	Low or no Compliance
Shipment Waiting Time	medium/high increase (negative impact)	no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)	medium/high decrease (positive impact)
Corridor disruption Functionality Rate	High	Moderate	Low
Recovery time	High	Moderate	Low

KPI	States		
Governance Effectiveness	High	Moderate	Low or no Effectiveness
Shipment Delay	medium/high increase (negative impact)	no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)	medium/high decrease (positive impact)
Carbon Emissions	medium/high increase (positive impact)	no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)	medium/high decrease (negative impact)
Energy Consumption	medium/high increase (negative impact)	no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)	medium/high decrease (positive impact)
Accident Reduction	medium/high increase (negative impact)	no change or low increase/decrease (very low impact)	medium/high decrease (positive impact)
Public Perception	medium/high positive change in perception (positive impact)	no change or very low change in perception (very low impact)	medium/high negative change in perception (negative impact)

Annex 6. Full CPTs and Priors

A full Conditional Probability Table (CPTs) and prior distributions are presented below (Table 8, Table 9). Each KPI has predefined qualitative states, as shown in the main questionnaire table (e.g., *medium/high increase, no change/low, medium/high decrease*). For conciseness and readability in this annex, these states are represented in abbreviated form as shown below, while maintaining full alignment with the original state definitions:

- p = Positive impact
- l = Low or no impact
- n = Negative impact

Table 13: Prior probabilities distribution table

KPI	Prior Probabilities		
	p	l	n
Operational Efficiency	0.95	0.05	0
Modal Shift Rate	0.25	0.75	0
Continuity Under Disruption	0.95	0.05	0
Weather Resilience	0.25	0.75	0
Infrastructure Resilience	0.2	0.8	0
Logistics Continuity	0.6	0.4	0
Recycled Materials Use	0.05	0.95	0
EU Compliance Level	0.35	0.65	0
Shipment Waiting Time	0.15	0.85	0
Corridor disruption Functionality Rate	0.5	0.5	0
Recovery time	0.75	0.25	0
Governance Effectiveness	0.5	0.5	0
Shipment Delay	0.45	0.55	0
Carbon Emissions	0.25	0.75	0
Energy Consumption	0.2	0.8	0
Accident Reduction	0.3	0.7	0
Public Perception	0.85	0.15	0

Table 14: Example of a full Conditional Probability Table (CPT)

				Energy consumption		
Modal Shift Rate	Operational Efficiency	Recycled Materials Use	Shipment Delay	p	l	n
p	p	p	p	0.67	0,20	0,13
p	p	p	l	0.72	0,28	0,00
p	p	p	n	0.80	0,20	0,00
p	p	l	p	0.67	0,20	0,13
p	p	l	l	0.72	0,28	0,00
p	p	l	n	0.80	0,20	0,00
p	p	n	p	0.62	0,25	0,13
p	p	n	l	0.67	0,33	0,00
p	p	n	n	0.75	0,25	0,00
p	l	p	p	0.41	0,46	0,13
p	l	p	l	0.46	0,54	0,00
p	l	p	n	0.54	0,46	0,00
p	l	l	p	0.41	0,46	0,13
p	l	l	l	0.46	0,54	0,00
p	l	l	n	0.54	0,46	0,00
p	l	n	p	0.36	0,51	0,13
p	l	n	l	0.42	0,58	0,00
p	l	n	n	0.49	0,51	0,00
p	n	p	p	0.28	0,25	0,47
p	n	p	l	0.33	0,32	0,34
p	n	p	n	0.41	0,25	0,34
p	n	l	p	0.28	0,25	0,47
p	n	l	l	0.33	0,32	0,34
p	n	l	n	0.41	0,25	0,34
p	n	n	p	0.24	0,29	0,47
p	n	n	l	0.29	0,37	0,34
p	n	n	n	0.36	0,29	0,34
l	p	p	p	0.58	0,29	0,13
l	p	p	l	0.63	0,37	0,00
l	p	p	n	0.71	0,29	0,00

l	p	l	p	0.58	0,29	0,13
l	p	l	l	0.63	0,37	0,00
l	p	l	n	0.71	0,29	0,00
l	p	n	p	0.53	0,34	0,13
l	p	n	l	0.59	0,41	0,00
l	p	n	n	0.66	0,34	0,00
l	l	p	p	0.32	0,55	0,13
l	l	p	l	0.38	0,62	0,00
l	l	p	n	0.45	0,55	0,00
l	l	l	p	0.32	0,55	0,13
l	l	l	l	0.38	0,62	0,00
l	l	l	n	0.45	0,55	0,00
l	l	n	p	0.28	0,59	0,13
l	l	n	l	0.33	0,67	0,00
l	l	n	n	0.41	0,59	0,00
l	n	p	p	0.20	0,33	0,47
l	n	p	l	0.25	0,41	0,34
l	n	p	n	0.32	0,33	0,34
l	n	l	p	0.20	0,33	0,47
l	n	l	l	0.25	0,41	0,34
l	n	l	n	0.32	0,33	0,34
l	n	n	p	0.15	0,38	0,47
l	n	n	l	0.20	0,46	0,34
l	n	n	n	0.28	0,38	0,34
n	p	p	p	0.52	0,15	0,33
n	p	p	l	0.57	0,22	0,20
n	p	p	n	0.65	0,15	0,20
n	p	l	p	0.52	0,15	0,33
n	p	l	l	0.57	0,22	0,20
n	p	l	n	0.65	0,15	0,20
n	p	n	p	0.48	0,19	0,33
n	p	n	l	0.53	0,27	0,20
n	p	n	n	0.61	0,19	0,20
n	l	p	p	0.27	0,40	0,33
n	l	p	l	0.32	0,48	0,20
n	l	p	n	0.39	0,40	0,20

n	l	l	p	0.27	0,40	0,33
n	l	l	l	0.32	0,48	0,20
n	l	l	n	0.39	0,40	0,20
n	l	n	p	0.22	0,45	0,33
n	l	n	l	0.27	0,53	0,20
n	l	n	n	0.35	0,45	0,20
n	n	p	p	0.14	0,19	0,67
n	n	p	l	0.19	0,27	0,54
n	n	p	n	0.27	0,19	0,54
n	n	l	p	0.14	0,19	0,67
n	n	l	l	0.19	0,27	0,54
n	n	l	n	0.27	0,19	0,54
n	n	n	p	0.09	0,24	0,67
n	n	n	l	0.14	0,31	0,54
n	n	n	n	0.22	0,24	0,54

Annex 7. Evolution of KPIs in the CRISTAL Project

The initial Key Results (KRs) were translated into Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) following a framework that utilised lagging (top-down) metrics to measure overall project success and leading (bottom-up) metrics to guide Research and Development and performance monitoring.

A. Original KPIs. (Top-down / Lagging KPIs)

- Contribute with at least a 20 percent increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.
- Assure Inland Waterway Transport capacity at 50 percent even during extreme weather events.
- Improve reliability by 80 percent.
- Reduction of Nitrogen oxides/Sulphur oxides, particulates, Greenhouse gases reported as carbon dioxide equivalent, and particulates as a result of modal shift from road and rail.

B. KPIs Developed in deliverable D1.3. (Bottom-up / Leading KPIs)

- **Efficiency (E):**
 - Capacity levels during extreme weather events (E1).
 - Early warning systems for extreme weather (E2).
 - Capacity levels during (E3).
 - Real-time infrastructure and water level monitoring (E4).
 - Tracked versus total shipments (E5).
 - Operational efficiency (E6).
 - Status updates (E7).
 - Actual versus planned shipments (E8).
 - Delays/Waiting times (E9).
 - Technical readiness level of technologies (E10).
 - Resource availability / Asset management (E11).
 - Operational cost of a fixed route (E12).
 - Overall corridor transit time (E13).
- **Environmental (ENV):**
 - Share of freight transport on IWT (ENV1).
 - Recycled materials (ENV2).
 - Evaluation of material composition applied by IWT infrastructure (ENV3).
 - Nitrogen oxides (ENV4).
 - Particulate matter in micrograms per cubic metre (ENV5).
 - Greenhouse gases reported as carbon dioxide equivalent (ENV6).
 - Energy consumption per tonne kilometre (ENV7).
- **Safety and Social (S):**
 - Number of new or adjusted governance models and solutions, roadmaps and guidelines (S1).
 - Accidents along the transport network (S2).
 - Time to react (S3).
 - Availability of multimodal transport information (S4).
 - Social acceptance survey results (S5).
- **Polish Pilot Specific (UG):**
 - Tons Freight / TEU Freight (UG-1).
 - Barge cargo capacity utilisation (UG-2).
 - IWW share in total supply chain distance in kilometres (UG-3).
 - Total manhours of people involved in supply chain (UG-4).

- **Italian Pilot Specific (ITA):**
 - Users Reservation of Navigation Lock by Multimodal Platform (ITA-1).
 - Navigation Bulletin downloads (ITA-2).
 - Registered users (ITA-3).
 - Navigation forecast points along the river (ITA-4).

C: KPIs Developed in deliverable D6.2 and deployed in D7.2, D8.2, D9.2. (Bottom-up / Leading KPIs)

- **Operational and Economic KPIs:**
 - Tracked versus total shipments (E5).
 - Operational efficiency (E6).
 - Status updates (E7).
 - Actual versus planned shipments (E8).
 - Delays/Waiting times (E9).
 - Operational cost of a fixed route (E12).
 - Overall corridor transit time (E13).
 - Tons transported (UG-1).
 - Barge cargo capacity utilisation (UG-2).
 - IWT share in total supply chain distance (UG-3).
 - Total manhours of staff involved in supply chain per week (UG-4).
 - Users Reservation of Navigation Lock by Multimodal Platform (ITA-1).
 - Navigation Bulletin downloads (ITA-2).
 - Registered users (ITA-3).
 - Navigation forecast points along the river (ITA-4).
- **Environmental KPIs:**
 - Nitrogen oxides in kilograms per tonne kilometre (ENV4).
 - Particulate matter 10 in kilograms per tonne kilometre (ENV5).
 - Greenhouse gases reported as carbon dioxide equivalent in kilograms per tonne kilometre (ENV6).
 - Energy consumption per tonne kilometre in megajoules per tonne kilometre (ENV7).
 - Nitrogen oxides in tonnes (Cold Ironing/Italian Pilot) (ENV4).
- **Social and Specific KPIs:**
 - Social acceptance survey results (Likert scale) (S5).
 - Accidents along the transport network (S2).
 - Availability of multimodal transport information (S4).
 - Automation of freight declarations (French Pilot).
 - Improved knowledge of quay occupancy (French Pilot).
 - Real-time multimodal coordination (French Pilot).
 - Condition monitoring and maintenance prediction (French Pilot).

D: KPIs Developed in WP4 Tasks 4.3 and 4.4. (Bottom-up / Leading KPIs)

- **Economic/Quantification Metrics (SCBA/BMC):**
 - Net Present Value (NPV) of Synchro-modal Corridor Management System solutions.
 - Reduction in waiting time (as a benefit parameter).
 - Improvement of reliability and capacity of IWT (as a benefit parameter).
 - Modal shift towards IWT (as a benefit parameter).
 - Quantification of costs of technologies.
- **BMC Validation Metrics (Polling Scores):**
 - How well the elements of the Finance block were captured (polling score 1-5).
 - Appeal of the offer (SCMS, polling score 1-5).

- Predicted traffic growth (e.g., plus 5 to 30 percent).

E: KPIs Developed in WP10. (Bottom-up / Leading KPIs)

- **Technology Functional Performance Metrics (Task 10.1):**
 - **Acoustic Emission System (AE):** Detect emissions greater than 20 decibels against background noise at less than one millisecond latency.
 - **Acoustic Emission System (AE):** Localisation microcrack error prediction less than 0.5 metres.
 - **Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR):** 80 percent of features detected and identified (SIR-FR-02b KPI).
 - **Smart Buoys (SB):** Depth accuracy less than or equal to plus or minus 0.1 metres.
 - **Smart Buoys (SB):** Velocity accuracy less than or equal to plus or minus 0.1 metres per second.
 - **Smart Buoys (SB):** Temperature accuracy less than or equal to plus or minus 0.5 degrees Celsius.
 - **Smart Buoys (SB):** Telemetry end-to-end latency less than or equal to 120 seconds for the 95th percentile.
 - **Fibre Optic Sensors (FOS):** KPI will be provided in terms of Navigable Height [metres].
- **Operational and Validation Frameworks (Tasks 10.3 and 10.4):**
 - Task 10.3 defined a common operational framework of KPIs to assess the pilots.
 - Task 10.4 developed a Sustainability Validation tool which integrated the outputs of all Work Package 10 tasks.